

Cu suportul Programului Erasmus+ al Uniunii Europene

Studii Europene

11

Chişinău

2018

Studii Europene

11

European Studies

Chisinau

2018

The articles reflect the views only of the authors and ECSA Moldova cannot be held responsible for any use which may be made of the information contained therein.

Publisher:
ECSA Moldova

Gesis-SSOAR

ISSN 2345-1041
ISSN-L 2345-1041

Honorary Council

Co-Presidents:

Prof. Dr. Nico GROENENDIJK, Enschede, Netherlands

Prof. Dr. Dusan SIDJANSKI, Geneva, Switzerland

Vice-Presidents:

Prof. Dr. Carlos Eduardo PACHECO AMARAL, Ponta Delgada, Portugal

Prof. Dr. Ioan HORGA, Oradea, Romania

Prof. Dr. Habil. Helena TENDERA-WLASZCZUK, Cracow, Poland

Members:

Prof. Dr. Francisco ALDECOA LUZARRAGA, Madrid, Spain

Prof. Dr. Habil. Alexandru ARSENI, Chisinau, Moldova

Prof. Dr. Elchin BABAYEV, Baku, Azerbaijan

Prof. Dr. Enrique Lorenzo BANUS IRUSTA, Pamplona, Spain

Prof. Dr. Iordan Gheorghe BARBULESCU, Bucharest, Romania

Prof. Dr. Leonce BEKEMANS, Brussels, Belgium

Prof. Dr. Habil. Christophe BERTOSSI, Paris, France

Prof. Dr. Mircea BRIE, Oradea, Romania

Prof. Dr. Georges CONTOGEOGIS, Athens, Greece

Prof. Dr. Larisa DERIGLAZOVA, Tomsk, Russia

Prof. Dr. Ioan DERSIDAN, Oradea, Romania

Prof. Dr. Gaga GABRICHIDZE, Tbilisi, Georgia

Prof. Dr. Ihar HANCHARONAK, Minsk, Belarus

Prof. Dr. Wilfried HELLER, Potsdam, Germany

Prof. Dr. Asteris HULIARAS, Corinth, Greece

Prof. Dr. Habil. Victor JUC, Chisinau, Moldova

Prof. Dr. Thomas KRUESSMANN, Graz, Austria

Prof. Dr. Anatoliy KRUGLASHOV, Chernivtsi, Ukraine

Prof. Dr. Ariane LANDUYT, Siena, Italy

Prof. Dr. Habil. Ewa LATOSZEK, Warsaw, Poland

Prof. Dr. Ani MATEI, Bucharest, Romania

Prof. Dr. Jose Maria MELLA MARQUEZ, Madrid, Spain

Prof. Dr. Snezana PETROVA, Skopje, Macedonia

Prof. Dr. Oliver REISNER, Berlin, Germany

Prof. Dr. Maria Manuela TAVARES RIBEIRO, Coimbra, Portugal

Prof. Dr. Grigore SILASI, Timisoara, Romania

Prof. Dr. Mihai SLEAHTITCHI, Chisinau, Moldova

Prof. Dr. Tudorel TOADER, Iasi, Romania

Prof. Dr. Habil. Grigore VASILESCU, Chisinau, Moldova

Scientific Committee

Co-Presidents:

Assoc. Prof. Dr. Marta PACHOCKA, Warsaw, Poland

Dr. Victoria RODRIGUEZ PRIETO, Madrid, Spain

Vice-Presidents:

Assoc. Prof. Dr. Diana EERMA, Tartu, Estonia

Dr. Mihaela Narcisa NIEMCZIK-ARAMBASA, Potsdam, Germany

Assoc. Prof. Dr. Anna VISVIZI, Athens, Greece

Members:

Assoc. Prof. Dr. Paulo Emilio VAUTHIER BORGES DE MACEDO, Rio de Janeiro, Brazil

Assoc. Prof. Dr. Paulo Jorge TAVARES CANELAS DE CASTRO, SAR Macau, China

Assoc. Prof. Dr. Georgeta CISLARU, Paris, France

Assoc. Prof. Dr. Simion COSTEA, Targu-Mures, Romania

Assoc. Prof. Dr. Klara CZIMRE, Debrecen, Hungary

Lecturer Dr. Dorin DOLGHI, Oradea, Romania

Senior Lecturer Dr. Sanna ELFVING, Bradford, United Kingdom

Assoc. Prof. Dr. Sedef EYLEMER, Izmir, Turkey

Assoc. Prof. Dr. Agnieszka KLOS, Warsaw, Poland

Assoc. Prof. Dr. Eva KOVAROVA, Ostrava, Czechia

Assoc. Prof. Dr. Aurelian LAVRIC, Chisinau, Moldova

Assoc. Prof. Dr. Kerry LONGHURST, Warsaw, Poland

Dr. Jose Luis DE SALES MARQUES, SAR Macau, China

Lecturer Dr. Marius MATICHESCU, Timisoara, Romania

Assoc. Prof. Dr. Cristina-Maria MATIUTA, Oradea, Romania

Senior Lecturer Dr. Anne MCNAUGHTON, Canberra, Australia

Assoc. Prof. Dr. Solomon MENABDISHVILI, Tbilisi, Georgia

Senior Lecturer Dr. Mihaela Daciana NATEA, Targu-Mures, Romania

Lecturer Giancarlo NICOLI, Rome, Italy

Assoc. Prof. Dr. Danielle OMER, Le Mans, France

Lecturer Dr. Moses ONYANGO, Nairobi, Kenya
Assoc. Prof. Dr. Marco OROFINO, Milan, Italy
Assoc. Prof. Dr. Saverina PASHO, Tirana, Albania
Assoc. Prof. Dr. Valentin PETRUSENKO, Plovdiv, Bulgaria
Dr. Vadim PISTRINCIUC, Chisinau, Moldova
Assoc. Prof. Dr. Galina POGONET, Chisinau, Moldova
Lecturer Dr. Istvan Jozsef POLGAR, Oradea, Romania
Lecturer Dr. Ada-Iuliana POPESCU, Iasi, Romania
Assoc. Prof. Dr. Lehte ROOTS, Tallinn, Estonia
Assoc. Prof. Dr. Iryna SIKORSKA, Kiev, Ukraine
Assoc. Prof. Dr. Habil. Zorina SISCAN, Chisinau, Moldova
Lecturer Dr. Beatrice STEFANESCU, Iasi, Romania
Assoc. Prof. Dr. Alina STOICA, Oradea, Romania
Assoc. Prof. Dr. Aleksandra SZCZERBA-ZAWADA, Gorzow Wielkopolski,
Poland
Senior Lecturer Dr. Jean-Marc TROUILLE, Bradford, United Kingdom
Assoc. Prof. Dr. Lika TSULADZE, Tbilisi, Georgia
Assoc. Prof. Dr. Penine UWIMBABAZI, Butare, Rwanda
Assoc. Prof. Dr. Alexis VAHLAS, Strasbourg, France
Assoc. Prof. Dr. Diego VARELA PEDREIRA, A Coruna, Spain
Lecturer Dr. Tigran YEPREMYAN, Yerevan, Armenia
Senior Lecturer Dr. Khaydarali YUNUSOV, Tashkent, Uzbekistan

Editorial Board

Editor-in-Chief:

Assoc. Prof. Dr. Vasile CUCERESCU, Chisinau, Moldova

First Deputy Editor-in-Chief:

Prof. Dr. Habil. Ludmila ROSCA, Chisinau, Moldova

Deputy Editor-in-Chief:

Assoc. Prof. Dr. Mihai HACHI, Chisinau, Moldova

Editors:

Assoc. Prof. Dr. Ion BURUIANA, Chisinau, Moldova

Assoc. Prof. Dr. Carolina DODU-SAVCA, Chisinau, Moldova

Assoc. Prof. Dr. Violeta MELNIC, Chisinau, Moldova

Prof. Dr. Habil. Elena PRUS, Chisinau, Moldova

Assoc. Prof. Dr. Alexandru ZNAGOVAN, Chişinău, Moldova

Contents:

Cultural Aspects and Human Rights of Minors in the Process of Marriage in the European Union <i>Kristi JOAMETS, Lehte ROOTS</i>	11
Educational Policies in the European Union: Actuality and Practical Significance <i>Ludmila CUROS</i>	35
European Monetary Union (EMU): Proposal for an Index on Financial Inequalities to Be Added to the Official Indexes of Maastricht <i>Lamberto LAURENTI</i>	45
Good Governance over Natural Resources: Legal Aspects of Transparency Policy <i>Nilyufar ABDULATOVA</i>	57
Greek Youth and the EU: What is the Relationship and How Can It Be Improved <i>Anna VALLIANATOEU, Dimitris THOMAKOS, Yannis MASTROGEORGIU, Evi HATZIANDREOU</i>	77
Migrants' Social Integration through Understanding and Communication. Holistic Approach <i>Ludmila ROSCA</i>	95
Problems of Attracting Venture Capital to the Republic of Moldova and Development of the Infrastructure of Venture Investment in the Conditions of European Integration <i>Tatiana ANDREEVA</i>	113
The Divergences in the Negotiation Process between Turkey and the European Union <i>Emilia Nicoleta SCHIOP, Mircea BRIE</i>	123
The Level of Competition in Public Procurement in the Republic of Moldova in the Light of International Commitments <i>Dorina HARCENCO</i>	143
The Rational Choice Theory as the Explanation of Coalition Formation in Germany 2017-2018	

<i>Viktoriiia KHOMENKO, Oleksandr DEMIANCHUK</i>	161
Who's Who	179

Cultural Aspects and Human Rights of Minors in the Process of Marriage in the European Union

Dr. Kristi JOAMETS

kristi.ioamets@ttu.ee

Assoc. Prof. Dr. Lehte ROOTS

lehte.roots@ttu.ee

Tallinn University of Technology, Estonia

Abstract. This article is elaborating ideas of right of minors to marry and possible human rights concerns related to this phenomenon. Due to the immigration to European Union the values and culture is in the process of change and not always in the direction that European countries expect. EU has created rules for family reunification and measures against trafficking; nevertheless the family law seems to be something that EU states do not have a common interest to regulate. Some ideas and solutions are provided to tackle the abovementioned phenomenon.

Keywords: marriage of minors, human rights of minors, EU law, culture and values.

Introduction

Marriage of minors is a phenomenon that should get attention in the context of population changes in Europe. Different values and cultural changes, polygamous marriages and performed violence which are related to marriages of minors is a concern of human rights. Though there are many international conventions providing rules to forbid or prevent child marriages and states, where such marriage is a common practice, have joined those conventions, the problem still exists and the numbers that are describing the violation of human rights are devastating. Theoretical and also practical question to be discussed is the conflict between international law and local law¹ combined with religion or traditions. The situation

¹ E.g. when the principles of human rights are incorporated into the constitutions of those states.

becomes more complicated in case the same practice takes place in Europe, performed by the migrants. Marriage of minors and the protection of their rights is not a problem of regions far away, but also here, in the middle of Europe.

International practice shows that mere legal norm forbidding child marriage is not sufficient, it is important to know how to interpret and implement in practice the protective legal norms in the situation of conflict and related to religion or tradition. Common solution for the problem is a non-recognition of such marriages but this seems to be not sufficient. Mere practice of non-recognition does not always protect a child, as this action can deprive a child from other rights she² obtains by the marriage. Therefore, the protection of the minor must consider several aspects related to the colliding rights.

This article analyses marriage of minors in the context of international and local law, religion and traditions. Also children and women's rights, as rights derived directly from the human rights are discussed in a smaller extent, to characterise the problem. Focus of the article is on the conflict between human rights and religions or traditions in Europe.

Marriage of minors

Marriage of a minor is a marriage engaged beyond the age of 18. Concepts of marriage of a minor and forced marriage are often treated together³ because marriage of a minor is often forced marriage.⁴ According

² In an article the focus of child marriage is the female minor, for that a word "she" is used to refer to the child.

³ NGO states that any child marriage is a forced marriage because a child is not mature to understand the meaning of marriage. A term "servile marriage" is used for marriages similar to slavery. See at Pokhari F. Stolen Futures. Trafficking for Forced Child Marriage in the UK. ECPAT UK, 2009. 16. Forward, Child and Forced Marriage. [online] Available from <http://www.forwarduk.org.uk/key-issues/child-marriage>. However, the authors of the article state that in respect of maturity there should be noted that in cases state evaluates the maturity of the child and gives a consent to marry based on this maturity control, marriage of an minor cannot be considered as a forced marriage only because of an age.

to many human rights conventions marriage before the age of 18 is harmful and discriminative, child marriage is considered as a violation of human rights violating the article 16(2) of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UDHR)⁵, which states that “Marriage shall be entered into only with the free and full consent of the intending spouses.” Article 16 of the Convention on the Elimination of all Forms of Discrimination Against Women (CEDAW)⁶ states that women should have the same right as men to “freely choose a spouse and to enter into marriage only with their free and full consent”, and that the “betrothal and marriage of a child shall have no legal effect”⁷. The Convention on the Rights of the Child (CRC)⁸ sets out the rights of children: the right to survive; the right to develop to their fullest; the right to protection from harmful practices, abuse and exploitation, and the right to participate fully in family, cultural and social life. Besides those conventions, child marriage violates the rights provided by the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights⁹, the Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights¹⁰, the Convention on the Consent of to Marriage, Minimum Age for Marriage and Registration of Marriages¹¹ and the Supplementary Convention on the Abolition of Slavery, the Slave Trade, and

⁴ Forced marriages differ from arranged marriages. In forced marriages, one or both of the partners cannot give free or valid consent to the marriage. In arranged marriages, the parents and families play a leading role in arranging the marriage, but the individuals getting married can nonetheless choose whether to marry or not. Forced and child marriage. Stop Violence Against Woman. A project of the Advocates for Human Rights. http://www.stopvaw.org/forced_and_child_marriage

⁵ <http://www.un.org/en/documents/udhr/>

⁶ <http://www.un.org/womenwatch/daw/cedaw/>

⁷ CEDAW General Recommendation No. 21 (1994) provides, with respect to Article 16 that the form and concept of the family can vary from State to State, and even between regions within a State. Whatever form it takes, and whatever the legal system, religion, custom or tradition within the country, the treatment of women in the family both at law and in private must accord with the principles of equality and justice for all people, as article 2 of the convention requires.

⁸ <http://www.ohchr.org/en/professionalinterest/pages/crc.aspx>

⁹ <http://www.ohchr.org/en/professionalinterest/pages/ccpr.aspx>

¹⁰ <http://www.ohchr.org/EN/ProfessionalInterest/Pages/CESCR.aspx>

¹¹ <http://www.ohchr.org/EN/ProfessionalInterest/Pages/MinimumAgeForMarriage.aspx>

Institutions and Practices Similar to Slavery¹², e.g. the right to equality on grounds of sex and age, the right to marry and found a family, the right to life, the right to the highest attainable standard of health, the right to education and development and the right to be free from slavery etc. In general, the forced and child marriage can be characterised as a crime against humanity under international law.¹³ These are only some international legal acts illustrating the protection of the minor from a marriage.

Efforts, to address marriage of minors in many parts of the world, date back to the 1920s. Legal reforms began to gain ground in the 1970s and 1980s, as countries such as Bangladesh, India¹⁴ and Indonesia established or raised the legal minimum age of marriage for girl to 18.¹⁵ Many states have set up a registration system for customary marriages to control the age of marriage, but considering that every year around 40 million births in a world are unregistered, one can understand that these are the minors, having no protection at all, against age-related abuses.¹⁶ Frequently, the failure to register the marriage, does not affect the validity of the marriage.¹⁷ Human rights activists and the United Nations have launched efforts to address

¹² <http://www.ohchr.org/EN/ProfessionalInterest/Pages/SupplementaryConventionAbolitionOfSlavery.aspx>

¹³ Gong-Gershowitz J. Forced Marriage: A “New” Crime Against Humanity?, 8 Nw. J. Int'l Hum. Rts. 53 (2009). <http://scholarlycommons.law.northwestern.edu/njihr/vol8/iss1/3/>; Bensouda F. “Gender Justice and the ICC: Progress and Reflections”. International Conference: 10 years review of the ICC. Justice for All? The International Criminal Court. Statement. Sydney. 14 February 2012, 2.

¹⁴ See Nichols J. A. 2013. Multi-Tiered Marriage. Reconsidering the Boundaries of Civil Law and Religion. Marriage and Divorce in a Multicultural Context. (ed. Nichols J. A.) Cambridge University Press, 11-59, 36.

¹⁵ See Malhotra A., Warner A., McGonagle A., Lee-Rife S. Solutions to End Child Marriage. What the evidence shows. ICRW. 2011. www.icrw.org/childmarriage, 4.

¹⁶ Ross S.D. 2008. Woman’s Human Rights. The International and Comparative Law Casebook. Chapter 14. Women’s Reproductive Rights. Philadelphia. University of Pennsylvania Press. 571-637, 635.

¹⁷ See Nichols, 53.

harmful traditional practices affecting women.¹⁸ Undoubtedly a lot has been done¹⁹, but fight for the human rights in the context of conflict of religion and traditions is very complicated. Despite the global rules, forbidding marriage of minors, there are still too many states, where based on traditions and cultural beliefs, marriage of a minor is common, threatening the rights of the children concerned. Based on data of UNICEF “Around 650 million girls and women alive today were married in childhood, and unless progress is accelerated, that number will remain at least as high through 2030”.²⁰ The highest rates are in West Africa, South Asia, North Africa/Middle East, India, Afganistan, Nicaragua etc.²¹ Numbers describe expressively, how many children suffer from the brutal curtailment of childhood and a violation of the rights of the child. According to Myers “13.5 million girls around the world marry before their eighteenth birthday every year. Based on current trends, 142 million girls will be married in the decade to 2020. That makes an average of 14.2 million girls every year”.²²

Globally, the minors who marry before 18 years are mainly girls and unfortunately it is not only a question of girls from age 15 to 17, but also starting from age 9 or even younger.²³ Practice of marriages of minors is

¹⁸ See Malhotra et al, 4; UNFA-UNICEF Global Programme to Accelerate Action to end child Marriages. 2018. https://www.unicef.org/protection/57929_92681.html

¹⁹ Thorton states that many changes in ideas and behaviour have permeated to the grassroots by teaching children the human rights and challenging by this the authority of their parents. (Thorton A. 2012. International Family Change and Continuity. The Past and Future from the Developmental Idealism Perspective. Marriage at the Crossroads. Law, Policy, and the Brave New World of Twenty-First-Century Families. (ed. Garrison M. and Scott E.S.)). 30- 53, 41.

²⁰ UNFA-UNICEF Global Programme to Accelerate Action to end child Marriages. 2018. https://www.unicef.org/protection/57929_92681.html

²¹ See Malhotra et al, 3. Raj et al, 1883.

²² Myers.

²³ See the Statement by EU High Representative Catherine Ashton on child marriage in Yemen. Brussels, 13 September 2013 A 456/3 - /... “I am appalled by reports of the death of an 8 year old Yemeni girl from serious injuries, including internal bleeding, sustained on her wedding night. I urge the Yemeni authorities to investigate this case without delay and to prosecute all those responsible for this crime.../. Available at: www.consilium.europa.eu/uedocs/cms_data/.../138730.pdf (16.12.2013).

often influenced by the poverty. Especially in rural areas, parents may consider girls as an economic burden for families, and therefore they are married off, as soon as they reach puberty.²⁴ According to Myers, “War, extreme poverty, recurrent natural disasters, political volatility, migration, displacement and unreliable economic conditions create fear and anxiety that leaves children particularly exposed to abuse and exploitation”.²⁵ Common is the practice that daughters are married off before choosing a bride for the sons and an unmarried daughter can even hinder the marriages of other children in a family.²⁶

The reason of marriages of minors can also be to receive a bride fee and a fear that better-educated boys can demand a higher dowry.²⁷ On the other hand as Myers states “fear of rape and sexual violence, of unwanted pre-marital pregnancies, the shame and dishonour of a family, of homelessness and hunger or starvation are all reported by parents and children as legitimate reasons for premature marriage. Poverty, weak legislative frameworks and enforcement, harmful traditional practices, gender discrimination and lack of alternative opportunities for girls (especially education) are all major drivers of early marriage that are strengthened by the fear and anxiety symptomatic of fragile contexts. As a result, parents and girls resort to early marriage as a protection against both real and perceived risks.”²⁸

Many studies provide that marriage before the age of 18 has many negative impacts for the health and education of the child.²⁹ It makes children vulnerable to sexual and other forms of physical violence and abuse.³⁰ Minors often die in the percouse of pregnancy and childbirth

²⁴ See Khanna et al, 6.

²⁵ Myers, 10.

²⁶ Maertens, 1.

²⁷ Khanna et al, 6.

²⁸ Myers, 8.

²⁹ Right to Education Project. Promoting Mobilisation and Legal accountability. Available at: <http://www.right-to-education.org/node/58> (16.12.2013).

³⁰ See Khanna T., Verma R., Weiss E. Child Marriage in South Asia: Realities, Responses and the Way Forward. “Solidarity for the Children of SAARC”. 2013. Available at: www.icrw.org/

complications³¹, also infants they give a birth to, are more likely to die.³² Married girls describe their marriage as lonely life, which is cutting them off from friends and family.³³ Furthermore marriages of minors may also mask child prostitution.³⁴

Laquer Estin states, that “in homogeneous societies, these different normative frameworks reflect widely shared values, reinforcing a common understanding of what marriage and family life should be. In more diverse societies, the range of normative variations expands and individuals may face contrasting opportunities and constraints from official and unofficial norms of family behaviour.”³⁵ According to Bix, “in a world of diverse marital regimes and growing decentralization of marriage regimes, there is at least one obvious role for a state: to set boundaries – namely minimum terms that will ensure that vulnerable parties (including third parties to marriage arrangements, in particular children) are not badly harmed.” He gives a following example – “the government might reasonably reject recognition of a marriage of an eight-year-old, even if this standard is accepted within a particular religious community.”³⁶

.../child-marriage-south-asia-realities-respons..., 2; see Child Marriage Facts and Figures. Available at: <http://www.icrw.org/child-marriage-facts-and-figures> (16.12.2013).

³¹ See also Chandra-Mouli V., Camacho A. V. and Michaud P.-A. 2013. WHO Guidelines on Preventing Early Pregnancy and Poor Reproductive Outcomes Among Adolescents in Developing Countries. *Journal of Adolescent Health* 52. Elsevier Inc. 517-522.

³² Khanna et al, 10.

³³ Bruce J., Clark S. 2004. “The implications of early marriage for HIV/AIDS policy”, brief based on background paper prepared for the WHO/UNFPA/Population Council Technical Consultation on Married Adolescents. New York: Population Council. The Population Council, Inc., 2. See also Raj et al; and about the marital quality and the age of marriage in Nepal Allendorf K., Ghimire D. J. 2013. Determinants of marital quality in an arranged marriage society. *Social Science Research* 42, 59-70. Elsevier.

³⁴ Ross S.D. 2008. *Woman’s Human Rights. The International and Comparative Law Casebook*. Chapter 9. CEDAW in Practice. Philadelphia. University of Pennsylvania Press. 326-368, 328.

³⁵ Laquer Estin A. L. 2013. *Unofficial Family Law. Marriage and Divorce in a Multicultural Context*. (ed. Nichols J. A.) Cambridge University Press 92-119, 92.

³⁶ See Bix B. H. 2013. *Pluralism and Decentralization in Marriage Regulation. Marriage and Divorce in a Multicultural Context*. (ed. Nichols J. A.) Cambridge University Press, 60-77, 71.

Despite the fact that most of the states where marriage of minors is practiced, have laws forbidding marriage before age 18, the marriage of minors is still a common practice even in the present-day circumstances. States in which the marriage of minors is practiced have joined conventions³⁷ protecting human rights³⁸ and forbidding marriages of minors³⁹, but the enforcement of the established rules is complicated – “/.../limited implementation machinery, poor coordination and convergence amongst various stakeholders, and limited awareness of the act are some examples of the weak enforcement of the law”⁴⁰ these are widely referred reasons. Gaffney-Rhys demonstrates that though “the civil law establishes an appropriate minimum age for marriage, but those bound by local customary law or religious law, e.g. Islamic law do not have to comply”. He argues that “the states do not follow the civil law, in many cases the national constitution is silent as to the relationship between civil law and customary law and does not therefore prioritise the former over the

³⁷ For example the Convention to Eliminate all forms of Discrimination against Women 1979 (CEDAW art 16), the UN Convention on the Rights of the Child 1989, the Hague Convention on the Celebration and Recognition of Marriages 1978, the UN Declaration of Human Rights 1948, the African Charter on Human and People’s Rights 2004, the African Charter on the Rights and Welfare of the Child 1990.

³⁸ However, sometimes with reservation but those reservations cannot lead to the non-compliance of the convention but narrowly specify the justified exceptions. These reservations cannot be incapable with the object and purpose of the treaties (see Ross S.D. 2008. *Woman’s Human Rights. The International and Comparative Law Casebook*. Chapter 1. *Women’s Status and CEDAW*. Philadelphia. University of Pennsylvania Press. 1-53, 45.

³⁹ Office of the United Nations High Commissioner for Human Rights emphasizes in Gender Equality Policy (2011) state, that by applying the principle of universality in gender integration and in the promotion of women’s rights, it is important to ensure that the cultures and their diversity, religious values and traditional practices do not negatively impact women. Available at: http://www.google.ee/url?sa=t&rct=j&q=&esrc=s&source=web&cd=1&ved=0CCoQFjAA&url=http%3A%2F%2Fwww2.ohchr.org%2Fenglish%2Fissues%2Fwomen%2Fdocs%2FGenderEqualityPolicy_September2011.pdf&ei=Q2fOUsXfCMYqhQf3l4DwCQ&usg=AFQjCNFvq-4fjDajE2EB6BxZvhk8T0ay9A&sig2=Aun-qi6OlfnkWjeMahA0-w&bvm=bv.59026428,d.ZG4 (pdf)

⁴⁰ Khanna et al, 6.

latter”⁴¹. However, likewise polygamy and genital mutilation also marriage of a minor can be considered as an individual interest, that Ross describes “has over ages been “clothed” in unsubstantiated claims of preservation of traditional values and religious sanctions”⁴².

Bruce and Clark refer to the fact that though CRC offers a cross-cultural definition of “childhood” (up to age 18) and a detailed vision of the needs and rights of children and their evolving capacities, yet it allows countries to apply these rights and protections only on the unmarried.⁴³ This legal construction reflects and is justified by a long-standing cultural norm – that marriage, regardless of age, confers adult status.⁴⁴ Bruce and Clark refer also to the third understanding that “a married girl is “taken care of” and has passed from the “protection” of her natal kin to that of her husband”.⁴⁵ This leads to the situation where minors’s rights are not protected.

Despite the declaration of protecting the minor’s rights, in practice the states accept violations of her rights. There is no doubt that human rights must prevail over cultural relativism and regional fragmentation. De Cruz describes it as “a culture of human rights”.⁴⁶ Kerikmäe and Nyman-Metcalf state referring to Abiad ⁴⁷ that “although no religion holds the monopoly on affecting human rights, the interrelationship between Islam and human rights is the most debated. Apart from political reasons for this,

⁴¹ Gaffney-Rhys R. 2012. “A comparison of child marriage and polygamy from a human rights perspective: are the arguments equally cogent?”. *Journal of Social Welfare and Family Law* 34, 1. Taylor & Francis 2012, 49-61, 50.

⁴² Ross S.D. 2008. *Woman’s Human Rights. The International and Comparative Law Casebook*. Chapter 13. Gender and Polygyny: Religion, Culture, Equality in Marriage. Philadelphia. University of Pennsylvania Press. 512-570, 569.

⁴³ Bruce and Clark, 1. Khanna et al, 7.

⁴⁴ Bruce and Clark, p 1. Ross defines such children as “statistically invisible as children” explaining further that through the marriage a man having sex with a girl younger than 14 is not a criminal. See Ross S.D. 2008. *Woman’s Human Rights. The International and Comparative Law Casebook*. Chapter 14. Women’s Reproductive Rights. Philadelphia. University of Pennsylvania Press. 571-637, 630.

⁴⁵ Bruce and Clark, 2.

⁴⁶ De Cruz P. 2010. *Family Law, Sex and Society. A comparative Study of Family Law*. Routledge: London and New York, 336.

⁴⁷ Abiad. 2008, 51-52.

the fact that Islam contains a special legal system through the so called Sharia law brings the issue to the forefront. The status of Sharia in Muslim countries (apart from the expressly secular ones like Turkey) is at the top of the substantive law hierarchy as an incontrovertible norm but the real impact is weakened by concurrent secular legislation. The impact of Sharia is mainly felt in family law (and inheritance)."⁴⁸ Related to woman rights, there is an idea of complete control over women in Islam.⁴⁹ However, Ross gives an example from the monitoring of the Women's Convention: [t]he Sharia itself gave equality to woman, but the problem that had to be overcome was that of interpretation."⁵⁰

So, the obstacle to protect women and children is not the Islamic law itself but its interpretation serving the rights and power of certain group – e.g. men with purpose to preserve patriarchal order and hence supporting certain interpretation of Islamic rules. In African countries often religion has been referred to justify child marriages, but this is more of tradition than religion. One can ask which of them two, tradition or religion, is the stronger justification for violence? In the context of human rights none of them. One can also ask which of them is weaker and easier to change? It is impossible to predict – it depends on the social changes, spread and understanding of the human dignity and violence.

In the process of fighting against marriages of minors it is important to understand that legal norms are only one tool. Certainly, they provide the principles, but intending to change the understanding of special social group these principles and how they gain the society and individual must be explained to this group. Cultural identity often prevails over individual

⁴⁸ See Kerikmäe and Nyman-Metcalf, 46-47.

⁴⁹ See Ross S.D. 2008. *Woman's Human Rights. The International and Comparative Law Casebook*. Chapter 12. FGM and Footbinding: Imperialism or Women's human Rights? Philadelphia. University of Pennsylvania Press. 461-511, 495.

⁵⁰ Ross S.D. 2008. *Woman's Human Rights. The International and Comparative Law Casebook*. Chapter 1. *Woman's Status and CEDAW*. 1-53. 46 and Chapter 12. FGM and Footbinding: Imperialism or Women's Human Rights? Philadelphia. University of Pennsylvania Press. 461-511, 495.

interests, but in relation to marriages of minors, a child is a victim and needs a protection.

Violence against women in a form of physical assault, harassment, emotional abuse, sexual assault, deprivation of resources, destruction of property, torture or confinement violates the woman's rights to be free of violence and prevents woman's ability to realize other rights, the situation when a woman is still a minor is more complicated, as a child is not mature enough to protect herself at least in some respect. Even though, there are measures of control over the performance of the principles provided by the conventions protecting women rights and children rights are incorporated into the state's legal order, it can still be bare and formal tool, in case the whole social, economic and political order is not changed ensuring the realization of all the rights, every single individual has.⁵¹

Marriage of a minor violates many international rights of the child. For the same reasons the states declare, that they do not accept marriages of minors and have joined the conventions related to the rights of the child. However, the states frequently cannot manage to avoid such marriages. The numbers of marriages of minors in a world characterise a realistic situation, where too many children are violated and abused mentally and physically. On one hand it is understandable, that it is difficult to change the traditions far away from Europe, where the poverty complicates the situation, but unfortunately marriages of minors, exist also in Europe where human rights have a visible and permanent place in the European values.

Marriage of a minor in Europe

Marriages of minors have reached to Europe via immigration flows. Marriage of a minor in Europe is a spread practice, in those migration

⁵¹ Drzewski K. 1999. Chapter 3. Inimõiguste rahvusvahelikustamine ja õiguslikustamine. Rahvusvahelised inimõigused ja nende kaitse. Sissejuhatav käsiraamat. (Internationalisation and legalisation of human rights. International human rights and their protection. Introductory handbook) (Sepper M.-L., Erne J., Lindpere H. Ed. of Estonian edition). Original: An introduction to the International protection of human rights: a textbook (Ed. Hanski R. and Suksi M).Turku Åbo Akademi University, Institute for Human Rights. Second edition.

groups, who practice it also in their states of origin. Children born in Europe are often married according to the traditions of certain social groups. They can be sent to the countries of origin to marry and though EU does not recognise such marriages, they continue living their traditional family life in Europe, based on their traditions. This leads to quitting the school, bearing children and serving their husbands. Such practise is violating their rights, but is justified by religion and traditions. It is logical that it is much easier to fight against child marriages in EU member state, than far away in some African, Arab or Asian state where it is part of a tradition and culture. Unfortunately also in Europe the questions related to marriages of minors are complicated and hard to avoid or solve. Despite the principle that human rights should prevail over religion and traditions, a tolerance of different cultures, can lead to the situation where EU member states find themselves obliged to accept the practices violating the children rights.⁵² The fact is that too many immigrants tend to isolate themselves culturally from the states they are living in, by maintaining the authoritarian family structures and traditions.⁵³

German politician Sarrazin describes the situation in Germany as following: “the obedient muslim-girl will marry according to the common custom, though against her own will, with the young man found by her father and is forced to quit the school for that reason. Struggle to get free from the family bounds, leads to the violence, forced leave to Turkey and in

⁵² Council of Europe, Parliamentary Assembly states in its resolution again in 2005 (the first similar statement was made in 1954 (see United Nations General Assembly Resolution 843 (IX)) that it is outraged by the fact that, under the cloak of respect for the culture and traditions of migrant communities, there are authorities which tolerate forced marriages and child marriages although they violate the fundamental rights of each and every victim (clause 3). And, clause 5 proves that since it infringes the fundamental human rights of the individual, forced marriage can in no way be justified. <http://www.refworld.org/docid/43f5d5184.html>

⁵³ See also Sarrazin, 241. See Pokhari F. Stolen Futures. Trafficking for Forced Child Marriage in the UK. ECPAT UK, 2009. 15.

worst case honor killing”.⁵⁴ Sarrazin states also that in Germany 90% of immigrants from Turkey marry with Turks; about 60% Turks with German passport marry with spouses brought from Turkey. Such import-spouses are exclusively with very low education and often close kins, which produces mental disabilities for children.⁵⁵ In England a survey about trafficking of forced marriages shows that the reasons of marriages of minors are the same as worldwide – to maintain family ties, improve an economic position of a family, both in UK or abroad, and for spouses to gain permanent residence in the UK. Based on a research the Forced Marriage Unit, the central government unit dealing with forced marriage casework and policy in UK, handles an average 300 to 500 cases of forced marriages annually, 30% of which are children.⁵⁶ However, this is considered to be only the tip of the iceberg.⁵⁷ Based on a survey of EU Agency of Fundamental Rights (2014) the Swedish National Board for Youth Affairs estimated that in 2011 there were 2500 adolsents who were worried that they will not be allowed to choose whom they want to marry.⁵⁸ A French survey (2008) showed that “non-consensual marriage” was experienced by 4% of immigrant woman and 2% of daughters of immigrants.⁵⁹ Based on a survey of European Union

⁵⁴ Sarrazin T. Saksamaa käib maha. Ohtlik mäng oma riigiga. 2013. (ed. Enno M.) OÜ Hea Lugu ja Janno Toots. Tallinna Raamatutrükikoda, (original edition: Deutschland schaff sich ab. Wie wir unser Land aufs Spiel setzen. 2010 Deutsche Verlags-Anstalt), 281.

⁵⁵ See Sarrazin, 283 and Huschek D., de Valk H., A., G. and Liefbroer A. C. 2012. Partner Choice Patterns Among the Descendants of Turkish Immigrants in Europe. *Eur J Population* 28: 241-268. Springer.

⁵⁶ Pokhari F. Stolen Futures. Trafficing for Forced Child Marriage in the UK. ECPAT UK, 2009. 8.

⁵⁷ Pokhari F. Stolen Futures. Trafficing for Forced Child Marriage in the UK. ECPAT UK, 2009. 8.

⁵⁸ Addressing forced marriage in the EU: legal provisions and promising practices. European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights. 2014. Publications Office of the European Union. Luxemburg, 9.

⁵⁹ Addressing forced marriage in the EU: legal provisions and promising practices. European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights. 2014. Publications Office of the European Union. Luxemburg, 9.

Agency of Fundamental Rights (2014) about 2% of Roma girls at age of 10-15 are married following the traditions.⁶⁰

Actually, it seems that EU member states are very well informed about the violation of the rights of the children linked to marriages. But the practice shows weak objection against it. Although forced marriages are criminalised in many member states, it is evident that initiate a criminal process of such a case is complicated for a state. One of the solutions to protect the minors from the forced marriages has been the increase of age to be able to marry for a non-EU citizen.⁶¹ But this is a tool that from the other hand may violate the rights of a child. Because the general principle of marriageable age is maturity. In respect to this, a minor should be able to marry when she is mature enough, in the European framework this is controlled carefully by state in every single case.

Inglehart and Baker state that “in the 20th century modernization was widely viewed as a uniquely western process that non-Western societies could follow only in so far as they abandoned their traditional cultures and assimilated technologically and morally “superior” to western ways.”⁶² However, they explain also that “the influences are not one-direction-like but mutual: religious⁶³ traditional values can be so powerful that can prevail in any situation.”⁶⁴ On the other hand Menski describes the situation as “being blinded by the supposedly dangerous threats of “tradition” and “religion”, however, noting that forced marriages can cause

⁶⁰ Addressing forced marriage in the EU: legal provisions and promising practices. European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights. 2014. Publications Office of the European Union. Luxemburg, 13.

⁶¹ See Gangoli G., Chantler K. 2009. Protecting Victims of Forced Marriage: Is Age a Protective Factor? *Fem Leg Stud* 17:267-288, 275.

⁶² Inglehart R., Baker W. F. 2000. Modernization, Cultural Change, And the Persistence of Traditional Values. *American Sociological Review*, Vol 65, 19-51, 19.

⁶³ Jänterä-Järeborg uses even a term “religiously motivated practice”. See Jänterä-Järeborg M. The legal scope for religious identity in family matters. *The Place of Religion in Family Law: A Comparative Search* (Eds Mair J and Örucü E), Intersentia, Cambridge-Antwerp-Portland, 2011, 73-96, 81.

⁶⁴ Inglehart and Baker, 22.

problems.⁶⁵ Jäntera-Järeborg states that the mix of religion and law leads to the question what the legal system should protect: religion or person's right to private life and family life under the ECHR.⁶⁶ Prevailed consideration is still that human rights prevail over religion and traditions.⁶⁷

Declaration on the Elimination of All Forms of Intolerance and of Discrimination Based on Religion or Belief (1981) at 3 provides that "discrimination between human beings on grounds of religion or belief constitutes an affront to human dignity and a disavowal of the principles of the Charter of the United Nations, and shall be condemned as a violation of the human rights and fundamental freedoms proclaimed in the UDHR and enunciated in detail in the International Covenants on Human Rights, and as an obstacle to friendly and peaceful relations between nations". Undoubtedly, also the protection of a child prevails⁶⁸. Actually, there are also several cases in which forced marriages are decided to be void.⁶⁹

From the viewpoint of minor's rights, the practice of marriages of minors in Europe is not acceptable. Correspondingly consensual sex with a girl below a minimum age constitutes statutory rape, the same act with a

⁶⁵ Menski W. Islamic law in British courts: do we not know or do we not want to know? The Place of Religion in Family Law: A Comparative Search (Eds Mair J and Özücü E), Intersentia, Cambridge-Antwerp-Portland, 2011, 15-69, 25.

⁶⁶ Jäntera-Järeborg M. The legal scope for religious identity in family matters. The Place of Religion in Family Law: A Comparative Search (Eds Mair J and Özücü E), Intersentia, Cambridge-Antwerp-Portland, 2011, 73-96, 96.

⁶⁷ See Pokhari F. Stolen Futures. Trafficking for Forced Child Marriage in the UK. ECPAT UK, 2009. 15.

⁶⁸ See De Blois M. Jewish family law and secular legal orders: the example of *get* refusal. The Place of Religion in Family Law: A Comparative Search (Eds Mair J and Özücü E), Intersentia, Cambridge-Antwerp-Portland, 2011, 207-233, 233.

⁶⁹ E.g. see Özücü E. How far can religion be accommodated in the laic family law of Turkey? The Place of Religion in Family Law: A Comparative Search (Eds Mair J and Özücü E), Intersentia, Cambridge-Antwerp-Portland, 2011, 117-157, p 131 and 133; Jäntera-Järeborg M. The legal scope for religious identity in family matters. The Place of Religion in Family Law: A Comparative Search (Eds Mair J and Özücü E), Intersentia, Cambridge-Antwerp-Portland, 2011, 73-96, 87-88; Crawford E.B and Carruthers J.M. The place of religion in family law: the International private law imperative. The Place of Religion in Family Law: A Comparative Search (Eds Mair J and Özücü E), Intersentia, Cambridge-Antwerp-Portland, 2011, 37-69, 57.

similar aged girl goes unsanctioned, in case a girl is married to this man. The rules protecting a child and religion-referred-rules, justify the violation of the rights of the child, cannot exist simultaneously alongside each other. In Europe, in some member states, the marriage of minors is allowed but only when the parents or court or some administrative body has assessed the maturity of the child.⁷⁰ However, the youngest age is 14. Naturally the child of 14 is a child, but still in more mature age than 5-13. Such marriages where state is involved to protect a child, marriage of a minor does not carry a negative meaning. In case a marriage of a minor derives from the religion, and no evaluation of his/her maturity has been made, the child marriage forms a problem. Related to legal capacity Myers' statement that "early marriage is also sometimes referred to as forced marriage"⁷¹, because children rarely consent freely, or understand the long-term implications of marrying young"⁷² is right. Still, also in those cases the parent(s) of the child give a consent, but it is hardly believable that those parents evaluate the maturity of the child. As indicated above, the reasons for marriages of minors are often economic and social and not based on a free mature consent of the child. Another widely used tool avoiding child marriages is criminalisation of forced marriages.⁷³ But criminalisation alone is not

⁷⁰ See also Joamets K., Roots L. Marriage of an Adolescent in the Context of Migration. *European Studies. The Review of European Law, Economics and Politics.*, 2, 117-130.

⁷¹ See Chantler K. 2012. Recognition of and Intervention in Forced Marriage as a Form of Violence and Abuse. *Trauma, Violence, & Abuse*, 13(3), 176-183. Sagepub.com

⁷² Myers J. 2013. Research Report. Untying the Knot. Exploring Early Marriage in Fragile States. World Vision, UK. Available at: www.worldvision.org/...nsf/.../Untying-the-Knot_report.pdf (16.12.2013), 6.

⁷³ The Istanbul convention (2011) (<http://www.conventions.coe.int/Treaty/Commun/ChercheSig.asp?NT=210&CM=&DF=&CL=ENG>), the first legally binding instrument in Europe in the field of violence against women and domestic violence, requires countries which ratify it to prohibit forced marriage (Article 37) and to ensure that forced marriages can be easily voided without further victimization (Article 32), but does not make any reference to a minimum age of marriage. Razak referring to Na'im (2000) points out that 1000 women are annually subjected to forced marriages (Razak S H. 2004. *Imperilled Muslim Women, Dangerous Muslim Men and Civilised Europeans. Legal and Social Responses to Forced Marriages. Feminist Legal Studies* 12: 129-174, 151).

sufficient, it should be combined with other measures, both legal and practical.⁷⁴

Questions of child marriages⁷⁵ are addressed in EU by its legislation on anti-discrimination, asylum, immigration, free movement of persons, criminal justice, data protection etc. Article 8 of the Treaty of the Functioning of the European Union (TFEU) provides that the Union aims to eliminate inequalities and promote equality between women and men in all its activities. Declaration No 19 on the Article 8 of the TFEU states that “in its general efforts to eliminate inequalities between woman and men, the Union will aim its different policies to combat all kinds of domestic violence. The EU member states should take all necessary measures to prevent and punish these criminal acts and support and protect the victims”.

EU member states are bound to the ECHR and other international conventions⁷⁶, some referred in this article, and the EU Charter of Fundamental Rights. The following directives of EU can be applied directly or indirectly in cases of marriages of minors: Council Directive 2003/86/EC of 22 September 2003 in the right to family reunification, Directive 2004/38/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 29 April 2004 on the right of citizens of the Union and their family members to move and reside freely within the territory of the Member State, Directive 2012/29/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 25 October 2012 establishing minimum standards on the rights, support and protection of victims of crime, and replacing Council Framework Decision 2001/220/JHA, Directive 2011/95/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 13 December 2011 on standards for the qualification of third-country nationals or stateless persons as beneficiaries of international protection, for a uniform

⁷⁴ Addressing forced marriage in the EU: legal provisions and promising practices. European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights. 2014. Publications Office of the European Union. Luxemburg, 7.

⁷⁵ In EU legal document in most cases the child marriage and forced marriages are pointed out separately as forced marriage can cover also women of age. However, the principles provided for avoiding the forced marriages are applicable also for the child marriages.

⁷⁶ Some states with low-priority reservations.

status for refugees or for persons eligible for subsidiary protection, and for the content of the protection granted (recast).

In principle, conditions and requirements for family reunification depend on the status of the person who wishes to bring his/her family members. Member states can establish the rules that marriage of a minor is prohibited in case of family reunification. Family reunification directive⁷⁷ allows member states to require the third-country national sponsor and his spouse to be of a minimum age before they can exercise the right to family reunification.⁷⁸ However, refusing the reunification based on age every single case should be examined carefully.⁷⁹ Article 5(5) of the directive demands to consider the best interests of minor children when examining an application. In this respect the widely discussed raise of the age for marriage is not an appropriate tool.

As in general the annulled marriage annuls also the residence permit then in case of victims of domestic violence the victims can grant the independent resident permit. Also, Istanbul convention provides that parties shall take the necessary legislative or other measures to ensure that victims of forced marriage brought into another country for the purpose of the marriage and who, as a result, have lost their residence status in the country where they habitually reside, may regain this status.⁸⁰

⁷⁷ Directive COUNCIL DIRECTIVE 2003/86/EC of 22 September 2003 on the right to family reunification.

⁷⁸ The Directive 2004/38/EC does not allow member states to establish minimum age requirements for spouses of EU nationals who exercise free movement rights (see Addressing forced marriage in the EU: legal provisions and promising practices. European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights. 2014. Publications Office of the European Union. Luxemburg, 26).

⁷⁹ See Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament and the Council on guidance for application of Directive 2003/86/EC on the right to family reunification (2014), 7-8.

⁸⁰ Art 59(4).

Conclusion

The article was elaborating on the problematic issues of marriage of minors where from one point of view these types of marriages are forbidden by international and EU law but from the other side are widely practiced also in the European Union. The impact of culture, religion and values of families play a major role in the practice. Minors still get married according to the traditions and religion of the families that violate the EU values and norms, but the states are pretty armless to protect the rights of a minor. There are some attempts from the side of the EU to regulate the marriage of minors at least in the case of immigration and in the framework of immigration control. The family reunification directive is regulating the age of a person who is eligible for the family reunification in case of marriage. The EU citizens' directive nevertheless is silent about the age limit. In fact as the family law in general is still mainly regulated by the EU member states there is still a strong need to create common rules based on the values of European Union to protect minors and their rights. There are of course several interests involved the state, the family and the minor. As stated in the article, the rights of the child should be protected highly and should prevail over individual interest of families or religions and values of the country of origin. Marriage gives additional rights but also obligations to the minor; so the maturity of the child has to be checked before the minor has a right to marry. There is much to be elaborated more on these questions in further researches.

Bibliography:

Abiad N. 2008. Sharia. Muslim States and International Human Rights Treaty Obligations: A comparative Study. British Institute of International and Comparative Law, London.

Allendorf K., Ghimire D. J. 2013. Determinants of marital quality in an arranged marriage society. Social Science Research 42, Elsevier, 59-70.

- Antokolskaia M. 2007. Objectives and Values of Substantive Family Law. *International Family Law for the European Union*. Meeusen J., M. Pertegás, G. Straetmans, F. Swennen (eds). Antwerpen-Oxford: Intersentia, 49-67.
- Antokolskaia M. 2010. Harmonisation of Substantive Family Law in Europe: Myths and Reality. *Child and Family Law Quarterly* 22, Jordan Publishing, 397-421.
- Billig M., S. 1992. The marriage squeeze and the rise of groomprice in India's Kerala state. *Journal of Comparative Family Studies*, 23(2), 197-216.
- Bix B. H. 2013. Pluralism and Decentralization in Marriage Regulation. *Marriage and Divorce in a Multicultural Context*. (ed. Nichols J. A.) Cambridge University Press, 60-77.
- Bruce J., Clark S. 2004. The implications of early marriage for HIV/AIDS policy: brief based on background paper prepared for the WHO/UNFPA/Population Council Technical Consultation on Married Adolescents. New York: Population Council. The Population Council, Inc.
- Caldwell J., C., Reddy P. H., & Caldwell P. 1983. Causes of marriage change in South India. *Population Studies*, 37(3), 343-361.
- Child Marriage Facts and Figures. Available at: <http://www.icrw.org/child-marriage-facts-and-figures> (16 Dec 2013).
- Chandra-Mouli V., Camacho A. V. and Michaud P.-A. 2013. WHO Guidelines on Preventing Early Pregnancy and Poor Reproductive Outcomes Among Adolescents in Developing Countries. *Journal of Adolescent Health* 52. Elsevier Inc., 517-522.
- Conolly A. J. 2012. Naturalising Cultural Difference and Law: Author's Introduction. *Australian Journal of Legal Philosophy* 37, Monash University, 280-292.
- Council of Europe Family Policy Database. Family law and children's rights. Marriage and cohabitation. Available at: www.coe.int/familypolicy/database (10 Dec 2013)
- Chantler K. 2012. Recognition of and Intervention in Forced Marriage as a Form of Violence and Abuse. *Trauma, Violence, & Abuse*, 13(3), 176-183. Sagepub.com.

- De Cruz P. 2010. *Family Law, Sex and Society. A comparative Study of Family Law*. Routledge: London and New York.
- Dethloff N. 2003. *Arguments for the Unification and Harmonisation of Family Law in Europe. Perspectives for the Unification and Harmonisation of Family Law in Europe* (ed. Boele-Woelki K.). Intersentia. Antwerp-Oxford-New York.
- Dixon-Mueller R. 2008. How young is “too young?” Comparative perspectives on adolescent sexual, marital and reproductive transitions. *Stud Fam Plan*, Vol. 39, 247-262.
- Eruklan A. 2013. *Adolescence Lost: The Realities of Child Marriage*. *Journal of Adolescent Health* Vol. 52, 513-514.
- EU Citizenship Report. Available at: http://ec.europa.eu/commission_2010-2014/reding/factsheets/citizenship-report/index.html (16 Dec 2013).
- Gangoly G., Chantler K. 2009. Protecting Victims of Forced Marriage: Is Age a Protective Factor?. *Fem Leg Stud*, Vol. 17. DOI 10.1007/s10691-009-9132-7, 267-288.
- Gender Equality Policy (2011). Available at: [http://www.google.ee/url?sa=t&rct=j&q=&esrc=s&source=web&cd=1&ved=0CCoQFjAA&url=http%3A%2F%2Fwww2.ohchr.org%2Fenglish%2Fissues%2Fwomen%2Fdocs%2FGenderEqualityPolicy_September2011.pdf&ei=Q2fOUsXfCMYqhQf3l4DwCQ&usg=AFQjCNFvq-4fjDajE2EB6BxZvhk8T0ay9A&sig2=Aun-qi6OIfnkWjeMahA0-w&bvm=bv.59026428,d.ZG4\(pdf\)](http://www.google.ee/url?sa=t&rct=j&q=&esrc=s&source=web&cd=1&ved=0CCoQFjAA&url=http%3A%2F%2Fwww2.ohchr.org%2Fenglish%2Fissues%2Fwomen%2Fdocs%2FGenderEqualityPolicy_September2011.pdf&ei=Q2fOUsXfCMYqhQf3l4DwCQ&usg=AFQjCNFvq-4fjDajE2EB6BxZvhk8T0ay9A&sig2=Aun-qi6OIfnkWjeMahA0-w&bvm=bv.59026428,d.ZG4(pdf))
- Gaffney-Rhys R. 2012. A comparison of child marriage and polygamy from a human rights perspective: are the arguments equally cogent? *Journal of Social Welfare and Family Law* 34, 1. Taylor & Francis 2012, 49-61.
- Huschek D., de Valk H., A., G. and Liefbroer A. C. 2012. Partner Choice Patterns Among the Descendants of Turkish Immigrants in Europe. *Eur J Population* 28: 241-268. Springer.
- Inglehart R., Baker W. F. 2000. Modernization, Cultural Change, And the Persistence of Traditional Values. *American Sociological Review*, Vol. 65, 19-51.

- Joamets K. 2012. Marriage Capacity, Social Values and Law-Making Process. *International and Comparative Law Review* 12. Palacký University, 97-115.
- Kerikmäe T., Nyman-Metcalf K. Less is more or more is more? Revisiting universality of human rights. 2012. *International and Comparative Law Review*. Vol. 12, no 1. Palacký University, Olomouc, Czech Republic. 35-51.
- Khanna T., Verma R., Weiss E. Child Marriage in South Asia: Realities, Responses and the Way Forward. "Solidarity for the Children of SAARC". 2013. Available at: <http://www.icrw.org/.../child-marriage-south-asia-realities-respons>.
- Laquer Estin A. L. 2013. Unofficial Family Law. Marriage and Divorce in a Multicultural Context. (ed. Nichols J. A.) Cambridge University Press 92-119.
- Legal capacity of persons with intellectual disabilities and persons with mental health problems. Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union, 2013. Published by European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights, 2013. Available at: www.google.ee/url?sa=t&rct=j&q=&esrc=s&source=web&cd=4&ved=0CEMQFjAD&url=http%3A%2F%2Ffra.europa.eu%2Fsites%2Fdefault%2Ffiles%2Flegal-capacity-intellectual-disabilities-mental-health-problems.pdf&ei=T26nUqWuKsOI4gSo2ID4Cg&usg=AFQjCNHP31TyrKW3gb0aeRjUOo2dRmehDA&sig2=wvrJom1E53imqI0Efm3WMw&bvm=bv.57799294,d.bGE (9 Dec 2013).
- Maertens A. 2013. Social Norms and Aspirations: Age of Marriage and Education in Rural India. *World Development* Vol. 47, 1-15. Elsevier Ltd.
- Malhotra A., Warner A., McGonagle A., Lee-Rife S. Solutions to End Child Marriage. What the evidence shows. ICRW. 2011. www.icrw.org/child-marriage
- Meeusen J. 2007. System Shopping in European Private International Law in Family Matters. *International Family Law for the European Union*. Meeusen J., M. Pertegás, G. Straetmans, F. Swennen (eds.). Intersentia. Antwerpen-Oxford.
- Myers J. 2013. Research Report. Untying the Knot. Exploring Early Marriage in Fragile States. World Vision, UK. Available at: www.worldvision.org/...nsf/.../Untying-the-Knot_report.pd... (16Dec 2013).

Malhotra A., Warner A., McGonagle A., Lee-Rife S. Solutions to End Child Marriage. What the evidence shows. ICRW. 2011. Available at: www.icrw.org/childmarriage

Na'im A. A. 2000. Forced Marriage. Available at: http://soas.ac.uk/honour_crimes/ForcedMarriage.htm (30 Jan 2014).

Nichols J. A. 2013. Multi-Tiered Marriage. Reconsidering the Boundaries of Civil Law and Religion. Marriage and Divorce in a Multicultural Context. (ed. Nichols J. A.) Cambridge University Press, 11-59.

Pintens W. 2003. Europeanisation of Family Law. Perspectives for the Unification and Harmonisation of Family Law in Europe. Boele-Woelki K. (ed.). Intersentia. Antwerp-Oxford-New York.

Raj A., Raj A., Saggurti N., Balaiah D., Silverman J. G. 2009. Prevalence of child marriage and its effect on fertility and fertility-control outcomes of young women in India: a cross-sectional, observational study. *Lancet*, Vol. 30.

Razak S H. 2004. Imperilled Muslim Women, Dangerous Muslim Men and Civilised Europeans. Legal and Social Responses to Forced Marriages. *Feminist Legal Studies* 12: 129-174.

Right to Education Project. Promoting Mobilisation and Legal accountability. Available at: <http://www.right-to-education.org/node/58> (16 Dec 2013)

Statement of the Catherine Ashton on child marriage in Yemen. Brussels, 13 September 2013 A 456/3. Available at: www.consilium.europa.eu/uedocs/cms_data/.../138730.pdf (16.12.2013)

Sarrazin T. Saksamaa käib maha. Ohtlik mäng oma riigiga. 2013. (ed. Enno M.) OÜ Hea Lugu ja Janno Toots. Tallinna Raamatutrükikoda.

Thorton A. 2012. International Family Change and Continuity. The Past and Future from the Developmental Idealism Perspective. Marriage at the Crossroads. Law, Policy, and the Brave New World of Twenty-First-Century Families. (ed. Garrison M. and Scott E.S.), 30- 53.

UNFPA (2005) State of the World Population 2005 The Promise of Equality: Gender Equity, Reproductive Health and the MDGs, New York: UNFPA. Available at: www.unfpa.org/swp/2005/pdf/en_swp05.pdf .16 Dec2013.(

Vainu V., Järviste L., Biin H. Soolise võrdõiguslikkuse monitooring. Uuringuraport. (Monitoring of Gender Equality) 2009. Sotsiaalministeeriumi toimetised 2010. Published by Ministry of Social Affairs 2010, 130-131.

Vogl T. 2010. Sisters, Schooling, and Spousal Search: Evidence from South Asia. Paper presented at Northeast Universities Development Consortium Conference on 6-6 November 2010 at MIT.

International Legal Acts

Convention to Eliminate all forms of Discrimination against Women 1979 (CEDAW art 16).

UN Convention on the Rights of the Child 1989.

Hague Convention on the Celebration and Recognition of Marriages 1978.

UN Declaration of Human Rights 1948.

African Charter on Human and People's Rights 2004.

African Charter on the Rights and Welfare of the Child 1990.

Estonian Legal Acts

Estonian General Part of the Civil Code Estonian State Gazette (RT) I, 06.12.2010, 12.

Estonian Marriage Law Act Estonian State Gazette (RT) I, 09.05.2017, 28

Draft of Cohabitation Act. Available at: http://www.riigikogu.ee/?page=en_vaade&op=ems&enr=650SE&koosseis=12. (10 Aug 2014).

An explanatory letter of the Draft of the Cohabitation Law Act. Available at: http://www.riigikogu.ee/?page=en_vaade&op=ems&enr=650SE&koosseis=12. (10 Aug 2014).

Copyright©Kristi JOAMETS

Copyright©Lehte ROOTS

Educational Policies in the European Union: Actuality and Practical Significance

Ph.D. Student Ludmila CUROS

ludmilacuros@mail.ru

International Relations Institute of Moldova, Moldova

Abstract. Educational policy must be a priority in the activity of state and non-governmental bodies because the stability within the state and the pace of its development depend on a great extent on a policy success in education. Education systems have to cope with various challenges, developments and problems related to their own field of education, but also adapt to international ones in order to compete on the national and international market. The quality of educational policy depends on the activity and the sense of responsibility for the results of the training and education, of all the factors, including students, teachers, and parents and public authorities that determine the state policy in the sphere of education. In this context, it is absolutely necessary to study the advanced experience in the field (abroad (in the case of EU countries) and in the Republic); increase interest in education and lifelong learning; to organize roundtables, co-practical scientific conferences, interactive activities involving students, teachers, parents, officials from state and non-governmental bodies, etc.

Keywords: education, training, educational policy, quality, lifelong learning.

Nowdays science marks a high level of evolution and provides new ways of using tehnology, such as in education and comunication. This is why this evolution does have a big influence over education development, especially over kidergarden, school, and university's organization program, over those who are about to teach and the relationship between teachers and learners. This changes are inffern from the intention of creating a good place to learn and teach by creating the right space for good relationships to develop, also the: necessity of enlist two foreing languages learning, by placing the emphasis on multiculturalism in education, by spreading open and distance learning and lifelong learning, through the need to revise the

curriculum for the internationalization of teaching-evaluation content and processes, by modifying and / or adapting national education policies internationally emphasize the influence of science evolution over education's development. Education and training take place in the context of increasing the international mobility of students, students and teachers, when the impact of new technologies on education becomes more and more visible, when the educational requirements change dramatically as a market emerges European work and multinational enterprises appear, when training can not be limited to certain periods in the life of the individual, but must take place throughout life, when education can not be achieved without the direct participation of all labor market participants. In this context, education systems have to cope with various challenges, developments and problems related to their own field of education as well as to society as a whole. These conditions increase the role of education as a factor that contributes decisively to social cohesion and development.

Over the last decades, all European countries have tried to respond to new challenges and demands through reforms of the national education system, seeking a fair balance between the principles of quality, effectiveness, diversity, equity, and the competencies of central and local government and the autonomy of each educational institutions. Reforms that focused on specific directions such as: reorienting education programs and objectives to the expected outcomes in the various educational processes, in terms of knowledge, skills and capacities; equal opportunities for access to education and active inclusion in the education system; decentralization and autonomy of educational institutions; the orientation of educational institutions to the requirements of the specific environment; enhancing the quality of education, developing ways to evaluate each child, student, student, teacher, educational institution, and the system as a whole (at national level); the status and training of teachers as key factors in promoting reforms; financing education and training in its various forms.

Thus, the issue of quality, equity and effectiveness in education is at the forefront. Strengthening the quality and evaluation process of the

education system is the central issue in the educational sphere. In order to work well, the entire education system must be based on a very high level of quality. In any developed society, quality enables everyone to discover, amplify and use their own skills. Without this quality, access to education makes no sense at all.

Education ministers from EU countries identified the following priority areas:

- All students must acquire the skills they need, including reading and math. To this end, school curricula, teaching materials and student assessment systems will be upgraded.
- Every student should be provided with high quality education, including migrant children.
- Pre-school education must be accessible to a larger number of children, more support should be given to pupils with special needs for their better integration into normal-school schools, and the drop-out rate should be reduced.
- Teachers, school principals and teacher trainers need to receive increased support through effective selection and recruitment procedures and training programs.¹

To this end, the European Commission presented in 2012 the "Rethinking Education" initiative to encourage EU countries to ensure that young people acquire the skills they require in the labor market. The package includes analysis papers on teaching support and the assessment of key competences in initial education and training (a review of literature data). Also, a High Level Group on Literacy has been created. It brings together teachers and decision-makers and aims to analyze the situation in Europe, identify needs and requirements as they evolve, and find the best ways to address them. To this end, a European network of national organizations for the promotion of literacy is launched in February 2014. The objectives of this network include greater awareness, exchange of good practices, policies, campaigns and initiatives to promote literacy. In December 2016, the Commission presented a Communication on Improving

and Modernizing Education, which includes a set of actions aimed to support EU countries in delivering high-quality services for pre-school children's education and care and in developing high-quality school systems, innovative and inclusive policies.

Educational policies are the strategic directions for the development of the education system and include laws and norms applied in practice through methodologies, controlled and monitored, and ultimately evaluated through impact studies. They are coherent strategies, based on analysis, synthesis, diagnosis, and prognosis specific to the educational environment at all levels. Their content is aimed at organizing the education system, the function of the institutions, financing of education, evaluation, management, curriculum, training, improvement, and promotion of the teaching staff. Like any other policy, education has multiple levels, from declarations to achievement:

- The declarative level that includes the rhetoric, speeches, work agendas, ads. It is manifested when certain terms are frequently circulated because they represent a certain international orientation to which a particular state adheres. This is especially true when it comes to getting funds. Such terms, often used in world educational policies, are women's education, community involvement, civil society building. And the educational policies in the Republic of Moldova have begun to convey these terms alongside equal opportunities, human rights, children's rights, school inclusion, the right to free expression, etc.
- The level of implementation (application) that includes the changes that result from the testing and implementation of the policies themselves, sometimes their adaptation to local conditions or the application of a specific policy. If a policy is applied, there are some changes or adaptations that the practitioner is applying to. Sometimes local conditions make an impractical policy, although previous levels have been achieved. Such an example can be found in the concept of "equal chances". It is promoted at the declarative

level, it is decreed that in all the localities where there are so many children that a class for a certain ethnic minority is formed, that class will be formed, and at the level of implementation, it is found that there are no teachers ready to teach that class.

The level at which most policies fail is the implementation level. A common phenomenon in educational practice, especially in states where the economy is still in developing process, is that policies are thought by a group of international experts, and the implementation part lies with local experts. Such an approach will lead to failure, as local experts are confronted with practical problems of practice, but do not have the power to decide on changing policy lines. The educational policy of other countries needs to be adapted to the local one but not implemented directly, the effect will at best be null. Adaptation requires a detailed analysis of the specificity of the country that will implement that policy, its culture and traditions, the level of awareness of the country's citizens. In order to reduce the failure during the implementation of an education policy, it is necessary to analyze the existing situation. The current situation from which an educational policy has to be build can be analyzed in three components: the problem, the factors that generated that problem and the justification of the importance of solving that problem. The problem situation can be defined and exemplified by statistical data, current information, the name of other sources that refer to that problem. The question to be answered by this approach is the following: what is the problem? Factors that generate a particular problem can be economic, social, political, etc. For example, in the Republic of Moldova, there are a series of changes in the social, economic, political context affecting the education sector: administrative decentralization, market economy, raising the level of the unemployed, low wage levels in education, emigration of young people, etc. Justifying the importance of solving the identified problem involves identifying the impact that expected outcomes will have on other social sectors.

For example, in order to solve the problem of the low education budget, how the allocation of 4% of gross domestic product (GDP) will affect

the education system? Will the improvements expected here have positive effects on other areas? If a possible result is increased wages in education, which will result in raising the socio-economic prestige of the teaching profession, this means that more young people will choose this profession. The possible consequences are increasing the quality of human resources in education, reducing the unemployment rate and reducing the emigration of young graduates. These options are possible solutions to solve the problem situation identified in the previous stage. Solutions can be identified in groups of experts, interviews with people relevant to the topic chosen, comparative analysis of similar measures taken in other countries, brainstorming with local experts and practitioners, etc. When we are about to realise the comparative analysis, the countries under discussion must be socio-economically or geo-politically comparable. For example, countries with which the Republic of Moldova can be compared are East European countries, members of the former USSR, those aspired to access to the European Union, those in the immediate vicinity – Romania, etc.

The evaluation of policy options in the field of education requires the definition of evaluation criteria, certain investigations are undertaken (in the area of estimated costs, the planning of necessary actions is being attempted) and the criteria for all the solutions identified in the previous stage are applied. Such criteria may be cost-quality ratio, local capacity to implement proposed measures, financial sustainability, short-term efficiency, long-term positive effects, public support, political support, etc. For each of these criteria, a feasibility scale is established with 3-5 steps, where step 1 represents the lowest degree of feasibility of that criterion, and step 3 (5) represents the highest degree of feasibility of that criterion. After the scoring of each solution from the perspective of all the criteria, the solutions will be hierarchized, those with the highest score will be applied, those who achieve a medium score will be kept in reserve and those with a low score will be eliminated. These analyzes are fundamental and can not be ignored under any pretext, for example, limited time. To ensure successful implementation of this policy, stakeholder groups: professional associations,

parents, political parties, institutions, and organizations are identified with the decision. In order to receive their support, it is good that they are also involved in the decision.

Policy planning and implementation mean achieving two of the three levels of an education policy. For the level of action, the strategy for implementing the policy is being developed, and for the level of implementing the policy is piloted, improved and expanded on a large scale. The monitoring and evaluation of the educational policy must be carried out permanently, the purpose of which is to ensure the correlation between all three levels: declarative, action and application. An educational policy is a strong point of reference for future decisions, but it is not rigid. When practice demonstrates the need for reformulation or when the problem situation changes, that educational policy must also be modified, adapted to the needs of the present, to succeed in the future. The effects of today's educational policy will be felt in the future, but not at the moment.

Through its policy, the European Union is considering creating a European area of freedom, security, and justice where people no longer need control at internal borders, regardless of their nationality. Simultaneously, common standards are implemented for the control of the external borders of the Union as well as for visa, asylum, and immigration policies. The European construction has developed not only horizontally, but also by increasing the number of countries participating in the integration process, but also vertically, by including new and increasingly important objectives on the issues that the new Europe ought to have in mind. The analysis of the many directives, regulations, programs, and initiatives of the European Union highlights that this issue is constantly transformed by the desire to respond to the needs and needs of the European Union in an appropriate and effective way. If at the beginning of the European construction, education and training occupied a peripheral position in European policies, it was only in 1976 that the Council would adopt what would be the founding act of Community cooperation in the field of education.

At the beginning of the 1990s, the European Commission opened the debate on Community cooperation on education and training. Subsequently, all Community treaties recognized the importance of education and training. At the same time, although the policy on education and training is subject to the co-decision procedure, in line with the principle of subsidiarity, and this policy is mainly under the competence of the Member States, the European Union has adopted a number of programs European and international scale to promote exchanges, mobility and mutual understanding. In this context, the European Union proves to be a useful forum for exchanging ideas and best practices to create a functioning system of cooperation between the Member States by maintaining the right of each Member State to decide on the content and organization of education and training systems.

Education and training systems need to change their priorities so as to ensure that all European citizens have the knowledge, skills, and competencies needed to meet the challenges and demands of jobs and modern life. Although education policy is decided by each state, the members of the European Union have recognized that they share common goals. That is why the role of the Union is to support cooperation between the Member States and, where necessary, complement their actions, in particular by supporting mobility and cooperation between educational institutions. In 2000, in the context of an increasingly visible globalization, the Lisbon Strategy was launched to transform Europe into the most competitive and dynamic knowledge-based economy in the world by 2010, the "knowledge triangle" (research, education, and innovation) representing a central element of it. The strategy did not have the expected results and education was identified as one of the main drivers for the relaunch of the Lisbon Strategy.

Since the start of European cooperation in the field of education, the main priorities have been to promote transnational mobility of students and teachers, to promote European cooperation between educational establishments and to improve the quality of education and training. Currently, the European Union's education and training programs are 1.

Socrates 2. Leonardo Da Vinci. 3.Tempus. 4.Erasmus Mundus. 5. The new lifelong learning program.

A global vision for Vocational Education and Training (VET) in 2020 agreed by the European Commission is that by 2020 European VET systems should be more attractive, more relevant, more career-oriented, more innovative, accessible and flexible compared to 2010 and should contribute to excellence and equity in lifelong learning by providing the following:

- Attractive and inclusive Inclusive VET;
- High-quality initial VET;
- VET continues, easily accessible and career oriented;
- Flexible VET systems based on the learning outcomes approach;
- A European area of education and training with transparent qualifications systems;
- Significantly increased trans-national mobility opportunities for pupils and VET professionals;
- High-quality, accessible, high-quality information, guidance and counseling services throughout life.

Helping all citizens to improve their skills and qualifications is a crucial issue in the EU's development and job creation as well as in promoting equality and social inclusion. The economic crisis places these long-term challenges even more at the center of attention. Public and private budgets are subject to strong pressures, existing jobs are disappearing, newly created jobs often require different skills, and a higher level of qualification. Therefore, education and training systems should be more open and relevant to the needs of citizens, the labor market and society in general. Good practices must be taken and adapted to the national level of a country in order to be competitive on the global market and to provide mobility to young people for professional and personal development. Failures in other countries must be analyzed and avoided in national education policy. The requirements of the new century have raised questions throughout the world such as: "until" and "by what methods" do we learn? From employers, authorities to every individual, the answer

seems to be unanimous: permanent learning is no longer a luxury, but a necessary condition for adapting to changing professional, social, economic and informational requirements.

Bibliography:

Communication From The Commission To The European Parliament, The Council, The European Economic And Social Committee And The Committee Of The Regions, Improving competences for the 21st Century: An Agenda for European Cooperation on Schools.

Militaru Cezar, Adina Pavel, Adriana Zanfir, Politici în domeniul Calității Educației la nivelul Uniunii Europene, Martie 2011.

Militaru Cezar, Sisteme de management ale calității în învățământul superior economic, București, Editura Printech 2009.

http://ec.europa.eu/education/policy/school_ro

Copyright©Ludmila CUROS

European Monetary Union (EMU): Proposal for an Index on Financial Inequalities to Be Added to the Official Indexes of Maastricht

Prof. Dr. Lamberto LAURENTI

lamberto.l@hotmail.com

Institute of European Studies "Alcide De Gasperi", Italy

Abstract. In the context of the construction of the European Monetary Union, financial parameters have been formulated in order to bring the economies of the Member Countries into line with certain constraints. In this essay, following the concept of "starting justice" (J. Rawls), a new parameter to be added to the canonical ones is proposed. Particularly for the younger generation, applying such a parameter would lead to gains in proportion to their work and creativity. A better distribution of resources, in fact, would create a greater demand for goods with a resulting greater production. The augmented production would lead to an additional increase in employment (and further growth in the demand for goods) and, therefore, to the creation of a virtuous circle that creates the conditions for widespread prosperity.

Keywords: European Monetary Union, EU, EURO, European Central Bank, Maastricht Parameters, Economics and Ethics.

The process towards the creation of the European Monetary Union (EMU) was based on objectives established at the beginning, and on "deadlines" which, theoretically, left little room for "discretion". In analyzing the problems that arose after the Maastricht treaty, we would like to point out that such rigidity was one of the causes that led to the lack of homogeneity in the path towards meeting the criteria established for the creation of a Single Monetary System. Both the objectives as well as the time constraints were set without taking into account the different economic cycles in the various European countries. Furthermore, it must also be stressed that other objectives, such as social or employment ones, have been neglected.

Another cause to which we can ascribe the difficulties that arose was the absence of a singular guiding entity over the countries belonging to the European Organization that could have lead the charge towards the creation of the EMU. We believe that the root cause should be attributed to an oft-mentioned, but, unfortunately seldom practiced, “European conscience”. This happens, above all, when the financial “gaps” become more pronounced, by increasing expectations of a stronger bond between the various Nations, expectations that at times remain, however, ignored.

The coordination of economic policies has in fact always been a difficult problem to deal with, as the nation that potentially has the strongest economic system often tends to defend its own characteristics, rather than favoring the most important general needs.

Those countries that demonstrate a positive differential should instead favor, in a more European spirit, those nations whose differentials are negative.

Governments should, first and foremost, develop a truly coherent European conscience, on which a compensatory economic-financial program depends, the outcome of which should coincide with a policy suitable to and homogeneous for the whole of Europe.

This distance between economic-financial programs and policies has often marked the journey towards a unified Europe, despite Parliament having called attention to the need for “parallel economic policies”.

Without going too far back in time, let us consider, for example, the financial crisis of 1992-93, which was especially serious and which involved various member countries and a consequent shift away from the Maastricht criteria. An element of particular concern was, for certain countries, the distancing from the margins inherent to the European Monetary System (EMS). The EMS tried reluctantly to manage the crisis situation by bringing the fluctuation margins to 15% (it must be said, however, that the Nations with the best monetary potential did not benefit from this widening of the fluctuation band).

The release of the British pound and the Lira from the EMS created, as is well known, a stalemate within the System.

Referring to the causes that, after Maastricht, led to certain distortions and to centrifugal tendencies with respect to the definition of the EMU, we will now analyze them in detail.

The Maastricht treaties were spawned at a unique time for Europe, and aimed to revive the various nations of the European Community, with the awareness that the efforts did not concern only the economic aspect alone. Doing so would have accelerated the coordination process, and economic and monetary unification would have been achieved by the year 2000.

However praiseworthy, from a practical point of view, their intentions might be, ultimately some countries have still had to face difficulties due to exogenous or endogenous causes.

It is also necessary to consider the peremptory deadlines fixed at the time, including the various phases in which the EMU was to be structured.

It was anyways necessary to move past the stalemate that had arisen in Europe, so that each country would be, from an economic standpoint, tied to these indicators, in order to force them to take more realistic and secure action towards achieving the EMU.

Consequently, if, on the one hand, the act of outlining parameters created certain tensions related to the behavior demonstrated by member countries, nevertheless these parameters represented the last “ratio” in causing both the opposition of some countries and the compliance of others, towards the hope of a European spirit, not only from an economic and financial point of view, but also an international one.

The terms of each phase, therefore, could have been decided upon with some flexibility. The “virtuous” European countries, at the time, were in favor of a re-formulation of these criteria, but not against the criteria themselves, even if, to be honest, someone (the Governor of the Bank of France) suggested that the Monetary Union could have also been launched

with the participation of only the five countries considered “virtuous” at the time: Germany, France, Luxembourg, The Netherlands, and Austria.

We would like to point out that the current European situation presents not only real differences, but those that are also related to the same economic culture.

In his work entitled *Capitalism versus Capitalism*, Albert Michel argues that the same liberalist economy encompasses a wide range of cultures and interpretations, which leads to an ulterior cause, even if unjustified, concerning the difficulty of integrating the economic policies of each member country in the European Union.

In examining some causes in detail, one reaches the conclusion that the reunification of Germany allowed for the so-called asymmetric shock to the EMS mechanism. In fact, the German authorities tried to counter the inflation that was caused, in large part, by the expenses necessary for reunification, increasing interest rates and damaging other European economies in the process. It must be said, in fact, that Germany used the monetary instrument without first considering the fact that roughly a third of the inflation resulted from a fiscal cause.

Returning to the argument in question, we agree with Loukas Tsoukalis, who believes that it was a mistake to establish a peremptory time limit for the fulfillment of the Maastricht criteria. He argues, in fact, that in doing so, speculators, who were trying to make predictions on the evolution of some financial policies, were thus given an advantage. This resulted in the movement of funds, attracted by areas that offered better returns. The same advantages of a single financial market were partly canceled out by such sudden and abrupt movements of sums of money, creating tensions within both the country of origin and that of arrival.

The dispute over these dynamics is a somewhat dated and, at the same time, delicate matter. Even in less suspect times (at the beginning of

the 50s), Marco Fanno had already foreseen the disadvantages deriving from sudden movements of funds between the various markets¹.

In more recent years, Robert Triffin² has emphasized the possibility of circumscribing or limiting such movements even through a redistribution of taxes. The issue relating to taxes was raised by Loukas Tsoukalis as well, who believes that, in this way, speculators would be quite discouraged and the financial burden would weigh on those investors who seek to profit from differences in the exchange rates and interest rates. Tsoukalis asserts that it would be opportune to introduce a system of taxation, even if limited, on short-term international transactions with speculative tendential aims, instead of establishing a set percentage over the entire sum relating to the long-term³.

It is quite clear that the financial crisis of September 1992 and the desertion of exchange rate agreements by other currencies at the end of July 1993 may have resulted in a lack of credibility, not only with regards to the EMS, but especially towards those countries whose currency showed a certain instability.

In short, the solution for maintaining a monetary system that is efficient and functional for all currencies is to create a broader coordination effort and a deeper European spirit on the part of the various countries, especially after the risk linked to the conflict between Eastern and Western Blocks had diminished.

In preparation for the entry of new countries into the Monetary Union, however, it is necessary to recover, from both a historical and a philosophical perspective, this Europeanistic spirit, which should involve in a coordinated way both the countries that have a weak currency and those with a strong currency, to create similar expectations for everyone.

¹ See Marco Fanno, *La teoria delle fluttuazioni economiche* (Torino, Unione Tipografico-Editrice Torinese, 1956).

² See Robert Triffin, "Une Banque Monétaire Européenne avec des fonctions de banque centrale", *Répères, Bulletin Économique et Financier*, 1987/2, 59-68.

³ See Loukas Tsoukalis, *In Defence of Europe: Can the European Project Be Saved?* (Oxford, Oxford University Press, 2016).

With that said, it is fundamental that economic policy bears in mind, first and foremost, the conditions dictated by social policy and employment.

It is also necessary, furthermore, to have increased social awareness towards issues related to employment throughout Europe.

In this sense, it would have been advantageous to outline an index, as yet still nonexistent, for employment – it is not always the case that a strong currency has an equally positive corresponding employment sector. Ireland, for example, demonstrated a stable currency in the early 1990s, which corresponded however to a fairly high level of unemployment (20%).

We must keep in mind the already well-known relationship between the percentages of inflation and the unemployment rate compared to the percentage increase in GDP.

The economic situation is neither negative, at least in certain historical periods, if the result of this difference approaches zero. Naturally, a positive balance in favor of the increase in GDP is desirable. In this regard, as already requested by various parties, it would be advantageous to exclude from the assessment of GDP the costs for facilities and primary services (schools and hospitals), and to include those due to environmental pollution.

This problem has been analyzed differently by the various countries belonging to the EMU, resulting in the creation of diverse economic policies developed in relation to the various solutions adopted by different governments of the member countries regarding the issue of employment. This has resulted in negative effects, not only from a social point of view, but also for the market and for currencies. We believe it necessary to reference Delors' White Paper, which discussed the idea of creating 15 million jobs in Europe. In fact, employment has always been one of the primary objectives of the European Union.

It is opportune, from both ethical and socio-economic points of view, to attribute greater value to the "human" element as a possible independent variable of socio-economic dynamics.

On the other hand, the persistent problem of employment always remains an unknown, with economic and political repercussions. One might wonder whether it would not have been better if the European nations had strongly committed to coordinating social policies, something that would have brought advantages in the economic sector as well.

Again with regards to employment policy, Tsoukalis asserts the need to create both incentives in the labor market and, at the same time, a strict regulation of the same market. Additionally, he argues that it is necessary to facilitate the job market. He justifies this statement by saying that, if we consider work at a fixed cost to the Company, the employer has to think twice about employing someone. In our opinion, the market could instead be less rigid by relying on an intermediate solution, by favoring mobility even to other companies, more or less similar if possible, in the European context rather than proceeding with dismissals in the sector of entrepreneurial work.

In this way, there would be no rigidity regarding salary costs. Consequently, the impediments on the part of economic operators to hire personnel would also be reduced, even with regards to circumstances of wage rigidity.

Tsoukalis also maintains that the burden that is placed on the jobs market should affect only those operators and products that damage the environment.

In short, we could argue that the criteria laid down in Maastricht should have also been expanded to include those that were not strictly financial or economic. It's important to note, however, that in the subsequent intra-governmental conferences, adequate importance was given to the social element, which was then codified in the Treaty of Amsterdam.

Another socio-economic element to consider is the one concerning wealth and, above all, the distribution of it among the various populations.

The measure of wealth is not indicative when considered in relation to the population. The so-called "per capita" index is misleading in that it

allows for statistical information in reference to the two quantities “income” and “population”. In other words, it does not illustrate how this income is distributed, nor who or how many earners there are of it; ultimately, it is an indicator that, in this important aspect, tends to be omissive. As a result, because of a statistical equalization, only a virtual income for non-earners is determined. This is despite a per capita index being used in macroeconomic surveys. The result consists in the fact that one might determine for two countries the same final index, but with a strong distributional difference.

In fact, an equitable allocation of wealth, besides responding to an ethical need, also produces positive effects on the economic level, in that it establishes on equal terms an increase in total demand which should correspond to an increase in the production of wealth, and therefore employment. In this way a virtuous circle would be initiated that could result in widespread well-being.

With that said, it would have been more advantageous to adopt a wealth distribution index referring to the member countries, who could have in turn enacted a more effective policy regarding the “plan” in the aforementioned sense, or rather socio-economically. This index could have been represented by the well-known Lorenz curve.

In a fair distribution of resources, meaning one with equal starting opportunities (Rawls spoke of “starting justice”), equitable values are located along the bisector of the graph. The curve shows deviations from this straight line and therefore also a distributive inequality. Naturally, the greater this deviation is, the greater the inequality between resources and populations, and vice versa.

As such, we must consider the scarce ethical sense of some public in contrast to the founding values of the “Europe project”.

Let us examine in empirical fashion what could be an index of the distribution of the resources to add to the canonical ones of Maastricht regarding the potential member countries of the European Union that intend to be a part of the EMS.

In the graph we assume that the variables “x” and “y”, which represent resources and subjects respectively, are standardized so as to allow a maximum value of 1 (area of the square with $x=1$ and $y=1$).

The line connecting the two extreme points (0, 0) and (1, 1) represents the condition of absence of inequality. The area bounded by this line and the x-axis corresponds to half the value of the square 1:1.

The area of concentration indicates an inequality in the distribution of resources among the “y” (population) elements. It is measured roughly in the following expression⁴:

$$\text{Area of Concentration} = 0,5 - [\sum (x_{i+1}-x_i)(y_{i+1}+y_i):2]$$

Calculated by interrelating the area of the triangle $[(x_1-x_0)y_1]:2$ with the area of all of the trapezoids below the line that connects coordinate points (x, y) with (x_{i+1}, y_{i+1}) .

We could therefore define “r” as the index of concentration between the above-mentioned area and the area of maximum concentration, or in other terms: $r = (\text{area of concentration} / 0.5)$

It follows that the lower said value is, the better the distribution of resources within a given country. It will be up to the competent European

⁴ This mathematical formula is an elaboration of Prof. Luigi Battisti, I.T.C.G. “Enrico Fermi”, Tivoli (Rome).

institutions to establish which “r” limit should be reached that would then be integrated into the other Maastricht indexes.

Moreover, among the financial economic parameters, it would have been opportune to include the macroeconomic one of the national savings entity. After all, even the Nobel Prize winner Amartya Sen maintains that it is necessary to replace the concept of mere productivity (cost-benefit relationship), with that of development (distributive equity of resources, education, health, environment), which ultimately entails, as mentioned above, greater and more widespread well-being.

Besides, ethics in an ontological sense can not but move in favor of man and therefore of the society of which every man is part.

At the end of this analytical excursus on the constraints of Maastricht, it should be added that the ratio between GDP and public debt must be stripped of the inflation component to move from the “nominal” to a “real” evaluation.

Lastly, it would be opportune to distinguish, as already pointed out by the European Parliament, between current expenditure and capital expenditure in order to assess the public finances of a future country that wishes to enter Europe.

Ultimately, as Dahrendorf says⁵, it is truly necessary to square the circle between economic progress and civil society, especially in the light of a program that tends towards a united and sovereign Europe.

These indications and the parametric corrections proposed in this essay would have better highlighted the internal situation of the member countries, in order to create evaluation criteria for the entry into the EMU more in-line with the economic reality of the countries requesting entry into the Euro area.

⁵ See Ralf Dahrendorf, *Economic Opportunity, Civil Society and Political Liberty* (Geneva, United Nations Research Institute for Social Development, 1995).

Bibliography:

Dahrendorf, Ralf. *Economic Opportunity, Civil Society and Political Liberty*. Geneva: United Nations Research Institute for Social Development, 1995.

Fanno, Marco. *La teoria delle fluttuazioni economiche*. Torino: Unione Tipografico-Editrice Torinese, 1956.

Laurenti, Lamberto. *La Banca Centrale Europea e l'Euro. Storia, Analisi, Prospettive*. Roma: Istituto Poligrafico e Zecca dello Stato, 2009.

Triffin, Robert. "Une Banque Monétaire Européenne avec des fonctions de banque centrale", *Répères, Bulletin Économique et Financier*, 1987/2, 59-68.

Tsoukalis, Loukas. *In Defence of Europe: Can the European Project Be Saved?* Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2016.

Copyright©Lamberto LAURENTI

Good Governance over Natural Resources: Legal Aspects of Transparency Policy

Lecturer Nilyufar ABDULATOVA

abdulatova@gmail.com

University of World Economy and Diplomacy, Uzbekistan

Abstract. This article presents a comparison analyze about the environmental and transparency aspects of good governance in the raw materials/natural resources sector in developed and developing countries. Two developed (Norway, Germany) and two developing (Russia, Kazakhstan) countries have been selected for this comparison study. Therefore, research questions regarding the legal domestic and international initiatives have been covered in the article.

Keywords: good governance, raw materials, extractive industries, transparency, environmental governance, natural resources, sustainable development, permanent sovereignty over natural resources.

More or less significant resolutions have been done since the humanity has realized the importance of the transparency aspects within the natural resources management. International initiatives in order to strengthen the transparency in extractive sector have been taken could be possible solutions to create effective overseeing mechanisms in order to eradicate problems like corruption. The extractive industries are a great temptation for corrupted political elite in many developing countries. "Political and economic problems such as corruption are increasingly affecting more than one state."¹

The importance of these kind initiatives should not be underestimated. The main idea of transparency initiatives should explain the accountability of revenues coming from extractive industries sector to

¹ Rotberg, Corruption, Global Security and World Oder, 2009, 416 et seqq.

people, local media and civil society. “Transparency is often linked to a democratizing impulse in governance.”²

The transparency in extractive industries is start point for developing welfare, combating human rights violations and eradication corruption in resource – rich developing countries. The importance of the transparency in extractive industries has been examined in the “OPL 245 Corruption Scandal.”³ The case is about the “huge amount of revenues from oil business have been paid by two gigantic oil companies “Shell” and “Eni” to former oil minister of Nigeria in 1998.”⁴ This is a well-known problem of developing countries, so –called oil money for “private pockets.”⁵

As Hendrix and Nolad pointed out in their research: “the effectiveness of transparency initiatives has varied depending on the industry structure, the vulnerability of major extractive firms to shaming, the relative importance of participants sensitive to human rights concerns, geological and other considerations that affect the availability of alternative sources of supply, the technical ability to implement certifications procedures, and the political interests of the dominant powers.”⁶ During the G8 summit in Heiligendamm, the participants have maintained the transparency in extractive industries issue. Two key approaches have been discussed:

- “transparent financial flow from the extractive sector,”⁷
- “the certification of raw materials.”⁸

² Gupta/Mason, *Transparency in Global Environmental Governance: Critical Perspectives*, 2014, 133 et seqq.

³ Shell and Eni’s Misadventures in Nigeria: Shell and Eni at risk of losing enormous oil block acquired in corrupt deal, Briefing Nov. 17, 2015, <https://www.globalwitness.org/en/campaigns/oil-gas-and-mining/shell-and-enis-misadventures-nigeria/> (15/11/2016).

⁴ Ibid.

⁵ Ibid.

⁶ Hendrix, Noland, *Confronting the Curse: The Economics and Geopolitics of Natural Resources Government*, 2014, Peterson Institute for International Economics, 92 et seqq.

⁷ Report of international Conference: Transparency in the Extractive Sector, http://site.resources.worldbank.org/INTEXTINDTRAINI/Events/21866024/GTZ_Konferenz_ENGL.pdf (09/09/2016).

⁸ Ibid.

The Kimberley Process Certification Scheme – a “the current international system to deal with the conflict diamonds issue”⁹ can be considered as “a nonbinding international accord among signatory governments”¹⁰ on transparency and accountability in raw materials sector.

The good governance in the raw materials sector has been underlined as an emerging subject during the Germany’s G8 Presidency. Germany has highlighted the importance of the Raw Materials Sector by the following statement: “The future availability of raw materials is currently of great importance owing to the strong increase in demand, also by the emerging economies.”¹¹ “Industrial and newly industrial countries have a special interest in and bear a great deal of responsibility for ensuring that the world's resource wealth is used responsibly in order to make an effective contribution to the development process.”¹² “Therefore, there is an intention to continue to foster transparency in the raw materials sector and strengthening the Extractive Industries Transparency Initiative (EITI) and embark on new ways to certify raw materials.”¹³

The Extractive Industries Transparency Initiative is the essential international initiatives on extractive industries transparency issues. The “progenitor”¹⁴ of this crucial international project has become the “Publish What You Pay”¹⁵ initiative. The misuse of revenues from extractive industries has become explicit problem for resource-rich countries. The Extractive Industries Transparency Initiative is the common effort to solve the problem. As it has been pointed out during the Conference:

⁹ Hendrix, Noland, *Confronting the Curse: The Economics and Geopolitics of Natural Resources Government*, 2014, Peterson Institute for International Economics, 92 et seqq.

¹⁰ *Ibid.*, 94.

¹¹ Report on Growth and Responsibility – Leitmotif for Germany’s G8 Presidency, <http://www.g-8.de/Content/EN/Artikel/2007/03/Anlagen/2007-03-01-g8-schlaglichter-en,property=publicationFile.pdf> (06/11/2016).

¹² *Ibid.*

¹³ *Ibid.*

¹⁴ Hendrix, Noland, *Confronting the Curse: The Economics and Geopolitics of Natural Resources Government*, 2014, Peterson Institute for International Economics, 92 et seqq.

¹⁵ *Ibid.*, 92.

“transparency seems to mitigate corruption.”¹⁶ The Extractive Industries Transparency Initiative comprises two key elements:

-“requiring extractive firms operating within their territory to disclose payments to governments to explore or extract energy or minerals.”¹⁷

-“establishing a formal multistakeholder group that evaluate the information provided by the firms, the government and the third-party administrator”¹⁸.

Requirements of the Extractive Industries Transparency Initiative for implementing countries have been revised in 2016. The IETI – Standard 2016 consists of “eight key requirements”¹⁹:

- Requirement 1 *Oversight by the multi-stakeholder group* – “the EITI requires effective multi-stakeholder oversight, including a functioning multi-stakeholder group that involves the government, companies, and the full, independent, active and effective participation of civil society.”²⁰

- Requirement 2 *Legal and institutional framework, including allocation of contracts and licenses* – “disclosing of information related to the rules for how the extractive sector is managed, enabling stakeholders to understand the laws and procedures for the award of exploration and production rights, the legal, regulatory and contractual framework that apply to the extractive sector, and the institutional responsibilities of the State in managing.

¹⁶ Report of international Conference: Transparency in the Extractive Sector, http://site.resources.worldbank.org/INTEXTINDTRAINI/Events/21866024/GTZ_Konferenz_ENGL.pdf (09/09/2016).

¹⁷ Hendrix, Noland, *Confronting the Curse: The Economics and Geopolitics of Natural Resources* Government, 2014, Peterson Institute for International Economics, 103.

¹⁸ *Ibid.*

¹⁹ The EITI Standard 2016, https://eiti.org/sites/default/files/documents/english-eiti-standard_0.pdf (18/09/2016).

²⁰ *Ibid.*

- Requirement 3 *Exploration and Production* – “disclosing of information related to exploration and production, enabling stakeholders to understand the potential of the sector.”²¹

- Requirement 4 *Revenue collection* – “a comprehensive reconciliation of company payments and government revenues from the extractive industries.”²²

- Requirement 5 *Revenue allocation* – “disclosing of information related to revenue allocations, enabling stakeholders to understand how revenues are recorded in the national and where applicable, subnational budgets.”²³

- Requirement 6 *Social and economic spending* – “disclosing of information related to social expenditures and the impact of the extractive sector on the economy, helping stakeholders to assess whether the extractive sector is leading to the desirable social and economic impacts and outcomes.”²⁴

- Requirement 7 *Outcomes and impact* – “Regular disclosure of extractive industry data is of little practical use without public awareness, understanding of what the figures mean, and public debate about how resource revenues can be used effectively.”²⁵

- Requirement 8 *Compliance and deadlines for implementing countries* – “This section outlines the timeframes established by the EITI Board for publication of EITI Reports, annual progress reports and Validation.”²⁶

The Extractive Industries Transparency Initiative in Standard 2016 has done the major amendment closely relative to the OPL 245 case. The amendment is about the “beneficial ownership transparency for extractive

²¹Ibid.

²² Ibid.

²³ Ibid.

²⁴ Ibid.

²⁵ Ibid.

²⁶ Ibid.

companies a requirement for membership.”²⁷ The Requirement 2.5 (c) declares that as of “1 January 2020, it is required that implementing countries request, and companies disclose, beneficial ownership information for inclusion in the EITI report.”²⁸ The EITI – Standard should be implemented not only by governments and by the companies. It has well known fact “the more countries begin implementing EITI and validation standards tighten, the more companies will be subject to host government the sector”²⁹ “pressure to participate.”³⁰ International organizations have been commenced transparency initiatives. The United Nations General Assembly Resolution on “Strengthening Transparency in Industries” is an immense intention to reinforce the matters in regard of the extractive industries. The Resolution highlighted the significance of the Extractive Industries Transparency Initiative: “noting the efforts of countries that are participating in all relevant voluntary initiatives to improve transparency and accountability in industries, including in the Extractive Industries Transparency Initiative in the extractive sector, and to share their experience with interested Member States.”³¹

Another joined action has been initiated by the UN is the UN Global Compact principles. The UN Global Compact is a “voluntary initiative designed to help fashion more humane world by enlisting business to follow ten principles concerning human rights, labor, the environment, and corruption.”³² The UN Global Compact has been evaluated as “a forum whose aim is to facilitate cooperation among the various economic and

²⁷ Shell and Eni’s Misadventures in Nigeria: Shell and Eni at risk of losing enormous oil block acquired in corrupt deal, Briefing Nov. 17, 2015, 12, <https://www.globalwitness.org/en/campaigns/oil-gas-and-mining/shell-and-eni-misadventures-nigeria/> (15/11/2016).

²⁸ The EITI Standard 2016, https://eiti.org/sites/default/files/documents/english-eiti-standard_0.pdf (18/09/2016).

²⁹ Ibid.

³⁰ Hendrix, Noland, *Confronting the Curse: The Economics and Geopolitics of Natural Resources Government*, 2014, Peterson Institute for International Economics, 106.

³¹ UNGA Res. A/RES/62/274, Plen. 56, 11/09/2008.

³² Williams, *The UN Global Compact: The Challenge and the Promise*, Business Ethics Quarterly, 2004, 755.

social actors in global arena in order to promote general UN values”³³ by some scholars. Environmental and transparency issues have been emphasized in these UN Global Compact Principles. Anti-corruption Principle (Principle 10) underlined that “business should work against corruption in all its forms, including extortion and bribery.”³⁴

Germany is extremely reliant on “imports of industrial raw materials.”³⁵ Therefore, the national strategy of the Raw Materials Supply Management is a “significant component of German economic policy.”³⁶ The Federal Government’s Raw Materials Strategy emphasized nine “core objectives”³⁷. They cover “trade barriers and competition”³⁸ issues, “raw materials diversifying”³⁹ issues, “recycling”⁴⁰ matters, “bilateral raw materials partnerships”⁴¹ initiatives, “transparency of extractive industries”⁴² approaches and “integration of national measures with European Raw Materials Policy”⁴³.

Germany encourages different crucial international initiatives to deepen transparency and good governance in extractive industries. One of them is the Extractive Industries Transparency Initiative. Germany has underlined its “contribution addressing to transparency and good governance in its international relations”⁴⁴ on the international conference dedicated to transparency issues in Berlin 2007.

³³ Thérien, Pouliot. *The Global Compact: Shifting the Politics of International Development?*, Global Governance, 2006, 56 et seqq.

³⁴ The Ten Principles of the UN Global Compact, <https://www.unglobalcompact.org/what-is-gc/mission/principles> (11/12/2016).

³⁵ The German Government’s Raw Materials strategy, www.bmwi.de (11/12/2016).

³⁶ Ibid.

³⁷ Ibid.

³⁸ Ibid.

³⁹ Ibid.

⁴⁰ Ibid.

⁴¹ Ibid.

⁴² Ibid.

⁴³ Ibid.

⁴⁴ Report of international Conference: Transparency in the Extractive Sector, http://site.resources.worldbank.org/INTEXTINDTRAINI/Events/21866024/GTZ_Konferenz_ENGL.pdf (09/09/2016).

Germany has obtained “candidate country status”⁴⁵ of the Extractive Industries Transparency Initiative in February 2016. Germany is expecting to enhance its extractive industry policy by implementing the Extractive Industries Transparency Initiative Standard. Two key objectives have been considered within the German Government’s Raw Materials Strategy on extractive industries transparency matters:

- “enhancing the transparency of cash of flow in conjunction with exploration activities and the extraction of resources within the framework of the Extractive Industries Transparency Initiative,”⁴⁶

- “establishing open raw materials markets, the environmentally compatible extraction of raw materials, and the increase in welfare due to enhanced transparency, as a contribution towards economic development.”⁴⁷

Moreover, Germany supports the extractive industries policy within the European Union framework. The European Union Directive 2013/34/EU declares the importance of the transparency of revenues from the extractive industries sector by stating the following: “in order to provide for enhanced transparency of payments made to governments, large undertakings and public-interest entities which are active in the extractive industry or logging of primary forests should disclose material payments made to governments in the countries in which they operate in a separate report, on an annual basis and the report should include types of payments comparable to those disclosed by an undertaking participating in the Extractive Industries Transparency Initiative.”⁴⁸ Furthermore, the special provisions of the transparency in the extractive industries have been promoted in the

⁴⁵ EITI Report on Implementation of the EITI in G7, EU and OECD countries, <https://eiti.org/sites/default/files/documents/study-on-eiti-implementation-in-oecd-countries.pdf> (03/12/2016).

⁴⁶ The German Government’s Raw Materials strategy, www.bmwi.de, 15.

⁴⁷ Ibid.

⁴⁸ DIRECTIVE 2013/34/EU on the annual financial statements, consolidated financial statements and related reports of certain types of undertakings, amending Directive 2006/43/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council and repealing Council Directives 78/660/EEC and 83/349/EEC, OJ L182 of 29/06/2013, 24.

German Development Policy. One of the key goals of German development policy is “strengthening the transparency, accountability and efficiency of the state on the basis of democracy and the rule of law.”⁴⁹

The special actions in regard of transparency in the extractive industries include the following methods:

- “strengthening the role of the public budget as a central policy control instrument and of the actors in parliament, government and the administration who are involved in the budget process (budget preparation and execution),”⁵⁰

- “strengthening independent and effective external financial controls (e.g. audit offices, civil society organizations),”⁵¹

- “improving the capacity for generating revenue through reforms of revenue policy and management, including dovetailing the two (e.g. promoting tax equity, customs modernization),”⁵²

- “promoting budgeting approaches that take account of impacts on relevant target groups (e.g. gender-responsive budgeting).”⁵³

Norway is rated as “the tenth largest oil exporter and the third largest gas producer”⁵⁴ in the world. The oil industry of Norway is “the largest industry measured in value creation, State revenues and export value.”⁵⁵ “The industry has thus been highly important for the Norwegian economy and the financing of the Norwegian welfare state.”⁵⁶ As it was pointed out above, the Extractive Industries Transparency Initiative has emitted “a global standard for transparency in the oil, gas and mining

⁴⁹ Strategies 178: Promotion of Good Governance in German Development Policy, <https://www.bmz.de> (12/10/2016).

⁵⁰ Ibid.

⁵¹ Ibid.

⁵² Ibid.

⁵³ Ibid.

⁵⁴ <https://eiti.org/norway> (07/12/2016).

⁵⁵ Report on Facts 2014: The Norwegian Petroleum Sector, http://www.npd.no/Global/Engelsk/3-Publications/Facts/Facts2014/Facts_2014_netting.pdf (07/12/2016).

⁵⁶ Ibid.

industries”⁵⁷ and the main “subject is a standard for publishing cash flows between companies in the extraction industry and the government.”⁵⁸ Norway supports the Extractive Industries Transparency Initiative since 2003.⁵⁹ The Extractive Industries Transparency Initiative application has been extended to oil and gas industries in Norway.

Norway has been recognized as “the best example for its transparent management of oil revenues.”⁶⁰ It ought to be emphasized that Norway has been “compliant with the Extractive Industries Transparency Initiative requirements since March 2011.”⁶¹ The “status of compliant”⁶² means that Norway has published “satisfactory reports”⁶³ and has “effective overseeing mechanisms”⁶⁴ within the agenda of the Extractive Industries Transparency Initiative. The supervision mechanism over transparency and accountability of petroleum activities has been applied through the national legislation.

Norway has implemented the Extractive Industries Transparency Initiative’s goals into national legislation. “The Petroleum Act”⁶⁵ is the major legal instrument to regulate the transparency aspect of good governance over natural resources. Essential rules related to the licensing, taxation and exploration matters have been issued in the Act.

Furthermore, Norway has established the Norwegian Oil Fund. “The revenue management and expenditure (3.7-3.8) all the state's revenues

⁵⁷ Report on Extractive Industries Transparency Initiative: Reconciliation of cash flows from the Petroleum Industry in Norway, <http://www.resourcegovernance.org/sites/default/files/Norway%20EITI%20Reconciliation%20Report%202008.pdf> (13/12/2016).

⁵⁸ Ibid.

⁵⁹ Ibid.

⁶⁰ Report of international Conference: Transparency in the Extractive Sector, http://site.resources.worldbank.org/INTEXTINDTRAINI/Events/21866024/GTZ_Konferenz_ENGL.pdf (09/09/2016).

⁶¹ EITI – The Norwegian Annual Activity Report 2014, https://eiti.org/sites/default/files/documents/2014_norway_annual_activity_report.pdf (22/11/2016).

⁶² Ibid.

⁶³ Ibid.

⁶⁴ Ibid.

⁶⁵ Ibid.

from petroleum activities and gas sector are transferred into The Government Pension Fund.”⁶⁶

One of the main requirements of the Extractive Industries Transparency Initiative Policy is contract transparency. Norway has included the contract transparency questions in its work plan within the framework of the Extractive Industries Transparency initiative.

According to special report, Norway has presented only “partial disclosure”⁶⁷ of the contracts. The Report has recited the following: “license agreements themselves are not publicly disclosed, but standard license agreements related to exploration and production are available from the Ministry of Energy of Norway.”⁶⁸

As it has been pointed out before, Norway is a very active supporter of the Extractive Industries Transparency Initiative. The Government of Norway has implemented various crucial reforms in regard of transparency in the extractive sector. However, there is still space for more improvements and intensions. One of the key intentions of Norway within the context of the Extractive Industries Transparency Initiative is the “encouraging good practice in other countries.”⁶⁹ Only joint actions on international level can to achieve significant reforms related to transparency in extractive industries.

Russia is a very crucial actor within the extractive industries governance in the world. Especially it is a “dominant player”⁷⁰ on the

⁶⁶ EITI – The Norwegian Annual Activity Report 2014, https://eiti.org/sites/default/files/documents/2014_norway_annual_activity_report.pdf (22/11/2016)

⁶⁷ EITI Brief on Contracts Transparency in EITI countries: a review on how countries report on Government’s contract transparency policy, https://eiti.org/sites/default/files/documents/eiti_brief_on_contract_transparency.pdf (18/10/2016).

⁶⁸ Ibid.

⁶⁹ EITI Report on Implementation of the EITI in G7, EU and OECD countries, <https://eiti.org/sites/default/files/documents/study-on-eiti-implementation-in-oecd-countries.pdf> (03/12/2016).

⁷⁰ Petersen, Barysch, Russia, China and the Geopolitics of energy in Central Asia, 201, 5 et seqq, http://carnegieendowment.org/files/petersen_cer_eng.pdf (11/12/2016).

“Eurasian energy map.”⁷¹ Russia grips “the world’s eighth largest crude oil reserves”⁷² and “the world’s largest gas exporter.”⁷³

Considering Russia within the international good governance initiatives is quite a complicated issue. Russia tries to “ignore emerging performs of transparency in oil and gas sectors” in order to follow its specified “approach to energy security.”⁷⁴ Consequently, Russia prefers to stay away from the However, the security approach is not the only reason to avoid the international initiatives in regard of extractive industries. It is well-known fact that for many decades developing resource-rich countries have very corrupted regimes. Russia is not an exception. Moreover, Russia has no “national laws to worry about the prosecution for bribing of foreign officials.”⁷⁵

Nevertheless, during the G20 meeting in Saint Petersburg Russia has changed its attitude towards the Extractive Industries Transparency Initiative. The Saint Petersburg Declaration emphasizes following statement about the transparency concerns in extractive industries:

- “combating corruption in high-risk sectors,”⁷⁶
- “enhancing initiatives aimed at increasing extractive transparency, including voluntary participation in the Extractives Industries Transparency Initiative.”⁷⁷

Russia is not still “applicant”⁷⁸ to the Extractives Industries Transparency Initiative. Particularly from the BRICS countries (Brazil, Russia,

⁷¹ Ibid.

⁷² Ibid.

⁷³ Inozemtcev, The “Resource Curse” and Russia’s Economic Crisis, 2009, <https://www.chathamhouse.org/events/view/155549> (13/09/2016).

⁷⁴ Makarychev, Russia’s Energy Policy: Between Security and Transparency, 2006, <http://www.ponarseurasia.org/node/5095> (12/12/2016).

⁷⁵ Vogl, Natural Resources, Natural Corruption? How can transparency help end the fleecing of resource-rich countries by their corrupt leaders?, 2012, <http://www.theglobalist.com/natural-resources-natural-corruption/> (02/12/2016).

⁷⁶ Ibid.

⁷⁷ Ibid.

India, China and South Africa) have fallen “outside its scope and are not covered by the EITI standard.”⁷⁹

Russian Government has initiated next steps towards the Extractives Industries Transparency Initiative inside of the BRICS countries framework. Therefore, Russia has mentioned the possibility on “further talks on implementation with the private sector in regard of transparency.”⁸⁰

The shaky position of the “civil society”⁸¹ and “lack of political opposition”⁸² remain the control over the extractive sector under the corrupted elite. The artificial and unproductive overseeing mechanism over extractive industries revenue exists in Russia. So-called the “Stabilization Fund”⁸³ has been arranged to “accumulate revenues from the export duty for oil and the tax on the oil mining operations.”⁸⁴

Russia has a big chain of debatable problems in regard of transparency in the extractive industries. Corrupted political and business elite tries to hold the sector under the control. Special forms of partnership like “mixture of government-owned and privately”⁸⁵ keep the “Russian corporations dominated”⁸⁶ in extractive industries sector.

Kazakhstan is a post-Soviet republic with huge natural resources potential. Nowadays Kazakhstan is amid the “top 15 countries in the world

⁷⁸ Халилова, Леонтьева, Гайнуллина, Коррупированность отношений в сфере природопользования, или Проклятие природных ресурсов, Актуальные проблемы экономики и права. 2016, 26-34.

⁷⁹ Briefing on the Extractive Industries Transparency Initiative: state of play, [http://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/bibliotheque/briefing/2014/140758/LDM_BRI\(2014\)140758_REV1_EN.pdf](http://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/bibliotheque/briefing/2014/140758/LDM_BRI(2014)140758_REV1_EN.pdf) (10/11/2016).

⁸⁰ EITI Report “Implementation of the EITI in G7,EU and OECD countries”, 15.02.2016, 31.

⁸¹ Ibid.

⁸² Ibid.

⁸³ Ibid.

⁸⁴ Ibid

⁸⁵ Belyi, Greene et al., Russia a complex transition: Increasing Transparency and Accountability in the Extractive Industries, 2012, <http://www.transparency-initiative.org/wp-content/uploads/2012/12/TAIRussia.pdf> (28/11/2016).

⁸⁶ Ibid.

when it comes to essential oil reserves, 62% of the country is occupied by oil and gas areas.”⁸⁷

Kazakhstan has joined the Extractive Industries Transparency Initiative in 2013. The famous “Kazakhgate scandal”⁸⁸ around the corrupted political elite of the country “has spoiled the investment climate”⁸⁹ in republic. Therefore, it should be stated Kazakhstan has pursued the urgent steps in order to improve the investment climate of the country.

The famous scandal in mining sector, so-called “Kazakhmys case”⁹⁰ has shackled the investment situation even more. Foreign investors seek for confidentiality in regard of “clean business”.⁹¹ The investors “need to be sure that a company is being unduly influenced from behind the scenes, and that its financial relationships with governments are not contributing to corruption.”⁹² Both of scandals closely related to the transparency lack, weak governance and unsuccessful legislation in the extractive sector of Kazakhstan.

Currently Kazakhstan has accomplished two important enactments according to the Extractive Industries Transparency Initiative Standard. The first achievement in regard of transparency is the “online platform”⁹³ where the companies should file the Extractive Industries Transparency Initiative reports. The Ministry of Energy of the Republic of Kazakhstan has implemented this platform. The companies operated in the extractive industries sector of the country are obliged to publish their reports via this online system.

⁸⁷ https://www.kmgep.kz/eng/about_kazakhstan/oil_and_gas_sector/ (23/11/2016).

⁸⁸ Зачем Казахстану ИПДО: Астана реализует план прозрачности нефтегазовой отрасли, 2013, http://rusenergy.com/ru/articles/articles.php?id=69780&phrase_id=3426785 (06/11/2016).

⁸⁹ Ibid.

⁹⁰ Risky business: Kazakhstan, Kazakhmys plc and the London Stock exchange, Report/Jul. 13, 2010, 4, <https://www.globalwitness.org/ru/reports/risky-business/> (19/10/2016).

⁹¹ Ibid.

⁹² Ibid.

⁹³ Отчет о проделанной работе по реализации ИПДО в Казахстане, https://eiti.org/sites/default/files/documents/2014_kazakhstan_annual_activity_report_ru.pdf (07/01/2017).

Within the framework of the Extractive Industries Transparency Initiative, the Republic of Kazakhstan has implemented “the Electronic Licensing System for subsoil use”⁹⁴. The online licensing and reporting are the big steps towards the transparency in extractive industries in Kazakhstan. However, there is still space for improving the transparency policy. Furthermore, Kazakhstan is of the “19 countries”⁹⁵ has mentioned the contracts transparency issues in its work plan for the Extractive Industries Transparency Initiative. According to Requirements 2.4 of the Extractive Industries Transparency Initiative Standard the “implementing countries are encouraged to publicly disclose that provide the terms attached to the exploitation of oil, gas and minerals.”⁹⁶ Kazakhstan still disregards the Requirement. The country has no any “law on disclosing the contracts”⁹⁷ conferring the Extractive Industries Transparency Initiative’s report on contract transparency matters.

The developing resource – rich countries, like Kazakhstan, always encounter so-called “natural resources curse”⁹⁸. Moreover, Kazakhstan faces the “Caspian region curse”⁹⁹ problems. Kazakhstan has to reconsider national approach in regard of the natural resources management in order to elucidate the “resource curse” effect.

Nowadays, the humanity encounters many problems related to natural resources use. The States, Governments and International Organizations try to issues a plenty of reforms in regard of development of

⁹⁴ Ibid.

⁹⁵ EITI Brief on Contracts Transparency in EITI countries: a review on how countries report on Government’s contract transparency policy, https://eiti.org/sites/default/files/documents/eiti_brief_on_contract_transparency.pdf (18/10/2016).

⁹⁶ The EITI Standard 2016, https://eiti.org/sites/default/files/documents/english-eiti-standard_0.pdf (18/09/2016).

⁹⁷ EITI Brief on Contracts Transparency in EITI countries: a review on how countries report on Government’s contract transparency policy, https://eiti.org/sites/default/files/documents/eiti_brief_on_contract_transparency.pdf (18/10/2016).

⁹⁸ *Meissner*, The Resource Curse and Rentier States in Caspian Region: A Need for Context Analysis, GIGA Working Paper, 05/2010, https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=1612183 (09/12/2016).

⁹⁹ Ibid.

the mechanisms saving the natural resources, especially for future generations. Various international tools linked to this debatable issue have been created by states and international organizations. Of the major tools is a good governance concept. It is a complex of legal instruments, reforms and international initiatives.

The good governance in the Raw Materials Sector has been maintained in the Master's Thesis. The study emphasized two aspect of good governance over natural resources: environmental and transparency (financial).

As an illustration, the study has examined four different prevailing approaches of implementation of international regimes in regard of the good governance over natural resources. In particular, two developed (Germany, Norway) and two developing (Russia, Kazakhstan) have been observed in the thesis.

As can be seen, Germany and Norway have made essential attempts in regard of environmental governance over natural resources on national and international levels. The operative implied mechanisms have a positive effect on the extractive industries in regard of environment. Germany, as it has been mentioned before, still has a plenty of environmental problems. Nevertheless, the realized national strategies based on the United Nations Environment Program approach have positive outcome in the extractive sector as well. The emergence of environmental governance over natural resources has been highlighted in the German's Government's Raw Materials. Additionally, German and Norway explicitly promote the environmental governance over natural resources thought the partnership on regional and international levels.

Kazakhstan and Russia are countries with big bunch of environmental problems. These countries have not performed an effective legal framework in regard of environmental governance over natural resources. The next question is the transparency policy in the extractive industries of the four countries (Germany, Norway, Russia, and Kazakhstan). The question has been scrutinized within the framework of the Extractive Industries

Transparency Initiative. The process of implementation the requirements of the Extractive Industries Transparency Initiative within the national legal framework has been started Norway. Germany has maintained the transparency in the extractive industries though many international initiatives. Especially, the transparency in the raw materials sector has been promoted during G8 presidency of Germany. Norway and Germany are very active and productive regarding, the national legal reforms related to the transparency in the extractive industries. However, the full publicly disclosing of contracts has been reached yet by the countries. Germany has just joined the initiative in 2016. Norway has reached only partial disclosing of the contacts. Russia tries to ignore the Extractive Industries Transparency Initiative referring on the classified content of the national strategy on natural resources. However, the political elite highlights the transparency issues in the extractive industries on different international forums. Kazakhstan has special position in regard of the Extractive Industries Transparency Initiative. The country has accepted the initiative only as a method to improve the investment climate of the country after sensational scandal linked to extractive industries of the country. However, the country has implemented online platform of licensing for subsoil use. The contract transparency is still debatable issue, despite the country has added the contract transparency requirement to its work plan with the Extractive Industries Transparency Initiative. Developed countries, like Germany and Norway, have commenced essential reforms in regard of the extractive industries. It has to be noted that the Extractive Industries Transparency Initiative is one the operative tool related to good governance over natural resources. Developing countries have to reconsider their approach in regard of both aspects of good governance over natural resources.

Bibliography:

Aponte, The Role of International Law in Intrastate Natural Resource Allocation, Proceedings of the Annual Meeting, American Society of International Law, Vol. 106, 04/2012, 75-78.

Armstrong et al., *Routledge Handbook of International Law*, 2009, Taylor & Francis Group.

Arreaza, *The WTO, Natural Resources, Trade, and Sustainable Development: commentaries on recent trends in international economic law*, 2016. Available at <https://ssrn.com/abstract=2859377> (04/12/2016).

Barral, *Sustainable Development in International law: Nature and Operation of an Evaluative Legal Form*, EJIL, 05/2012. Available at <https://academic.oup.com/ejil/article/23/2/377/487236/Sustainable-Development-in-International-Law> (09/12/2016).

Belyi, Greene, Chernyakhovskaya, Demakova, Selezneva, *Russia a complex transition: Increasing Transparency and Accountability in the Extractive Industries*, 2012. Available at <http://www.transparency-initiative.org/wp-content/uploads/2012/12/TAIRussia.pdf> (28/11/2016).

Birnie, Boyle, Redgwell, *International Law and Environment*, 3d ed. 2009, Oxford.

Bowling, Pierson, Ratté, *The Common Concern of Humankind: A Potential Framework for a New International Legally Binding Instrument on the Conservation and Sustainable Use of Marine Biological Diversity in the High Seas*. Available at http://www.un.org/depts/los/biodiversity/prepcom_files/BowlingPiersonandRatte_Common_Concern.pdf (17/11/2016).

Bungenberg/Hobe, *Permanent Sovereignty over Natural Resources*, 2015, Springer.

Cooney, *The Precautionary Principle in Biodiversity Conservation and Natural Resources Management*, 2004, IUCN.

Curtis, *Russia: a country study book*, 1st ed. 1998. Available at <https://cdn.loc.gov/master/frd/.../ru/russiacountrystu00curt/russiacountrystu00curt.pdf> (13/11/2016).

Fitzmaurice, Ong, Merkouris, *Research handbook on International environmental law*, 2010, Edward Elgar Publishing Limited.

Feichtner, *International (Investment) Law and Distribution Conflicts over Natural Resources*, 2014. Available at <http://publikationen.ub.uni-frankfurt.de/frontdoor/index/index/docId/33380> (30.10.2016).

Gardner, Respecting Sovereignty, *Fordham Environmental Law Review*, 11/2011, 133-138.

Grieves, Forest L, Environmental Protection in the Federal Republic of Germany: Focus on the Saarland." *Environmental Review: ER*, 1984, 252-269.

Gupta, Mason, *Transparency in Global Environmental Governance: Critical Perspectives*. 2014, MIT Press.

Hendrix, Noland, *Confronting the Curse: The Economics and Geopolitics of Natural Resources Government*, 2014, Peterson Institute for International Economics.

Hossain/Chowdhury, *Permanent Sovereignty over Natural Resources in International Law: Principle and Practice*, 1984, Frances Pinter (Publishers)

Inozemtcev, The "Resource Curse" and Russia's Economic Crisis, 2009. Available at <https://www.chathamhouse.org/events/view/155549> (13/09/2016).

Kiss, Alexandre. The Common Heritage of Mankind: Utopia or Reality? *International Journal*, 1985, pp. 423-441.

Meissner, The Resource Curse and Rentier States in Caspian Region: A Need for Context Analysis, GIGA Working Paper, 05/2010. Available at https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=1612183 (09/12/2016).

Makarychev, Russia's Energy Policy: Between Security and Transparency, 2006. Available at <http://www.ponarseurasia.org/node/5095> (12/12/2016)

Martella, Grosko, *International Environmental Law: The Practitioner's Guide to the Laws of the Planet*, 2014, ABA Publishing.

Swartz, State Sovereignty and Environmental law, *European Journal of Business and Social Sciences*, 11/ 2014.

Nogoibaeva, Leighton, Mateeve, Baetov, Myrsaliev, Koichikulova, Tashmatova, Murzaeva, *Contemporary International law: materials and cases*, 2012, Bishkek.

Petersen, Barysch, Russia, China and the Geopolitics of energy in Central Asia, 2011, Center for European Reform (CER).

- Rotberg, Corruption, Global Security, and World Order, Brookings Institution Press, 2009.
- Shaw, International Law, 5th ed. 2003, Cambridge.
- Schaber, Property Rights and the Resource Curse, Global Governance, 06/2011, 185-196.
- Shelton, Common concern of humanity, 2009. Available at <http://ias.jak.ppke.hu/hir/ias/20091sz/05.pdf> (02/12/2016).
- Shelton, Kiss, Judicial Handbook on Environmental Law, United Nations Environment Programme, 2005, UNEP.
- Schrijver, Development without destruction, 2010, Indiana University Press.
- Schrijver, Sovereignty over natural resources: balancing rights and duties, 1997, Cambridge.
- Schrijver, Weiss, International Law and Sustainable Development. Principles and Practice, 2004, Koninklijke Brill NV.
- Thérien/Pouliot. The Global Compact: Shifting the Politics of International Development? Global Governance, vol. 12, no. 1, 2006, 55-75.
- Toksoz, Good Governance: improving quality of life, 2008, TESEV.
- Vogl, Natural Resources, Natural Corruption? How can transparency help end the fleecing of resource-rich countries by their corrupt leaders? 2012. Available at <http://www.theglobalist.com/natural-resources-natural-corruption/> (02/12/2016).
- Williams, The UN Global Compact: The Challenge and the Promise, Business Ethics Quarterly, 10/ 2004, 755-774.
- Халилова, Леонтьева, Гайнуллина, Коррупированность отношений в сфере природопользования, или Проклятие природных ресурсов, Актуальные проблемы экономики и права, 2016, 26-34.

Copyright©Nilyufar ABDULATOVA

Greek Youth and the EU: What is the Relationship and How Can It Be Improved

Dr. Anna VALLIANATOU

annavallianatou@yahoo.com

University of Athens, Greece

Ph.D. Candidate Dimitris THOMAKOS

dthomakos@hotmail.com

Panteion University, Greece

Director Yannis MASTROGEORGIU

info@diktio.eu

DIKTIO, Greece

Dr. Evi HATZIANDREOU

info@diktio.eu

DIKTIO, Greece

Abstract. Euroscepticism among European youth is prevalent, not uniformly among the Member States but existing nevertheless. A survey of young Greeks reveals contradictions characterised by inconsistencies which reflect superficial attitudes, low appreciation or ignorance of the initiatives and achievements of the EU, its policies and their impact on citizens' lives. Europe's young generations need to be at the centre of policies. As this alone does not suffice, education and innovative communication are pillars for effectively reaching both hearts and minds across the Continent reinvigorating the European Project.

Keywords: Youth and the EU, Greece, European identity, Youth policies.

Introduction

The future of Europe lies with its youth. The European Union (EU) recently turned 60, savouring its success and, regardless of a few failures along the way, managed to overcome a significant crisis with a renewed interest and commitment to the European project. In achieving those noble goals, the commitment and engagement of the younger generations of

Europeans is of paramount importance. Yet, young people are both systematically underrepresented and feel excluded from society. The erosion of trust in the system and its institutions is something the EU cannot afford. Certain troubling signs are on the wall. Support among young people for the European project is in decline or may be mixed at best, depending on the Member State. A proxy indicator of the decline of support for the EU among young Europeans is the decrease in participation in elections. According to the latest Flash Eurobarometer (European Youth Report, 2017), the percentage of Europeans aged 15-30 who voted in an election past the three years decreased from 80% in 2011 to 73% in 2013, and to 63% in 2015 and 64%, in 2017. Furthermore, although almost two-thirds of respondents (64%) in Member States say they voted in a political election in the last three years, the votes are most likely to have been on a local level (44%), followed by national (43%), regional (31%). The 2015 Flash Eurobarometer showed 31% participation at EU level voting. Respondents in Sweden (63%) and Belgium (59%) seem to be the most likely to have voted at the EU level, while the lowest proportion of respondents were in Slovenia, Hungary, Lithuania, and the United Kingdom (all 19%). Some recent polls raise some alarming issues as well. The special European Parliament Eurobarometer on Youth (Eurobarometer, 2016) revealed an impression of exclusion because of the economic crisis prevalent among 57% of the respondents at the European level, with 39% indicated disagreement with the statement. It comes as no surprise that rates are higher in countries that suffered due to the crisis, with Greece at the top; 93% of the country's young people felt excluded. In comparison with Maltese, where 28% of the young generation reported the same concern. As alarming as these findings are, one from another recent survey, "Young Europe 2017 – The Youth Study of the TUI Foundation" (Young Europe, 2017), found that on average 21% of respondents wanted their country to leave the EU and almost 40%, except for the 60% of the Greek youth, wanted the EU to return power to national governments. It is indicative and perhaps revealing that for three out of four young Europeans, the core of the EU is not its shared values but rather

economic cooperation. Only half of young Europeans regard democracy as the best form of government (!). The particularities of the Greek case have already been mentioned.

Austerity measures have sparked widespread participation in spontaneous and informal social movements that invested in “revolutionary conservatism”. Other raw reactions towards these measures and the Greek political system were expressed via negative slogans and violent behaviour (such as occupying or destroying public property). Furthermore, undemocratic, violent, and dark forms of activity by the civil society have arisen under the guardianship of Golden Dawn (a pro-Nazi party) or by radical leftist groups. Young Greeks feel that their prospects have been curtailed if not eliminated. An erosion of trust in institutions – including in the EU – may turn out to be detrimental and corrode hopes of solid recovery. It goes without saying that surveys like the ones mentioned above and the feedback they provide is essential in guiding policymaking, particularly during a period of crisis in which the European project and its ideals are challenged and disputed.

Our Study: Rationale and Methods

To explore the issue further, we conducted an online survey of young people called “YOU & EUROPE”. The survey was an integral part of the Jean Monnet Project IDEA “Aurora Through European Identity and Integration”¹. IDEA’s broader aim was to foster young people’s knowledge of EU issues and raise awareness of how EU policies positively impact daily lives through a “play & learn” method utilizing words similar in many languages, originating from a common root of the Indo-European language. YOU & EUROPE’s objective was to elicit views on EU-related issues, such as Euroscepticism, information about the benefits of EU integration, and awareness about how EU policies positively impacted their daily lives. The survey’s target group was Greeks ages 16 to 25 years old. While surveys on European issues

¹ “Idea 4 Europe”, <http://idea4europe.eu/site/> (accessed 28 March 2018). PROJECT NUMBER -574833-EPP-1-2016-EL-EPPJMO-PROJECT

occasionally include younger views, a primary goal of this survey was to hear from a segment not reached by traditional methods of polling (i.e., landline telephone). Hence an online survey in collaboration with the most popular youth TV channel in the country, like MAD TV and radio, were used via social media outlets. A comprehensive 15-question questionnaire was initially developed. The questionnaire of the initial survey was pilot-tested in a group of student members of the DIKTIO Network for Reform in Greece and Europe. The time of completion varied from 12 to 15 minutes.

To provide extra incentive for participation in the survey, a weekly electronic drawing selected one respondent who would win a tablet or a smartphone. The initial questionnaire was uploaded and promoted accordingly on the website of MAD TV for almost two months (from 19 December 2016 to 14 February 2017). It was quite disheartening that despite the active promotion by MAD and DIKTIO, from December 19, 2016, to February 14, 2017, only 170 questionnaires were answered, a number far below the required target of at least 1,000. This was quite a disappointing finding; we reviewed some of the respondent's profiles/responses to explore whether it reflected a general lukewarm interest of youth on issues related to the EU, a short attention span, or both. After further consultation, to achieve the goal of the required number of participants, we shortened the survey from 15 questions to 9 to make the questionnaire less time-consuming and more attractive to "impatient" young people. In order to increase responses rigorous campaign of social media posts from MAD TV and DIKTIO, e-mails, and other contacts helped increase awareness and publish the survey. Between February 14 and March 31, 2017, a total of 1,173 questionnaires were answered, thus achieving the target sample size². The profile of the respondents is a close match to MAD's audience as revealed by their own marketing analysis.

² Youth Survey, You & Europe, *Idea 4 Europe*, <http://www.idea4europe.eu/site/index.php/activities/youth-survey> (accessed 28 March 2018).

Overview of Findings

In this section, we give an overview of the results to guide the discussion and policy recommendations. Detailed responses to each question are shown on the IDEA website: <http://idea4europe.eu/site/images/presentation-english.pdf>.

Based on the responses, the freedom to travel, live, work, and study in the EU are considered the EU's most important benefits (86% of responses), while the preservation of peace on the continent is seen as the EU's greatest achievement. A majority (62.71%) agrees with the statement: "everyday life in Greece is improved by the participation of the country in the European Union". The economic crisis has negatively affected the young Greeks perception of the EU – it is no surprise that 94% consider unemployment and the lack of dynamic growth (among others) to be the most important challenges the EU faces. The creation of a European Job Agency is the first thing the EU should do to bring young people together (56.6%). The EU has the EURES system, which does almost that, but apparently this is not well known among young people. EU initiatives with a significant effect on the everyday lives of the youth do not seem to be fully appreciated, but the abolition of roaming costs in 2017 is a significant benefit of the EU and is popularly known by Greek citizens; that is by a little more than half of the respondents (56.5%). The "Youth Guarantee" scheme is viewed by 85% of respondents as highly important; therefore it proves a factor of great concern. As for the Erasmus+ programme, 16.4% of the respondents were unfamiliar with it, surprising as it is the pivotal programme for free mobility for young people.

By a wide margin (84%), young Greeks support Europe moving forward and the reinforcement of the integration process. The responses do hint at traces of Euroscepticism. It is alarming that four out of ten respondents believe that participation in the EU has not improved. In addition, the fact that one out of four respondents cannot name any EU achievement reflects indifference, lukewarm support, and/or the lack of effective communication on the EU's part.

Overall, analysis of the survey responses reveals contradictions due to inconsistencies. These inconsistencies may reflect superficial attitudes, low appreciation or ignorance of the initiatives and achievements of the EU and impact on citizens' lives. The awareness and knowledge the respondents exhibited may indicate a reflection of the news, their environment, or what they have heard from various other channels, rather than a coherent outcome of an educational process. For example, on one hand, the young people state they support more integration (84%), and on the other hand, a significant proportion (almost 40%) do not believe that Greece's participation in the EU has had any benefit to their lives.

What the rather shallow view reflects is a weakness of an education system to bring and explain the EU (principles, values, benefits) in a fashion that raises interest and awareness. Further, media in Greece does not depict and rarely deals with reporting or explaining the numerous evident and not so evident benefits and improvements of everyday life gained through the country's thirty-six year membership in the European Union. It was disheartening to realise the limited interest in participating in a EU survey. Attention spans seem to be getting shorter and young people do not seem to care much about public-life issues, thinking perhaps they do not concern them. This evident disengagement poses indeed a great danger, leaving the ground open for extremism and demagogy.

Policymaking Recommendations

The imperative to *bring young citizens closer to Europe and to the European identity* is well recognised and acknowledged first and foremost by the European Commission itself and it does not pertain to Greece alone. To achieving this, there are two interrelated prerequisites: First, an increased awareness of the EU and its benefits, and second, more targeted policies and activities to reach out and connect with the youth. An integral part of course is monitoring and evaluating the EU younger generation through systematic surveys. The EU and its Member States must commission and coordinate more frequent surveys to investigate the main concerns of young

people regarding the Union's impact (in each Member State). Then these concerns should be factored into policies in sectors addressing them. For example, emphasis has to be given to the employment and training opportunities that Europe gives its youth, particularly during a crisis. Tania Marrochi argues (Marrochi, 2016) "*youth absenteeism is a broad and complex phenomenon*". Young people's political participation is not in decline, rather in transformation: young people participate more in alternative forms of political engagement – for example, street demonstrations, volunteerism, activism, or signing petitions. Young people seem to have a rather narrow understanding of what constitutes political action, which they mainly associate with the activity in political parties.

Scandals and corruption of the Greek government and the failure of political parties to provide the goods promised have altered the youths trust in the government. This corruption has made the younger generation view the old elite as unable to meet their expectations. Marrochi also states that to engage in the democratic process, people must believe that something is at stake and they can influence the process. Young voters today face challenges with respect to both. They enter with great delay the, worsened by the economic crisis, a phenomenon that postpones the age at which they feel there is something at stake. Young people do not believe they can influence the decision-making process. In fact, the main reason explaining their decision not to vote in elections is the belief that their vote will not change anything and that the political parties are all the same.

Therefore, apart from *running more surveys* targeted at education and youth, reinforcement of civil society would contribute to reinforcing EU values. The future of the Union depends greatly on public support for European values. Europe has to invest in raising awareness about the positive impact that EU policies have in every aspect of citizens' daily life. To achieve this goal, the EU need effective policy planning that will introduce the European context and values into teaching at schools and education institutions as part of the curricula.

More youth events should be established with the example of the European Youth Event, organised by the European Parliament. The event³ takes place in June 2018 in the European Parliament's seat in Strasbourg. It is a unique opportunity for young Europeans to make their voices heard. As stated on the event website, the young participants mainly will be asked to come up with ideas for the future of Europe and to discuss them with European decision-makers. More than 8,000 young people from all over Europe will meet and in July 2018, a report will be published featuring the most concrete ideas discussed during the event and distributed to all Members of the European Parliament (MEPs). In addition, in autumn 2018, some participants will present some of the ideas to parliamentary committees and get feedback from MEPs. A similar event took place in 2016. One would think this event would be publicised in all schools and universities in each Member State, yet it this is not happening. The same goes for the Youth Wiki⁴, Europe's online encyclopaedia of national youth policies. In line with the EU Youth Strategy and the objective of improving knowledge on youth issues in Europe, financial support is provided to National Structures contributing to the creation and maintenance of the Youth Wiki, an interactive tool providing information on the situation of young people in Europe and on national youth policies in a coherent, updated and useable form. The platform is a comprehensive database of the national structures, policies and actions supporting young people. It covers the eight main fields of action identified in the 2010-2018 EU Youth Strategy: education and training, employment and entrepreneurship, health and wellbeing, participation, voluntary activities, social inclusion, youth and the world, and creativity and culture. However, this information also is not sufficiently diffused to young people, meaning its positive impact on promoting European values is very much restricted. School Education

³ For more, see: European Youth Event, European Parliament, <http://www.europarl.europa.eu/european-youth-event/en/news.html> (accessed 28 March 2018).

⁴ "EACEA National Policies Platform", Youth Wiki, European Commission. <https://eacea.ec.europa.eu/national-policies/en/youthwiki> (accessed 28 March 2018).

Gateway⁵ is Europe's online platform for school education, currently available in 23 EU languages, and intended to provide everything teachers need in terms of information, learning and professional development, support and networking, collaborative projects and mobility opportunities, etc. Also, there is the Eurydice network, primarily focused on the way education in Europe is structured and organised at all levels. It aims at contributing a better mutual understanding of the systems in Europe. It provides those responsible for the education systems and policies in Europe with European-level comparative analyses and specific national information in the fields of education and youth, which will assist them in their decision-making.

Should not these events and platforms be publicised in all schools and universities in the EU Member States with the responsibility of the European Parliament offices in each Member State? Should not an employee responsible just for the EU youth campaign and new educational approaches be appointed either to the European Commission Representation or to the European Parliament offices? We are talking about 27 people with a very focused task. It should be taken into account that a significant number of young people participate in Civil Society Organisations (CSOs). According to a European Commission Communication (2012), *“Civil Society Organisations contribute to building more accountable and legitimate states, leading to enhanced social cohesion and more open and deeper democracies”*. The programme Development Education and Awareness Raising (DEAR)⁶ is an expression of the EU's founding values. It promotes values and attitudes that are in line with the Union's own founding values as expressed in Article 2 of the Lisbon Treaty. The aim of DEAR is to “enable every person in Europe to have lifelong access to opportunities to be aware of and to understand global development concerns and the local and personal relevance of those

⁵ School Education Gateway, <https://www.schooleducationgateway.eu/en/pub/index.htm> (accessed 28 March 2018).

⁶ “Development education and awareness raising”, European Commission. https://ec.europa.eu/europeaid/sectors/human-rights-and-governance/development-education-and-awareness-raising_en (accessed 29 March 2018).

concerns, and to enact their rights and responsibilities as inhabitants of an interdependent and changing world by affecting change for a just and sustainable world.”

Civil society is the most important promoter of European values. Traczyk and Chromiec (2018) suggest that an *“instrument probably called the Fund for European Values’ directed at Member States may be necessary”*. It would support NGO funding based on the experience of the value-promoting NGOs supported by the Union in its neighbourhood. In that way the EU would avoid dividing rhetoric and would *“contribute to strengthening the immune system of European democracies”*.

Apart from programmes that promote European values, a EU educational approach, broadly speaking, could exploit the opportunities new technologies and approaches have on higher education. As stated in a report by the European Commission (2014) the use of new technologies offers significant flexibility, which gives the opportunity for lifelong learning and continuing professional development. It enhances the quality and extends the impact of higher education across Europe. Openness and freely accessible education resources needs to be promoted: *“... governments must strongly encourage and support a greater integration of new technologies and associated pedagogical approaches in conventional provision”*.

The goal should be to ensure that all publicly funded education resources are openly available. Traditional providers must diversify their offering and provide more courses online, especially targeting continuing professional development and lifelong learning. The challenges will require targeted actions and support. In that way, non-traditional learners will be reached and Euroscepticism among the young can be better tackled. A number of researchers believe that education is becoming an increasingly important factor in structuring certain political attitudes. The study *“Euroscepticism and education: A longitudinal study of twelve EU Member States, 1973-2010”* (Hakhverdian A., van Elsas E., van der Brug W., Kuhn T., 2013) analysed the changing impact of education on Euroscepticism and

found a widening educational gap in Eurosceptic attitudes. This covers a large amount of data from the Mannheim Eurobarometer trend file 1970-2002 and recent Eurobarometer surveys to 2010 for 12 EU Member States. This study concluded that a higher level of education has a negative effect on Euroscepticism. People with low or medium levels of educational attainment were found to be significantly more Eurosceptic than highly educated Europeans. It is also argued that the effect of education becomes stronger over time. Education is a significant factor with respect to EU-related issues. It is stressed that at least in European politics, the education gap in Euroscepticism is here to stay. It seems that developing a social dimension of European integration might be an effective tool to diminish Eurosceptic attitudes among the low educated. This makes evident the significance of promoting new technologies so all publicly funded education resources would be openly available. Higher active participation of young people in EU actions and initiatives is an effective remedy. EU Youth Mobility programmes comprise a key aspect of EU Youth Policy. Erasmus⁷ heavily promotes mobility for young people through youth exchanges along with the European Voluntary Service and the mobility of young workers in cooperation with partner countries neighbouring the EU. The aim of the mobility activities is to have a positive impact on the qualitative development of youth work, youth policies and youth systems, as well as on the development of students' skills and employability, and to strengthen the European identity of young Europeans by fostering intercultural understanding, multilingualism, equality, inclusion and active citizenship among young Europeans. Another challenge relates to the development of social capital among young people, the empowerment of young people, and

⁷ The Erasmus programme was mainly based on Article 128 of the 1957 Treaty of Rome, which dealt with vocational training, and also with Chapter 3 of the Maastricht Treaty (1993), devoted to education, vocational training, and youth. In 2014, the European Commission launched the Erasmus+ programme, which was an advanced version of the old Erasmus but combined with the Lifelong Learning programme and the Youth in Action programme. Erasmus+ gives the same possibilities but with extra modalities, such as study and work placement. It also offers international modalities with universities outside Europe that have developed a partnership with European universities.

their ability to participate actively in society, in line with the provisions of the Lisbon Treaty, to “encourage the participation of young people in democratic life in Europe”. This issue can also be targeted through non-formal learning activities, which aim at enhancing the skills and competences of young people as well as their active citizenship. Moreover, there is a need to provide youth organisations and youth workers with training and cooperation opportunities, to develop their professionalism and the European dimension of youth work⁸.

Erasmus also supported collective mobility by promoting close cooperation among departments by sending and receiving students. In addition, Erasmus promoted “curricular integration”. This term referred either to joint or coordinated academic activities between the partner departments or to the incorporation of the temporary study period into the home curriculum. This was achieved in a variety of ways, for example through joint curricula, joint selection of students, mandatory periods abroad, regular recognition procedures and approval of study achievement abroad, etc. In addition, Erasmus had an inclusive approach to the temporary study period abroad.

The Erasmus+ programme is a powerful means for bringing youth closer to European ideals and cultivating the European identity. Europeanization is promoted generally to a large extent through the participation of many European partners. Regional approaches emphasize the importance of cooperation between European countries sharing common cultural elements and political interests despite their considerable diversity. Among the positive outcomes of Erasmus mobility is the internationalisation of higher education institutions, enhanced through the participation of education institutes in the programme. It increases internationalisation and Europeanization in the world of knowledge. Even if the mainstream curricula and other study provisions serve other purposes,

⁸ “Erasmus+ Programme Guide”, European Commission. http://ec.europa.eu/programmes/erasmus-plus/sites/erasmusplus2/files/files/resources/erasmus-plus-programme-guide_en.pdf (accessed 28 March 2018).

students in mobility programmes can act with flexibility and accelerate the necessary change.

Moreover, the EU has to run projects specifically targeting young people in collaboration with other European institutions for the same purposes, as well as *educational programmes at schools* to foster the development of a European culture in the next generations. For example, visits by groups of high school students to the EU bodies in Brussels, Strasbourg, and Luxembourg should be deeply integrated into the school life of all EU Member States. In the framework of ERASMUS+, IT-support platforms, such as eTwinning, the School Education Gateway, the European Platform for Adult Learning (EPALE) and the European Youth Portal, offer virtual collaboration spaces, databases of opportunities, communities of practice, and other online services for teachers, trainers, and practitioners in the field of school and adult education, as well as for young people, volunteers, and youth workers across Europe and beyond. All these should be reinforced and better diffused⁹. A newly released Flash Eurobarometer (European Youth Report, 2018) of 15-30-year olds seems to reinforce those ideas and suggestions, indicating a strong majority (over 80%) support compulsory school education on European matters, from the functioning of EU institutions to European culture.

The programme should be extended to include secondary education students as well. Thus, extra funds are required to provide more students and young people around Europe with the chance to participate in the programme. Furthermore, it is crucial to involve young people in the decision-making process, and mainly in the decisions that affect them. In this way, the EU shows them in practice its democratic character, letting their voices be heard. It proves to them that their view can really affect EU policymaking. For example, students can participate in special European Parliament sessions.

Overall, it seems that not so many additional new initiatives are necessary to develop adequate educational approaches in the EU. The

⁹ Ibid.

European Youth Policy already addresses most of the necessities and the EU Youth Strategy¹⁰ seeks to encourage young people to participate in the democratic process and in society through a multipronged approach:

1. Developing mechanisms for engaging in dialogue with young people and facilitating their participation in the shaping of national policies;
2. Supporting youth organisations, including local and national youth councils;
3. Promoting participation by under-represented groups of young people in politics, youth organisations, and other CSOs;
4. Supporting ways of “learning to participate from an early age.

Good ideas and successful implementation, however, do not suffice if your target audience is not reached and offered a convincing message. Hence, the issue of outreach, innovative ways to communicate, and actually reaching consistently and comprehensively Europe’s youth across the continent, in rural and remote areas too, is of paramount importance. It is not surprising that youngest respondents in the latest Flash Eurobarometer¹¹ (European Youth Report 2017), (15-19) were the most likely to mention educating young people in creative and immersive ways through virtual reality, real-life experiences and cultural and artistic events (37%) or making information and news about the EU available through innovative media channels in multiple languages, such as films, series or simulation games (26%). This is clearly a challenge that has not been met yet. Knowledge takes precedence over the opportunity to benefit from anything the EU has to offer.

The “New Narrative for Europe” project, which ran for two years (2016-2017), was specifically targeted to Europe’s young people. A

¹⁰ “EU Youth Strategy”, European Commission. <https://ec.europa.eu/youth/policy/youth-strategy> (accessed 28 March 2018).

¹¹ “Flash Eurobarometer 455, European Youth”, European Commission. <http://ec.europa.eu/commfrontoffice/publicopinion/index.cfm/Survey/getSurveyDetail/instruments/FLASH/surveyKy/2163> (accessed 28 March 2018).

culmination of the findings, “12 ideas for the Future of Europe”¹² covers a wide range of issues European youth believe will reinvigorate their involvement and commitment, from offering wider opportunities beyond current formats in Erasmus, or more widely supporting recycling and positive environmental actions, to making information available through innovative media channels and promoting critical thinking to combat fake news and extremism through citizen education. The latest Flash Eurobarometer that explored further those issues revealed that three areas where respondents indicated that the EU should take action to encourage young people to express solidarity are: education and training (68%), employment (49%) and welfare and social assistance (37%).

Let us hope that the European project will thrive in the next 60 years. Engaging those who will make it a reality and a resounding success requires a comprehensive strategic view of all these policies, a strong focus and a coordinated approach, coupled with commitment, political will, and resources.

Bibliography:

European Commission. “Commission Staff Working Document on Development Education and Awareness Raising in Europe. 2012. Accessed: May, Retrieved from: https://ec.europa.eu/europeaid/sites/devco/files/working-document-development-education-awareness-raising-programme-swd2012457-20121220_en.pdf

European Commission. “High Level Group On The Modernisation of the Higher Education, Report to the European Commission On New Modes Of Learning And Teaching Higher Education”. October 2014.

¹² “European Youth Portal, 12 ideas for the future of Europe, New narrative for Europe Communications Campaign, 2017”, European Commission. http://europa.eu/youth/sites/default/files/12_ideas_for_the_future_of_europe_0.pdf (accessed 28 March 2018).

Website References

“Development education and awareness raising”. European Commission. Accessed 29 March 2018. https://ec.europa.eu/europeaid/sectors/human-rights-and-governance/development-education-and-awareness-raising_en

“EACEA National Policies Platform”. Youth Wiki. European Commission. Accessed 28 March 2018. <https://eacea.ec.europa.eu/national-policies/en/youthwiki>

“Erasmus+ Programme Guide”. European Commission. Accessed 28 March 2018. http://ec.europa.eu/programmes/erasmus-plus/sites/erasmusplus2/files/files/resources/erasmus-plus-programme-guide_en.pdf

“EU Youth Strategy”. European Commission. Accessed 28 March 2018. <https://ec.europa.eu/youth/policy/youth-strategy>

“European Youth Event”, *European Parliament*. Accessed 28 March 2018. <http://www.europarl.europa.eu/european-youth-event/en/news.html>

“European Youth Portal, 12 ideas for the future of Europe, New narrative for Europe Communications Campaign, 2017”. European Commission. Accessed 28 March 2018. http://europa.eu/youth/sites/default/files/12_ideas_for_the_future_of_europe_0.pdf

“Flash Eurobarometer 408 - Report. Survey co-ordinated by the European Commission Directorate-General for Communication, DG COMM Strategy, Corporate Communication Actions and Eurobarometer Unit”. *European Youth*, April 2015: 15. Accessed 28 March 2018.

“Flash Eurobarometer 455 - Report. Survey co-ordinated by the European Commission Directorate- General for Education, Youth, Sport and Culture co-ordinated by the Directorate-General for Communication”. *European Youth Report*, September 2017. Accessed 28 March 2018; <http://ec.europa.eu/commfrontoffice/publicopinion/index.cfm/Survey/getSurveyDetail/instruments/FLASH/surveyKy/2163>

Hakhverdian Armen, Van Elsas Erika, Van der Brug Wouter. Kuhn Theresa. “Euroscepticism And Education: A Longitudinal Study Of 12 EU Member States, 1973-2010”. *Sage Journal*. Volume 14, n. 4, (2013): 552-541. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1465116513489779>.

Marrochi Tania. "The Need To Re-engage Europe's Youth", *European Policy Centre*, July 2016. Accessed 29 March 2018). http://www.epc.eu/pub_details.php?cat_id=4&pub_id=6852

School Education Gateway. Accessed 28 March 2018. <https://www.school-educationgateway.eu/en/pub/index.htm>

Tracyz, Adam and Chromiec Jakub, *European Values Will Not Defend Themselves*, January 2018. Accessed 29 March 2018. <https://www.euractiv.com/section/justice-home-affairs/opinion/european-values-will-not-defend-themselves/>

"Young Europe 2017 – The Youth Study Of TUI Foundation", *TUI Foundation*, May 2017. Accessed 29 March 2018. <https://www.tui-stiftung.de/en/media/young-europe-2017-the-youth-study-of-tui-foundation/>

"Youth Survey, You & Europe". *Idea 4 Europe*. Accessed 28 March 2018. <http://www.idea4europe.eu/site/index.php/activities/youth-survey>

Copyright©Anna VALLIANATOU

Copyright©Dimitris THOMAKOS

Copyright©Yannis MASTROGEORGIU

Copyright©Evi HATZIANDREOU

Migrants' Social Integration through Understanding and Communication. Holistic Approach

Prof. Dr. Habil. Ludmila ROSCA

rosca@irim.md

International Relations Institute of Moldova, Moldova

ECSA Moldova, Moldova

Abstract. The study analyses Moldovan migrants' experience who managed to create 250 organizations in 35 states and have determined political leaders from Moldova to create the Bureau for Relations with Diaspora. The Bureau's key tasks are to maintain a continuous dialogue with the diaspora and negotiate social security programs for migrants in destination countries. The political dialogue between the authorities in the Republic of Moldova and Italy, Portugal, Spain has registered significant results, improving conditions and opportunities for migrants' social integration. Based on this initial positive experience, the author suggests a tripartite model of social dialogue: engaging authorities from origin and destination countries and diaspora organizations. The model provides the possibility to reflect the functioning of the democratic system: diasporas come with proposals, authorities with decisions in support of new opportunities for migrants' social integration. The author uses dialectics to show contradictions between the real situation of migrants and the ideal of participatory democracy.

Keywords: social integration, social dialogue, holistic approach, diaspora.

L'actualité de cette étude est justifiée par de multiples facteurs. Tout d'abord, la migration est un phénomène social complexe, avec des multiples influences sur la vie des communautés humaines dans le pays d'origine et dans le pays de destination. En second lieu, l'Union européenne se confronte à ce moment avec une crise profonde, aggravée par le grand nombre d'immigrants et de réfugiés. En troisième lieu, on sait que dans les moments critiques sont vérifiés les capacités des institutions d'État, des structures supranationales pour répondre adéquatement aux facteurs de déstabilisation, d'honorer ses obligations en matière de responsabilité, les

engagements pris par la signature des accords de collaboration, de coopération et d'association. Quatrièmement, l'intégration de la personne dans la société du pays d'origine, ainsi que dans le pays de destination dépend de la capacité de la personne d'assimiler les principes et les valeurs reconnues et respectés par les communautés. Il faut aussi mentionner que les marginalisés, les exclus de la vie communautaire présentent un réel danger pour le fonctionnement normal des institutions de l'État et pour la stabilité du système politique. Tenant compte de la grande signification et de l'actualité de l'intégration sociale de la personne, des immigrants et des réfugiés, nous appliquerons le potentiel cognitif, l'approche systémique, structurelle et interdisciplinaire des méthodes: la dialectique et la synergetique. Seulement de cette façon, nous sommes en mesure de déchiffrer la complexité des interactions: de la migration, de l'intégration sociale par le savoir et par la communication, de la stabilité et de la prospérité des communautés de deux pays: d'origine et de destination. Voilà quel est l'objectif d'une recherche holistique.

L'objet de la recherche est la société humaine, composée non seulement des personnes qui vivent ensemble en même temps et dans le même espace, mais aussi des relations qui s'établent entre eux. L'approche holistique¹ de la société insiste sur son appréciation dans son ensemble, divisé en plusieurs éléments, tels que: les personnes, les familles, les groupes sociaux, les classés en fonction de divers critères, les relations sociales, politiques, économiques, culturels, religieux. La méthodologie holistique résulte de la primauté de l'ensemble en relation avec les parties, offre une interprétation originale du principe de l'unité et de la connexion mutuelle. La méthode dialectique, les lois et les principes de la dialectique mettent en évidence l'évolution de l'objet de recherche, la dynamique des relations sociales. Une étape importante dans la recherche de la société représente le système des relations sociales: la personne remplit plusieurs rôles: fils / fille; époux / épouse; grand-père / petit-enfant; employé /

¹ Holisme (du grec *holos*- entier) la philosophie de l'intégration. Le concept a été créé en 1929 par Jan Christiaan Smuts à l'occasion de son ouvrage *Holism and Evolution*.

employeur; chef / membre d'une organisation; étudiant / enseignant; acheteur / vendeur; croyant / athée, etc. Pour s'assumer certaines responsabilités découlant du rôle réel, la personne a des relations conçues sur horizontale. Également, l'affirmation de la personne comme sujet des relations sociales réside de ses relations avec l'ensemble, son affirmation au niveau social. La connaissance du propre statut social offre confiance en soi, ouvre constamment des nouvelles opportunités de croissance, de personnalisation. À l'étape initiale du processus d'intégration sociale de la personne, nous mettons la connaissance de soi. Pour déchiffrer l'importance de la connaissance de soi, il est nécessaire de consulter Confucius et Socrate. Dans leurs discours, l'accent est mis sur la connaissance, l'exploitation des résultats qui est impossible sans la connaissance de son propre potentiel cognitif et créatif. Aujourd'hui, ce processus est aussi appelé problématisation.

Dans le discours des anthropologues Valeriu Gubin et Elena Necrasova, on affirme que l'homme est né en tant qu'être biologique non préparé pour l'adaptation aux conditions naturelles d'existence, que le bébé ne survit pas sans aide.² De plus, l'homme est doué de la capacité d'apprendre, de se développer, d'explorer l'environnement naturel et les conditions de l'ambiance sociale, dans lesquels il vit, travaille, s'affirme, assure son propre lieu. La mise en valeur des capacités cognitives d'une personne est un processus complexe, défini par les scientifiques comme socialisation qui se déroule sous la surveillance des parents, des éducateurs, des enseignants et des professeurs. Malheureusement, nous constatons que dans tous les pays de socialisation, on accorde une attention mineure par rapport à son potentiel de formation instructif. À notre avis, la socialisation est la première étape de l'intégration sociale de toute personne, est le facteur déterminant du problématisation. Autrement dit, sans socialisation – l'acquisition des connaissances accumulées par d'autres générations, la personne ne peut pas réaliser son potentiel cognitif, créatif, ne sait pas

² Валерий Губин, Елена Некрасова, *Философская антропология. Учебное пособие для вузов*, М.: ПЕР СЭ: СПб: Университетская книга, 2000.

grand-chose sur elle-même, elle compte sur sa propre expérience, instinct, intuition.³ En raison de l'absence des programmes complexes individualisés, axés sur le potentiel de chaque personne, le nombre d'indécis, des marginalisés, des exclus augmentent dans la société contemporaine. Ce sont les groupes sociaux qui créent des risques et menacent le bon fonctionnement des sociétés démocratiques.

Chaque état contemporain fait face à de multiples difficultés dans le classement des relations des institutions politiques avec la société civile, avec chaque élément de celui-ci; avec les groupes sociaux vulnérables, qui, pour des raisons quelconques s'intègrent plus difficile dans la vie communautaire. L'insuffisance des ressources financières, des personnes professionnelles dans l'éducation compliquent la situation. Mais une communication des autorités avec les groupes marginalisés y est mentionnée, où les dirigeants et les chefs d'institutions politiques, socio-culturelles comprennent l'importance des programmes axés sur l'intégration sociale de chaque personne. Au cours des sept dernières décennies, la situation dans ce domaine s'est aggravée par l'intensification des processus de la migration, car il double la responsabilité des pouvoirs publics à tous les niveaux: local, régional, national, communautaire. Il s'agit de l'élaboration et la mise en œuvre des programmes de politiques publiques, d'éducation, orientées sur l'intégration sociale des citoyens des États de destination qui forment des groupes vulnérables. L'augmentation du nombre d'immigrants exige une réaction adéquate de la part des autorités, qui sont obligées d'élaborer et d'adopter les actes normatifs qui garantissent la protection sociale des migrants.

La migration est un défi constant de l'humanité, ayant impact sur le développement économique et social, sur le système éducatif, sur les échanges culturels, etc. À l'heure actuelle, nous assistons à l'augmentation de l'impact de la migration sur la vie, sur l'activité de la population dans les

³ Ludmila Rosca, Migration, un approche teoretico-practique, forms d'integration sociale et socialization, Jean Monnet Seminar, Migrations, Tunis, Tunisia, 22-23 February 2016, 135-140.

pays d'origine et les pays de destination. Cette thèse se justifie par l'analyse des données statistiques sur la complexité du phénomène ; le volume et les zones couvertes; la diversité et la dynamique des processus de migration; les conséquences de la migration. Selon les rapports, de 2014, 3,8 millions de personnes ont immigré dans un des États membres de l'UE et 2,8 millions d'immigrants ont quitté un État membre de l'UE. Le 1er janvier 2015, le nombre de personnes ayant la nationalité d'un pays tiers et résidant dans un État membre de l'UE a été de 19,8 millions, ce que représente 3,9 % de la population UE-28. De plus, le 1er janvier 2015, 15,3 millions de personnes vivant dans l'un des États membre de l'UE avaient la nationalité d'un autre État membre de l'UE.⁴

La réalité sociale du pays d'origine, influencée par la migration en masse des travailleurs, nous pouvons l'analyser sur la base des données fournies par le Bureau national des statistiques de la République de Moldavie, par les études concernées la «Cartographie de la diaspora moldave dans 4 pays de l'UE: l'Italie, le Portugal, la France et le Royaume-Uni» et la Cartographie de la diaspora moldave dans la Fédération de Russie», financé par l'Organisation internationale pour migration, de l'investigation: la Consolidation des liens entre migration et développement en Moldova, réalisé au sein de la Réseau d'enseignement des spécialistes du domaine de la migration et les délivrances. (MIRPAL)

La République de Moldavie, État démocratique subissant un processus de consolidation des institutions, se confronte des 1993 avec les conséquences sociales de la migration de la population capable de travailler. Dans la recherche d'un emploi, d'une source permanente d'existence les Moldaves ont émigré vers les pays d'Europe occidentale et de l'Est, en Russie et d'autres pays de la CEI. Dans la première décennie d'existence de l'État, l'immigration illégale est un phénomène très répandu, non contrôlé par une institution. Bien que formel fonctionnait le Département des migrations, subordonné au Ministère de travail et de la protection sociale, en réalité, aucun des chefs d'institutions de l'État ne pouvait pas répondre à

⁴ <http://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics->

la question: combien de personnes sont allé travailler à l'étranger légalement et illégalement? Également, augmente le nombre de cas où les citoyens moldaves étant illégal dans les différents États membre supportent diverses formes de discrimination, deviennent des victimes de réseaux internationaux de trafic d'êtres humains, de trafic des migrants, de la prostitution, etc. Le processus de migration de la République de Moldova au cours des 10 dernières années, a subi une forte augmentation, le nombre des migrants a augmenté d'environ 50-60 mille par an.

En Moldavie, la migration a été causée par des facteurs économiques et a émergé comme un mécanisme pour réduire la pauvreté. Une étude récente montre que les facteurs économiques tels que la pauvreté, le chômage et les bas salaires représentent plus de 72 % des facteurs moteurs de la migration.

À partir de 1998 la migration en Moldavie a été caractérisée par un haut niveau d'intensité. Plusieurs études sociologiques visent toutes à la décrire le portrait du migrant moldave. La généralisation des données statistiques nous permet de voir que l'une des caractéristiques de la migration de la Moldavie est l'âge relativement jeune des sujets. L'âge moyen au moment du premier départ à l'étranger était de 29,7 années, passant de 36,1 ans au moment de l'enquête. Il n'existe aucune différence d'âge significative selon les régions ou les pays de destination. La majorité des migrants sont âgés de 18-44 ans. Les hommes prédominent dans l'âge de 18-29 ans, mais les femmes dans l'âge de 45-65 ans. Une caractéristique déterminante de la migration de la population de la Moldavie est le niveau élevé de l'éducation et de l'expérience professionnelle des migrants. Les données montrent que 28% des migrants ont des études universitaires, et 63% - le cycle professionnel / de formation continue. Les migrants de l'UE ont des niveaux d'éducation plus élevés par rapport à ceux de la région de la CEI.

L'exode massif de personnes professionnels formées (ingénieurs, médecins, informaticiens, enseignants, agronomes, etc.) a provoqué une pénurie de main-d'œuvre qualifiée nécessaire pour la Moldavie, en

particulier dans les domaines de l'éducation et de la santé. Certains analystes estiment que cela constituerait un éventuel handicap pour les perspectives de croissance. Ce processus est accompagné simultanément par un certain niveau de «de-compétences»), car, souvent, la migration suppose le développement des travaux non qualifiés par les migrants qualifiés. Dans ce contexte, il a été estimé les conséquences de la migration sur la population de la République.

L'analyse empirique des données sur la migration légale et illégale a conduit la transformation d'une structure inefficace – le Département de Migration dans le Service d'Etat de Migration, structure autonome à côté du Gouvernement de la République de Moldavie. Le Parlement a adopté en 2002 le concept sur la politique migratoire et la loi sur les migrations, qui ont constitués la base juridique pour la création du Département de Migration, structure habilitée à élaborer et à promouvoir une politique unique de l'Etat sur la migration de la population. Toutefois, ont été mises les bases du cadre institutionnel de coopération avec d'autres organes de l'Etat impliqués dans ce domaine: Ministère des Affaires étrangères, Ministère des Affaires Intérieures, Département des gardes-frontières, Département des technologies de l'information.

La signature des accords intergouvernementaux avec les pays où travaillent aujourd'hui la plupart des citoyens moldaves est l'une des priorités actuelles du Département de Migration sur plan externe. Il vise la réglementation de la main – d'oeuvre entre la Moldavie et les États de destination, la fixation des quotas de travail annuels pour les moldaves et, plus important encore, la protection sociale des travailleurs migrants, conformément aux normes et aux règles appliquées aux travailleurs-citoyens de ces États. L'enjeu de ces accords est la création d'alternatives légales de travail pour les candidats de la Moldavie pour travailler à l'étranger.

Parmi la multitude des difficultés avec lesquels se confrontent les migrantes moldaves à l'étranger, la première place occupent les problèmes linguistiques, suivis de celles d'emploi sur le marché du travail, la

légalisation du séjour sur le territoire du pays de destination et l'exploitation par le travail. Les problèmes de l'exploitation par le travail sont plus fréquents en Italie, étant mentionnées par de plus de 1/3 parmi les personnes interrogées, plus particulier pour le système des services de soins à domicile qui est moins réglementé. Il y a des films documentaires qui démontrent les pratiques d'exploitation des femmes, engagées en agriculture en Italie. En France sont très fréquents pour les migrants les difficultés en ce qui concerne l'accès aux services médicaux (1/3 parmi les personnes interrogées). Toujours en France se sont constatées les plus fréquents cas de discrimination des migrants (abus, humiliation, limitation ou interdiction de l'accès aux services publics) par les employeurs (presque 18%).

Dans la résolution des problèmes rencontrés à l'étranger, les migrants exigent, premièrement l'aide des compatriotes dans ce pays, puis font appel aux autres institutions, comme l'église, les organisations de la diaspora, les syndicats et les autres organisations préoccupées par la protection sociale. L'église est constamment préoccupée par la vie et l'activité des Moldaves à l'étranger. Les migrants moldaves fréquentent l'église orthodoxe moldave ou celle roumaine. Le plus souvent, l'église est l'endroit idéal où on rencontre d'autres compatriotes moldaves aux fêtes religieuses, ou on célèbre les événements les plus importants de leur vie: le mariage, le baptême, ce qui les fait se sentir comme chez eux. Les réunions avec les compatriotes ont un rôle important pour la socialisation des migrants pour trouver ou changer l'emploi. Souvent, l'église aide les migrants à trouver un emploi. Elle s'adresse aux institutions officielles avec des demandes en cas d'abus des droits fondamentaux des migrants. On publie des dizaines de témoignages de migrants lorsque l'église aide sous la forme de colis alimentaire, de premier refuge pour les pèlerins, les migrants à un prix symbolique, de 2-3 euros, alors que l'amélioration des conditions de résidence dans le pays de destination a commencé à l'église. En Italie, par exemple, il existe de nombreux organismes de bénévolat dont ont bénéficié les Moldaves. Une expérience positive a Caritas, ou opère des bars

juridiques. Ceux-ci aident à légaliser les actes des immigrés, à trouver un emploi, un logement ou un abri pour la nuit, nourriture, vêtements, ils les aident à rentrer chez eux ou de recevoir sécurité médicale.

La diaspora moldave dans les pays de l'UE et ceux de la CEI est en processus de consolidation, même si on montre numériquement un nombre représentatif d'organisations. Chaque organisation dispose d'un noyau actif, préoccupé par l'élaboration du plan d'activité, l'organisation de rencontres avec les artistes, les musiciens, les écrivains, et même les hommes politiques de la Moldavie. Les difficultés rencontrées par les représentants des organisations de diaspora sont déterminées par l'esprit réduit de participation des Moldaves à diverses activités.

Au sein des organisations, il y a un petit noyau de personnes qui consacre leur temps à travailler pour celles-ci. Cependant, la plupart des associations parviennent à être une source importante d'information pour les migrants moldaves, à promouvoir la République de Moldavie à l'étranger, ses traditions et coutumes, de maintenir les relations avec le service de migration dans les pays de destination, à coopérer avec les différents acteurs sociaux. Étant à l'étranger, 35 % des migrants moldaves s'intéressent régulièrement sur la situation sociale, politique et économique de la République de Moldavie et 49% - de temps en temps, en communiquant fréquemment avec des proches ou les amis restés dans leur pays d'origine.

Les organisations de diaspora au Portugal ont la plus haute fréquence d'accès aux services offerts. La participation des migrants dans l'activité de la diaspora a un impact positif non seulement sur l'individu et l'association, ainsi que sur les relations bilatérales entre les deux pays: d'origine et de destination. La diaspora joue un rôle majeur en ce que concerne l'information des migrants, la collecte d'informations sur la situation socio-économique des migrants légaux et illégaux. La diaspora a plus de possibilités que toutes les institutions de l'État d'origine pour établir le nombre réel de migrants moldaves d'un pays concret, c'est pourquoi le

gouvernement moldave a besoin pour mettre en valeur d'une efficacité maximale le potentiel des organisations de la diaspora.

Les organisations de la diaspora moldave de différents pays ont créé des réseaux sociaux. Les dirigeants des organisations communiquent dans le but de diversifier les formes et les techniques de collaboration avec les institutions de l'état d'origine et de destination, des organisations non-gouvernementales et des associations spécialisées de fournir des consultations, axées sur la protection sociale des migrants. Le potentiel organisateur de la diaspora moldave a été estimé dans la campagne présidentielle de l'automne 2016. Si les élections présidentielles s'étaient tenues sans violations graves des résultats, avec la participation active de la diaspora, ceux-ci auraient été autres, nous aurions choisi un président pro-européen.

Plusieurs études sociologiques ont pour but d'améliorer la gestion de la migration de la force de travail. Lors de l'élaboration de la recherche holistique du processus de migration, nous constatons que la gestion de la migration de la force de travail implique inévitablement le renforcement des organisations de la diaspora, l'augmentation de leur efficacité. Tenant compte de la nécessité et de l'importance de la gestion du processus de migration, en particulier la migration de la force de travail, les autorités gouvernementales moldaves sont obligées de définir les priorités dans ce domaine. À notre avis, on trouve parmi les priorités: la signature des accords de sécurité sociale avec les principaux pays de destination des migrants moldaves; la soutenance des programmes de migration circulaire pour les Moldaves; le développement de certains programmes pour la diaspora moldave de maintenir les relations avec les migrants moldaves, mais de contribuer aussi à maintenir les traditions et coutumes nationales, y compris la promotion de la culture moldave à l'étranger; la création de conditions pour le développement des entreprises, pour le l'élaboration des programmes pour attirer les envois de fonds dans l'économie nationale et le retour des citoyens moldaves. À leur tour, les organisations de la diaspora devraient développer les relations de partenariat, d'intensifier la

coopération avec les autorités publiques locales dans les pays de destination et d'origine, de diversifier les formes de prestation des services.

Maintenant, le pays est quitté par des citoyens qui ont des bons salaires, mais qui sont insatisfaites par l'instabilité socio-économique. «La République de Moldova a déjà perdu un grand potentiel. Plus de 600.000 de citoyens se sont établis définitivement à l'étranger. La migration de travail s'est transformée en migration définitive...» Du point de vue socio-économique, l'effet le plus important est que nous perdons la population jeune, apte de travail, bien préparée.

Une réserve de diminution de l'impact négatif de la migration sur la population de la République de Moldova est constituée par le rapatriement de la population et l'immigration. Le sociologue et le directeur générale de l'Institut de Marketing et des Sondages IMAS-INC Chişinău, Doru Petruţi, pense que la vitesse avec laquelle se réalisent les réformes est inférieure aux attentes de la population. «Il faut regagner de la confiance dans un système qui peut fonctionner dans l'intérêt des citoyens et celui-ci est un processus de durée (...) Les politiciens doivent travailler beaucoup pour que la Moldova devienne de nouveau attractive pour les investitures et pour les hommes. Une fois que tu commences une lutte réelle contre la corruption, tu essaies de ne jamais faire des pas en avant. Si tous ceux pas se font irréversibles, la République de Moldova peut reconquérir sa crédibilité, ne pas seulement devant les acteurs internationaux, mais aussi devant les citoyens propres, dont une grande partie vivent à l'étranger», a commenté l'analyste.

Le rapatriement des émigrants d'haute qualification est l'objet central du projet sur la Diaspora scientifique de la République de Moldova, soutenu financièrement par la Fondation Nationale Suisse pour la Science et l'Agence Suisse pour Développement et Coopération (E.P.F.L.), implémenté par l'Académie de Science de Moldova et E.P.F.L. Le projet – la connexion de diaspora scientifique de République de Moldova au développement scientifique et économique du pays d'origine, a été lancé le 30 avril 2010. Une autre initiative vient de la part de l'Organisation Internationale pour

Migration, la mission en République de Moldova, qui en partenariat avec l'Académie de Science de Moldova a annoncé le 16 septembre 2011 un concours de soutien pour 30 chercheurs – membres de la Diaspora scientifique moldave, qui veulent revenir en Moldova pour une visite de 7-11 jours, pour le but de réaliser des activités de recherche et pour partager l'expérience acquise.

Pour le moment, en République de Moldova sont implémenté deux programmes pour la promotion de la migration internationale en tant que facteur positif dans la promotion du développement, du transfert durable de know-how par l'intégration professionnelle des experts revenus. Le programme le Retour des experts, implémenté par le centre International pour Migration et Développement (CIM) de la part du Ministère Fédéral allemand d'Economie, Coopération et Développement (BMZ), soutient la réintégration professionnelle des diplômés universitaires et des experts avec expérience, originaires des pays en cours de développement, qui ont amélioré leurs capacités et compétences professionnels en Allemagne et sont intéressés de revenir dans leur pays d'origine. En octobre 2010, l'Organisation Internationale pour Migration, la Mission en République de Moldova en partenariat avec le Ministère de la jeunesse et du sport, le Ministère de l'éducation et l'Agence pour l'Emploi ont annoncé le démarrage d'un projet pilote de promotion et de soutien du retour temporaire ou définitive en Moldavie de 30 diplômés des institutions d'enseignement de l'étranger, pour s'engager dans les institutions publics/privés.

L'analyse du processus de l'immigration en République de Moldova, dans les dernières dix années, nous permet de remarquer le fait que cet indice est en croissance. Si en 2001 dans le pays ont immigré 1293 personnes, en 2010-2015, parmi lesquels 140 ont reçu une vise avec résidence permanente.

Conclusions

Ainsi, nous pouvons conclure par dire que l'intégration des moldaves dans la vie sociale du pays de destination est conditionné par plusieurs facteurs: l'établissement de relations optimales avec les institutions sociales, avec les autorités locales, avec les ONG locales; la normalisation des états morale-psychologiques, qui se produit par l'acceptation des toutes les conséquences du statut d'immigrant; l'assurance d'un rythme stable de croissance du bien-être (le salaire qui permet le retour des dettes et le soutien financier de ceux qui se trouvent à la maison), la capacité de la personne d'assimiler le contenu des valeurs, des normes morales et juridiques. Nous pouvons parler de l'intégration des immigrants dans la vie de la nouvelle société seulement dans le cas des immigrants légaux. Il est important pour les citoyens de la République de Moldova qui vont immigrer, de connaître la réalité: les immigrants illégaux peuvent être extorqués de l'argent, ils ne sont pas protégés par la loi, pendant que l'immigrant légal peut s'adresser, selon la nécessité, pour l'aide médicale, il se sent libre dans la rue, dans le magasin, dans les lieux publics.

Un rôle important dans la connaissance du processus d'adaptions et d'intégration des moldaves dans la vie sociale du pays de destination est constitué par la perception de la personne du mode de vie et de l'activité des natifs, l'assimilation des valeurs de la culture matérielle et sociale, l'attitude envers les chefs, envers les natifs. La perception est une qualité du sujet, qui par son individualité se distingue des autres et par sa nature – la sociabilité, s'approche, manifeste l'intérêt pour la structuration d'une relation. Plus les relations des moldaves avec les natifs sont organisées et constants, plus se multiplient les formes d'intégration sociale.

L'approche holistique de la migration sous aspect de l'intégration sociale des immigrants moldaves dans la société du pays de destination nous permet constater que la migration de la main d'œuvre a beaucoup affecté la société moldave. Les données statistiques, systématisées et publiées dans la dernière décennie sont inquiétants, c'est pourquoi les savants préoccupés par la thématique de la migration de République de

Moldova ont élaboré des projets de recherche, ont obtenu dans leur base soutien financier et ont effectué des recherches interdisciplinaires avec le but de décrire le portrait des migrants moldaves de ces trois bagues de migration de la main d'œuvre. De même que le rapport sollicité par la Banque Mondiale, que le projet *La cartographie de la diaspora moldave en Italie, au Portugal, en France et en Grande-Bretagne et dans les pays CSI*, nous offre la possibilité de nous documenter et de connaître la réalité dans le problème des conditions d'intégration des migrants dans la société du pays de destination, du rôle déterminant de connaître la langue parlée, les coutumes, les traditions de la culture et de la civilisation de celui-ci. À cet égard, nous pouvons conseiller l'application de la méthodologie employée par les chercheurs moldaves et dans le cas de l'investigation du processus de la migration des autres pays du bassin méditerranéen.

L'approche philosophique de l'intégration sociale de la personne nous oriente vers la connaissance du potentiel cognitif et créatif de celle-ci, vers la nécessité de développement aux enfants des capacités/habilités de connaissance et de communication. Ces objectifs se réalisent dans le processus de socialisation, personnalisation, dans les résultats desquels la personne se voit comme élément d'un système complexe de relations et influences, attend la connaissance de soi et respectivement se met en question, en déterminant sa position, son statut social et ses sens existentielles.

L'exposition des résultats de la recherche nous a permis de justifier la thèse, en vertu de laquelle l'intégration des moldaves dans la vie sociale du pays de destination est conditionnée par l'établissement des relations optimales avec les institutions sociales, les autorités et les ONG locales; par la normalisation des états moral-psychologiques, qui se produit par l'acceptation des toutes les conséquences du statut d'immigrant; l'assurance du rythme stable d'augmentation du bien-être, de la capacité de la personne d'assimiler le contenu des valeurs, des normes morales et juridiques. Plus les relations des moldaves avec les natifs sont organisées, plus les formes d'intégration sociale de ceux-ci se multiplient. Dans

l'intégration sociale des immigrants, dans le maintien des relations avec le pays natal, dans l'appropriation des responsabilités pour ceux qui sont à la maison et leur avenir, un rôle particulier revient à la diaspora moldave. La recherche nous a permis de constater que même si du point de vue numérique il existe plusieurs organismes de la diaspora moldave, enregistrés dans 35 États, cette structure est en procès de consolidation, d'assimilation du potentiel organisationnel, opérationnel. Dans plusieurs cas l'activité des associations des moldaves se réduit à l'organisation des manifestations culturelles. Tandis que la diaspora pourra faire beaucoup plus pour les immigrants, pour les autorités locales des deux États de destination et natale, qui devrait être préoccupées prioritaires par l'accumulation des données sur les migrants illégaux et sur la protection sociale des migrants légaux. Nous avons noté ci-dessus que l'existence des immigrants illégaux sur le territoire d'un État constitue une menace permanente de la sécurité et de la stabilité sociale de la population ce celui-ci. La collaboration bilatérale entre les autorités des deux pays pourrait être renforcée par l'utilisation du potentiel de la diaspora d'organiser et de communiquer avec les moldaves, qui disent plus simplement la vérité sur leur situation sociale, financier, sur les actes de discrimination vécus à ces égards qu'aux laideurs institutionnelles d'État, aux partis politiques, qui dans les années électorales leur font des visites et leur beaucoup promettent. Dans une telle manière, les accords bilatéraux deviendraient plus réalisables et avec un impact plus consistant sur les conditions de vie et les activités des migrants.

Nous pouvons parler sur l'intégration des immigrants dans la vie de la nouvelle communauté seulement dans le cas des immigrants légaux. Les données statistiques montrent que le nombre des migrants illégaux s'est réduit considérablement dans l'évolution du processus de la migration. Toutefois, nous considérons nécessaire à noter qu'il est important que les citoyens de la République de Moldova qui vont émigrer connaissent la réalité: les immigrants illégaux peuvent se rencontrer avec le chantage, ils ne sont pas protégés par la loi, pendant que l'immigrant légal peut

s'adresser, en cas de nécessité, pour l'aide médicale, il se sent libre dans la rue, dans le magasin, dans les lieux publics.

Pour la société moldave et sa gestion, la recherche a une signification stratégique. Nous proposons à tous: chercheurs, politiques, artistes, écrivains d'unir leurs efforts pour élaborer des projets/programmes, axés sur le rapatriement des migrants. Dans ce sens les données statistiques prometteuses: un nombre réduit des immigrants ont ouvert des affaires propres dans le pays de destination. Si l'immigrant ne dispose pas des propriétés personnelles, il est plus simple à convaincre de revenir à la maison. Les autorités, les chefs d'institutions d'État, des partis politiques parlementaires et extra parlementaires, des organismes non gouvernementaux devront se préoccuper du problème de rapatriement des citoyens de la République de Moldova. Dans les années de crise économique, politique, sociale, étant abandonnés par les autorités publiques, ils ont solutionné leurs problèmes financiers comment ils ont pu, avec les relations personnelles. Maintenant quand nous estimons les conséquences négatives de la migration des jeunes spécialistes du domaine de la médecine, de l'enseignement et des autres secteurs de l'économie nationale, nous considérons nécessaire la multiplication des programmes économiques, sociales, la promotion de facto des réformes en justice, en médecine et en enseignement ne pas dans le but destructeur, mais dans l'avantage de la société et de chaque citoyen de la République de Moldova. Ce thème ne doit pas être idéologisé, politisé. La situation est tellement grave que ceux qui dirigent, qui enseignent, qui comprennent que la Moldova a un avenir doivent s'impliquer, assumant leur responsabilité personnelle.

L'accent mis dans cette recherche sur l'intégration sociale par connaissance et communication nous détermine à prendre conscience que tous les problèmes de la société contemporaine se fortifient à cause de l'absence d'une communication efficace entre les chefs d'États, des communautés humaines, des hommes. La communication politique, socio-culturelle est efficace seulement dans les conditions de l'acceptation de

l'opinion de l'Autre, de l'appréciation du potentiel cognitif, créatif, des capacités et habilités individuelles, des intérêts. Pour améliorer l'efficacité de la communication politique, sociale, il est important de connaître et de respecter ses principes de base: le pluralisme d'opinions, la réciprocité, la tolérance, l'égalité, la transparence, la responsabilité.

Bibliographie:

Cheianu-Andrei, Diana. *Impactul migrației asupra cadrelor didactice și cercetătorilor din Moldova. Principalele concluzii asupra Cartografierii diasporei moldovenești*, 3217_informația_cheianu_migrația profesorilor_și diaspora, accesat 20 martie 2016.

Morcotilo, Iurie, Alexandru Fala. *Aspectul migrațional în securitatea economică a Republicii Moldova: analiză instituțională. Documente de analiză și prognoză economică*. Chișinău, 2014.

Profilul Migrațional Extins al Republicii Moldova 2009-2014. Raport analitic, 2015.

Proiectul *Strategiei Naționale de Dezvoltare a Republicii Moldova 2012-2020 „Moldova 2020”*.

Rosca, Ludmila. Migration, un approche teoretico-practique, forms d'integration sociale et socialization. Jean Monnet Seminar, Migrations, Tunis, Tunisia, 22-23 February 2016.

Губин, Валерий, Елена Некрасова. *Философская антропология. Учебное пособие для вузов*. М.: ПЕР СЭ: СПб: Университетская книга, 2000.

<http://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics->

Copyright©Ludmila ROSCA

Problems of Attracting Venture Capital to the Republic of Moldova and Development of the Infrastructure of Venture Investment in the Conditions of European Integration

Assoc. Prof. Dr. Tatiana ANDREEVA

andreevatatiana72@mail.ru

International Relations Institute of Moldova, Moldova

Abstract. Attraction of venture capital has become a top priority not only for the economies of developed countries, but also for the Republic of Moldova, in particular. Undoubtedly, the process of transition to market relations implies a revision of the main directions in the economic and social development of countries. The priority direction is the gradual transition to high-tech production, the use of the country's innovative potential with the aim of creating a developed infrastructure and competitive products that are in demand on world markets. The article reveals the importance of venture investment for the economy of the Republic of Moldova. The main problems of development of venture infrastructure in the country are described, as well as the main steps of formation and development of venture investment in Moldova.

Keywords: venture capital, venture investment, entrepreneurial activity, innovation, venture infrastructure.

Introduction

At the present stage of the development of the world economy, the most dynamic sector is considered to be the investment market, which is in constant flux and a state of flow of capital from one sphere of activity to another. The dynamic nature of the formation and development of investment gives them the quality of the process of time extension, involves the implementation of the chain metamorphoses: resources (goods, values) - investments (costs - capital gains) - income (effect). In our opinion, all the norms, rules and practical steps to implement the activities of this chain of interactions to the state of integration, that is, along the whole set of investment flows, represent investment activity.

Depending on the number of metamorphoses of investments in the process of their evolution, it is necessary to single out one of the most important areas, which, in our opinion, is very relevant and in demand in modern realities, is venture investment. Attraction of venture capital has become a top priority not only for the economies of developed countries, but also for the Republic of Moldova, in particular. Undoubtedly, the process of transition to market relations implies a revision of the main directions in the economic and social development of countries. The priority direction is the gradual transition to high-tech production, the use of the country's innovative potential with the aim of creating a developed infrastructure and competitive products in demand on world markets. Thus, under the circumstances, attracting investment in innovation and scientific development, which can serve as an effective impetus for economic development, is of particular importance. Undoubtedly, the development of innovative activities provides a variety of tools, among which venture investment can be particularly highlighted.

Main Text

The attraction of venture capital has always been problematic for not only the economically developed countries. This is especially true for countries with developing and transition economies, because venture capital investment is associated with high risk and represents a long-term and highly risky investment of private capital in high-tech promising companies whose activities are focused on the development and production of high technology products with market potential and large advantages, their development and expansion in order to maximize profits. First of all, venture investment is aimed at supporting and developing the real sector of the economy, and is in demand in most medium and small enterprises.

It should be noted that the main problem lies not only in attracting venture capital. The most urgent problem for most modern states is the creation and development of a full-fledged venture infrastructure. To this end, a large number of venture funds are being created, both private and

public, technology parks, various organizations, business incubators, etc., engaged in supporting start-ups.

Among the huge variety of goals and principles of venture capital investment, there are several key ones, namely:

1. Financing of companies, so-called start-ups, whose shares are not quoted on the exchange, but already have RFPs on the market (initial public offer);
2. The investor provides capital in order to maintain a highly efficient business and obtain a share in the authorized capital of the firm;
3. Investors can act as private individuals, as well as large organizations, banks, investment companies and funds, insurance, pension funds, the state, represented by authorized bodies, etc.;
4. Monetary and other funds are provided for a long period of time;
5. Companies that use venture capital, along with cash, gain access to new management methods, efficient resources, necessary business connections, experienced professionals and modern technological developments that promote profit, minimize risks.

Consequently, venture investment undoubtedly contributes to the development of a high-tech industry, allows attracting investments for the implementation of high-yield projects and, as a result, leads to the effective development of the state's economy. Thus, the priority direction in attracting foreign investment into the country's economy is venture business.

In modern realities, the economic development of the state determines the feasibility of conducting venture business. Unfortunately, after the global economic crisis of 2008, there was a decline in entrepreneurial activity both in the world as a whole and in the Republic of Moldova. Thus, by 2014 the number of registered small and medium-sized enterprises in the Republic of Moldova was 52,300, which was 97.4% of the

total number of economic entities in the territory of the Republic.¹ In 2016, the number of new companies decreased by 5,37% compared to 2015 and amounted to 5,673 companies, according to the State Registration Chamber report, and it should be noted that this is the lowest figure in the last decade. The tendency to decrease the number of new enterprises in the Republic of Moldova over the past decade can be traced according to the presented figure. The largest number of registered small and medium-sized enterprises in the Republic of Moldova (11,480) was observed in 2007, i.e. in the pre-crisis period, and, accordingly, it was during this period that the greatest inflow of direct foreign investments into the economy of the country was observed. Already in 2016 the number of enterprises is halved, the same trend is observed in the sphere of attracted foreign investments. This situation confirms the created problem in the economic development of our country, which should be solved by attracting venture capital and developing venture infrastructure, among other things.

Fig.1. Number of new enterprises registered in the Republic of Moldova in 2007-2016.

Source: State Registration Chamber²

¹ Деятельность малых и средних предприятий в Республике Молдова в 2014 году. Электронный ресурс: режим доступа [<http://www.statistica.md/newsview.php?l=ru&idc=168&id=4818>].

² Государственная регистрационная палата - DeepLace.md. Электронный ресурс: режим доступа [<https://deeplace.md/project/ofitsialnyi-sait-registratsionnoi-palaty>].

Thus, despite the relatively large number of existing companies in the Republic of Moldova, there has been a decline in the number of new enterprises, which is primarily due to a lack of investment and other financial instruments. The existing shortage of investment resources, including venture capital, impedes economic growth in the country, the growth of competitiveness, the development and diversification of production processes, the decline in the share of exports and the performance of export operations.

In the world economy, there are various sources of business financing. In the Republic of Moldova, out of all the variety, the most popular are currently the following:

1. Credit - the most common form of financing, is issued by banks and various lending institutions;
2. Commercial or commodity loan, which is carried out in the form of a deferred payment for the goods sold;
3. Leasing - a form of lending through the acquisition of fixed assets by enterprises;
4. Franchising - acts as an indirect source of business financing;
5. Charitable contributions and grants provided by various non-profit organizations for the implementation of entrepreneurial activities and some others.

Of course, venture investment is one of the most popular and common forms of financing in developed countries. The development of venture infrastructure in the Republic of Moldova can have a beneficial effect on innovation activity and increase the competitiveness of the domestic economy, primarily due to the fact that it does not require collateral or any other type of collateral does not provide for intermediate payments to investors and is provided in a short time. Unfortunately, it is worth noting the fact that, to date, there is practically no venture investment in the Republic of Moldova. This is due to a number of objective reasons that have influenced the fact that venture investment has not received its proper development.

First, the current legislation of the Republic of Moldova lacks the necessary regulatory framework that regulates this type of activity.

Second, there are no necessary venture funds that are called upon to find potential venture capital and encourage foreign investors to invest;

Third, the unstable political and socio-economic situation in the country, as well as a general lack of economic incentives for the development of investment activities;

Fourth, there is a shortage of qualified specialists able to manage venture funds;

Fifth, undoubtedly, low liquidity of venture investments;

Sixth, the lack of a transparent mechanism in the allocation of funds;

Seventh, unfortunately, a significantly low level of trust in the owners of innovative ideas prevails;

Eighth, most projects that require additional funding are not sufficiently prepared for this, in particular because of a lack of marketing research or a flaw in the business plan;

Ninth, in the Republic of Moldova, the scientific sphere is not sufficiently funded by the state; therefore, without the state support it is impossible to develop innovative processes;

Tenth, insufficient inflow of direct foreign investments into the economy of the country, and the banking system of the Republic of Moldova, according to the legislation, finances only the operating business; accordingly attracted funds are not allocated to investment projects that are start-ups.

Thus, the identification of existing problems in the field of venture investment indicates that for the effective functioning of the venture infrastructure, it is necessary to jointly participate in the reform process of all institutions, namely:

- State institutions that are able to establish and improve the legal and regulatory framework and create favourable conditions for the development of entrepreneurial activities;

- Educational institutions capable of training highly qualified personnel in the field of innovation;
- Scientific institutions capable of developing and improving scientific and innovative activities in the state.

It should be noted that reforms have already taken place in the Republic of Moldova, contributing to the development of innovative activities. In particular, in 2007 the Law on Scientific and Technological Parks and Innovative Incubators was adopted, with the objective: to stimulate activities in the field of innovation and technology transfer aimed at converting the results of research and innovation into new or improved products, services, processes.³ Based on this law, the “Academica” technopark and the innovative incubator “Inovatorul” were established, which turned out to be the only one of the country's most successful innovation structures. In the period from 2009-2013, the Inogro Science and Technology Park was formed in the Republic of Moldova, as well as innovative incubators at the Academy of Sciences of Moldova and the Polytechnic University of Chisinau. Despite the fact that there are prerequisites for creating incubators in other cities of the republic, innovative structures face a number of financial and personnel difficulties. Undoubtedly, the measures taken are extremely inadequate for the formation of an effective venture infrastructure, much less for attracting venture capital and foreign direct investment to the country's economy and, in particular, to its innovative sector.

Currently, more than 50 projects are being developed in the Republic of Moldova in the most promising areas, and directly in the field of energy saving, agriculture, waste processing and water purification^{4 5}.

³ ЗАКОН № 138 от 21.07.2007 о научно-технологических парках и инновационных инкубаторах. В: Monitorul Oficial Nr. 107-111. 27.07.2007, статья № 476.

⁴ Антирекорды молдавского бизнеса. Электронный ресурс: режим доступа [<https://joblist.md/ru/news/karjera/antirekordy-moldavskogo-biznesa>].

⁵ В Молдове создадут венчурный фонд. Кишинёвский Обозреватель. № 40, 2010. Электронный ресурс: режим доступа [<http://www.aitt.asm.md/node/16?q=news/172>].

Conclusion

It is obvious that the current economic situation in the Republic of Moldova does not allow the state to fully finance existing and potential innovative projects, so the issue of a more effective policy of attracting foreign capital and creating an operating venture infrastructure on the territory of the country becomes topical. Of course, it is necessary to use the experience of developed countries in the current conditions, and on the basis of this, to make appropriate changes. The most important measures in this regard include the following:

1. Creation of a venture financing system, namely, state venture funds operating under the leadership of the Parliament of the Republic of Moldova, whose competence should include partial financing of young innovative companies and minimizing the risks of private investors.

2. Creation of private venture funds.

3. Establishment of the National Agency for Technology and Innovation of the Republic of Moldova⁶, whose responsibilities should include the allocation of budgetary and attracted funds to innovative research, and the allocation of grants and loans for these purposes.

4. Involvement of business angels and venture capitalists to participate in innovative processes, providing for them significant tax benefits.

5. Holding special events, venture fairs, which can stimulate interest of domestic and foreign investors in financing projects.

6. Creation of an effective mechanism for expertise and monitoring of innovative projects and attracting qualified specialists in the field of investment within the framework of innovative incubators, venture funds and technoparks.

7. Implementation of the proposed changes for the development of venture infrastructure in the Republic of Moldova.

⁶ Венчурное финансирование в Молдове с учетом опыта Финляндии. Электронный ресурс: режим доступа [pstademica.md/.../Venchurnoe-finansirovanie-v-Moldove-s-uchetom-opyta-Finlyandii].

Thus, it is necessary to carry out consistent reforms and create effective conditions for the development of promising high-tech slaves. In this regard, we offer a range of the following activities:

1. The search for sources of venture capital and the allocation of funds for research development and initial investment of the emerging idea.

2. Search for potential foreign and domestic investors. At this stage, an important role is played by public venture funds, which, being interested in the project under study must provide the necessary financing.

3. In the process of financing start-ups, it is important to agree on the percentage of equity participation of venture funds in their activities.

4. Seeking additional financing, both within the state and by attracting foreign investors, which means obtaining additional advantages: qualified personnel, technologies, new management methods, quality raw materials, necessary equipment, etc.

5. Stimulation and development of mass production.

Proceeding from the foregoing, it should be noted that with proper use of financial resources, changes in legislation and business principles, venture capital investment will become widespread in the Republic of Moldova, and in the long term it will promote the revitalization of the entrepreneurial environment of the state, which in turn will increase the economic potential countries in the world arena.

Bibliography:

ЗАКОН № 138 от 21.07.2007 о научно-технологических парках и инновационных инкубаторах. В: Monitorul Oficial Nr. 107-111. 27.07.2007, статья № 476.

Попович Г., Букатынский А. Инновационный бизнес: сущность и методы управления. Издательство ARC, Кишинев, 2013. 138 с.

Перчинская Н. Венчурное финансирование в Молдове это реальность или мечты? Электронный ресурс: режим доступа [ava.md/2010/11/15/venchurnoe-finansirovanie-v-moldove-eto/].

Антирекорды молдавского бизнеса. Электронный ресурс: режим доступа [<https://joblist.md/ru/news/karjera/antirekordy-moldavskogo-biznesa>].

Венчурное финансирование в Молдове с учетом опыта Финляндии. Электронный ресурс: режим доступа [pstacademica.md/.../Venchurnoe-finansirovanie-v-Moldove-s-uchetom-opyta-Finlyandii].

В Молдове создадут венчурный фонд. Кишинёвский Обозреватель. № 40, 2010. Электронный ресурс: режим доступа [<http://www.aitt.asm.md/node/16?q=news/172>].

Венчурное финансирование. Электронный ресурс: режим доступа [<http://economics.studio/finansistam/venchurnoe-finansirovanie-51684.html>].

Деятельность малых и средних предприятий в Республике Молдова в 2014 году. Электронный ресурс: режим доступа [<http://www.statistica.md/newsview.php?l=ru&idc=168&id=4818>].

Государственная регистрационная палата - DeepLace.md. Электронный ресурс: режим доступа [<https://deeplace.md/project/ofitsialnyi-sait-registratsionnoi-palaty>].

Copyright©Tatiana ANDREEVA

The Divergences in the Negotiation Process between Turkey and the European Union

Ph.D. Student Emilia Nicoleta SCHIOP

schiopnicoleta@yahoo.com

Babeş-Bolyai University, Romania

Prof. Dr. Mircea BRIE

briedri@hotmail.com

University of Oradea, Romania

Abstract. The purpose of this article is to study the obstacles in the negotiation process between Turkey and the European Union. The objectives of the article are: to present the context of the negotiations between Turkey and the EU, to show the current state of these negotiations, to analyze different elements that hinder the negotiation process, to show the future perspectives and challenges, to evaluate. Before the recent challenges that the European Union is facing, widening this geopolitical structure to the east and south was a priority, but for the moment this goal is postponed. The migration crisis also affects Europe's neighbourhood. Turkey has to face the crisis of migratory populations. At the same time, it has to continue the steps towards integration, which implies a double effort.

Keywords: Turkey, the European Union, accession negotiations, enlargement, progress.

Introduction

The migration crisis also affected Europe's periphery, not just the major centers of power. Turkey has to face the crisis of migratory populations, but it does not have enough instruments like the central European countries. At the same time, it has to continue the steps towards integration, which implies a double effort.

To resolve this problem of the lack of Europeanization, the EU works towards revealing the mandatory requirements related to the accession process, while the candidate country is striving to meet their membership conditions by creating the necessary institutions during the process. About

the methodology, the paper will start with the theoretical part (from special sources). There will be official documents of studying the international elements. The academic sources will show a point of view closed to the objective perception. The information from the mass media show a point of view closed to the subjective perspective.

The subject is relevant, even if the accession negotiations with Turkey are no longer as effervescent as in the past. Turkey is moving away more and more from the European Union and there is no ambiguity that this state will not integrate in the next future. The situation of Turkey is a difficult one. However, the fact that there are approximately three millions of refugees is one of the reasons for what the accession negotiations are not suspended. Also, the Turkish state is an important Economic partner. The relations must be maintained, otherwise, the distance from the EU would be a less desirable option.

The European Union wants that the neighboring states to be partners and to maintain good relations with them for a good functioning. If the official discussions about the potential integration would be suspended, the official relations with the Turkish state would be jeopardized, especially because of the unstable situation in the Turkish country and in the international context.

The Turkish interest for joining the European Union decreased, searching possible alternatives through cooperation with countries such as Russia or China. As a result, the Turkish government is going through a crisis, with visible signs of regression of democracy, doubled by an increased influence of Islam in the leadership.

The general context of the accession negotiations

In 1715, the position of the Ottoman Empire was similar to Russia's from several points of view. It entered the European diplomatic scene at the end of the 15th century. In fact, the entrance of the Turks in the relational system amongst European countries was mainly due to rivalries between

France and the Habsburgs¹. Nevertheless, the Ottoman Empire did not express as a European state and was never part and parcel of the European diplomatic system all through the 18th century. To Napoleon, the European space meant “French Europe” conceived as a space whose borders had to be settled after pressures on the Ottoman Empire². The examples continue nowadays. Beyond all these, the hypothesis of cultural borders impose certain delimitations that we often assume whether we want it or not.

We do not aim at tracing such borders of the European area. We only point out the fact that our debate imposes rather a characterisation on European identity as a spatial notion protected just like a fortress. Is Europe not only politically, but also culturally a space imposing external borders clearly settled from a territorial point of view? Pursuing the evolution in time of the process of European construction, we can conclude by answering this question as follows: in the European Union, external borders are more and more important (more closed!), while the internal ones become more formal than real (more open!). Europe seen as a “fortress” is thus more open, more “hospitable” from the perspective of its members, and more closed, secure and less permissive for the rest of the world. In such a construction, we can identify not only the advantages of the high level of democracy and welfare the Community citizens may enjoy, but also the exclusivism imposed to others by closing the border. After removing internal barriers, Europe starts to become a super-state reinventing the “hard” border protecting states and politically associated people, excluding others that have not benefitted from such political decisions³. In this context, do external borders of the community become expressions of national state border? It is a difficult matter entailing debates not only on the character and typology of the border, but also on aspects introduced by

¹ Matthew Anderson, *L'Europe au XVIII^e siècle 1713-1783*, Paris, 1968, 157.

² Gerard Delanty, *Border in Changing Europe: Dynamics of Openness and Closure*, in *EuroTimes*, vol. 1, *Europe and Its Borders: Historical Perspective* (hereinafter *EuroTimes*, vol. 1), ed. Ioan Horga, Sorin Şipoş, Oradea, Institute for Euroregional Studies, 2006, 46.

³ Mircea Brie, *European Culture between Diversity and Unity*, in *Analele Universităţii din Oradea, Seria Relaţii Internaţionale şi Studii Europene*, 2010, 79-92.

the fact that the Union does not have a border from within which the exterior may be seen. There are several territories that, from a geographical point of view, are comprised “within” the community while not being part of the European Union. Thus the attempt to trace community border to (physically!) separate the “Europeans” from the “non-Europeans” becomes impossible from a cultural point of view⁴. Though recent, the historical heritage after the cold war imposes not only borders; they also impose actual barriers that cannot be crossed from the point of view of political decisions. Borders remain closed, irrespective of cultural heritage. On the other hand, the process of outlining external borders cannot be finished. Starting from such a remark, people and states that will belong to the “interior” are currently outside the borders. Thus the hard border whose construction is more and more obvious excludes the Europeans, not only the non-Europeans. Consequently, the European border is open or close depending on the exclusivist political interests and less from a possible cultural perspective. Hence, political discourses bringing motivations relating to the European cultural heritage concerning European integration of certain states such as Turkey are more populist actions. It is a political decision of an exclusivist club. “Europe is and should remain *a house with many rooms*, rather than a culturally and racially exclusive club”⁵. Thus, the European Community becomes a close territory on political grounds based on identity motivations⁶.

Under the influence of the European neighbourhood policy, the concept of external border of the European Union tends to acquire new means of expression. On the one hand, we see a flexibility of contacts between the two sides of the border. Such a trend is enhanced by the

⁴ Mircea Brie, Ioan Horga, *The European Union External Border. An Epistemological Approach*, in *Revista Română de Geografie Politică*, 2009, 15-31.

⁵ Robert Bideleux, *The Limits of Europe, Eurolimes*, vol. I, 62.

⁶ Mircea Brie, *Europe from Exclusive Borders to Inclusive Frontiers: Case Study Romanian - Ukrainian Frontier*, in Ioan Horga, Istvan Suli-Zakar (coord.), *Cross-Border Partnersip with Spacial Regard to the Hungarian-Romanian-Ukrainian Tripartite Border*, Oradea-Debrecen, 2010, 23-36.

means of cross-border cooperation through Euroregions and European instruments successfully implemented at the external border⁷. On the other hand, the remarkable actions of the European Union through which they attempt to implement policies for regional cohesion at the current borders is, according to some analysts, the proof that the European Union is consolidating the current external borders, thus considering, at least for the moment, the option of slowing down the enlargement to the east without effectively closing the gates to this enlargement⁸. Irrespective of the reasons for the European neighbourhood policy, we can see that there is a change of attitude on external border due to its implementation. In such a situation, regions and people outside community structures can benefit from programmes and instruments of a policy bringing them closer to community citizens. Through its programmes for territorial cooperation at the external border, the neighbourhood policy significantly contributes to developing a more homogenous system⁹ and the “integrated regional development”¹⁰. These policies are also required by the need to promote harmonisation of economic policies to contribute to achieving economic cohesion on a regional level. The attenuation of important commercial unbalance between EU and its neighbours by enlarging the common market beyond the external borders of the community is thus an imperative responding to the European policy for good neighbourhood¹¹. We can conclude to pointing out that the implementation of the European

⁷ Mircea Brie, *European Culture between Diversity and Unity*, in *Analele Universității din Oradea, Seria Relații Internaționale și Studii Europene*, 2010, 79-92.

⁸ Connecting the “orange revolution” in Ukraine, the European Commissioner for external relations and European neighbourhood policy, Benita Ferrero-Waldner, stated on the 1st of December 2004 that „*la question de l’Ukraine dans l’UE n’est pas à l’ordre du jour. Mais il est clair que nous ne fermons aucune porte*”. See Régis Matuszewicz, *Vers la fin de l’Élargissement?*, in Laurent Beurdeley, Renaud de La Brosse, Fabienne Maron (coord.), *L’Union Européenne et ses espaces de proximité. Entre stratégie inclusive et partenariats removes: quell avenir pour le nouveau voisinage de l’Union?*, Bruxelles, Bruylant, 2007, 109.

⁹ Annabelle Hubeny-Berlisky, *Le financement d’ela PEV- la réponse proposée (1)*, in Laurent Beurdeley, Renaud de La Brosse, Fabienne Maron (coord.), *op. cit.*, 317.

¹⁰ *Ibidem*, 320.

¹¹ Régis Matuszewicz, *op. cit.*, 110.

neighbourhood policy leads to altering the perception of external border; moreover, the implementation of European instruments for cross-border cooperation tends to move current border to the outside by building a new symbolic one including a peripheral privileged area having the advantages of neighbourhood. Nevertheless, this policy has limits. For example, in spite of the “opening”, we feel in the discourse of European officials referring to a possible enlargement of the European Union by Turkey’s accession, that it would lead to some issues in managing the European neighbourhood policy – some of the new partners might be Syria, Iraq and Iran. At the time, the EU is not ready to face such challenges¹².

The borders of Central and Eastern Europe (CEE) today are the result of a complex process conducted decades after the fall of communist regimes in this part of Europe. During the Cold War, Europe was divided into two by the two military blocs (NATO and the Warsaw Pact). On the line between the two military blocs emerged a *hard* border, *closed*, called the Iron Curtain. Subsequently, the European Union and NATO expansion eastward, through the integration of most of the former communist states of Europe, led to the disappearance of the *barrier* that had separated Europeans from Europeans¹³.

¹² Ioan Horga, Mircea Brie, *Europe between Exclusive Borders and Inclusive Frontiers*, in *Studia Universitatis Babeş-Bolyai, Series Europaea, Cluj-Napoca*, 2010, 63-86.

¹³ Mircea Brie, *European enlargement and new frontiers Central and Eastern Europe*, in *Studia Universitatis Babeş-Bolyai, Series Europaea, Cluj-Napoca*, LIX, 1, 2014, 113-130.

Map 1. The Iron Curtain (NATO vs. Warsaw Pact Nations)

Source: Personal adaptation after

<http://mrparana.weebly.com/section-114.html>, viewed on 31.05.18

Begun with the unification of Germany, this process of European enlargement to the East has proved to be particularly important for shaping a new reality in the form and role of borders in Central and Eastern Europe area. CEE states integrated into Euro-Atlantic structures that include three former Soviet republics (the Baltic States), and now have embraced this integrating idea following the only logical existing alternative of security (NATO) and the impulse of prosperity offered by the European Union. This need for very strong security in this part of the world was born from a psychosis, real or less real in the years after the fall of communism, of the continuous “siege” of Russia. In fact, this need for security has proven to be much stronger than other needs of states and of the population also because these countries first sought integration into NATO security¹⁴.

¹⁴ *Ibidem*.

Map 2. NATO members and partners (2018)

Source: Personal adaptation after
[http://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/
 File:NATO_affiliations_in_Europe.svg](http://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:NATO_affiliations_in_Europe.svg), viewed on 31.05.18

NATO expansion eastward led to the shaping of a new security border significantly expanded eastward compared to the former Iron Curtain that demarcated the area of influence of NATO vs. the Warsaw Pact. Today in CEE, with few exceptions, the NATO space overlaps exactly over the EU space. Moreover, we cannot but note that from the Baltic Sea to the Black Sea the external borders of the two organizations overlap exactly. These, associated to the last events of the year 2013 after the EU summit in Vilnius during which Ukraine refused the Association Agreement with the EU, allow us to distinguish a more or less clear east-west European divide

line that coincides largely with the new external border of the EU and NATO¹⁵.

Map 3. European Union (2018)

Source: BBC, <http://www.bbc.co.uk/news/world-middle-east-24367705>, viewed on 30.05.18

The status of Turkey is the one of the a candidate state (in 1987 it applied to join the European Economic Community and in 1997 it was declared eligible to join the EU); the involvement for the European integration dates back to 1959 and includes the Association Agreement in Ankara (1963) for the gradual establishment of a customs union (finally finished in 1995).

¹⁵ *Ibidem.*

The accession negotiations began in 2005. But only after Turkey will agree to apply the additional protocol of the Association Agreement Ankara - Cyprus, eight negotiation chapters will be opened and there will be unblocked those chapters which were provisionally closed.¹⁶

“The membership in the European Union do not usually come to the brink of a military coup.” In normal circumstances, one factor that may appease the secularist paranoia in Turkey would be the European leanings of the AKP, which has done much more than any other Turkish government for improving Turkey's chances of joining the EU. Lately, Turkey's European way has looked increasingly problematic (full-membership negotiations between Ankara and Brussels started in December 2005, but have been partially suspended because of the unresolved Cyprus issue and pessimism prevails in both Turkey and Europe). The EU was suffering from the enlargement fatigue and partly as a result, according to polls, only 40 % of Turks were enthusiastic about accession, down from 75 percent in 2005.¹⁷ After years, the percentage of Turks for the accession decreased.

Although there is a part of Turks that still want to see their country become a proud member of the EU, an even larger majority believe the European Union will never fully embrace Turkey, mainly because of its Muslim identity. Because the Turkish public grows frustrated with the European leaders, it also does with its own: the AKP'S Muslim constituency was shocked by the European Court of Human Rights in 2005 by the decision to uphold a ban on Islamic headscarves in Turkish universities, on the grounds that it was necessary to preserve the secular character of the educational institutions at that time. They had supported the European process in the hope that, as the AKP promised, it would promote religious freedom in Turkey. Furthermore, the failure of the AKP'S Cyprus policy for ending the economic and political isolation of the Turkish Republic of

¹⁶ European Commission, *Turkey*, 2016, https://ec.europa.eu/neighbourhood-enlargement/countries/detailed-country-information/turkey_en, accessed on 15.04.2018.

¹⁷ Omer Taspinar, “The old Turks’ revolt: when radical secularism endangers democracy”, *Foreign Affairs*, no. 86, 2007, 114-126.

Northern Cyprus (recognized only by Turkey) has left the party open to the charge that it has sold out Turkish interests to please the European Commission.

Turkey's quest for the membership remained on track; having suffered the most from the illiberal tendencies of its political system, the former Islamists continued to see Brussels as their best hope for moving the country toward democracy and economic prosperity. But there were still limits to what the AKP'S pro-EU stance was sending mixed signals.¹⁸

Beside the partnership, there is important to take into consideration the EU – Turkey Customs union.

The Customs Union with Turkey of 1995 was a major instrument of integration into the internal and global markets, offering powerful tools to reform the Turkish economy. It put Turkey into a liberal foreign trade regime for industrial goods and holds a promise of its participation in the internal market for industrial products. As a result, Turkish producers of industrial goods have become exposed to competition from imports and they operated in one of the largest free trade areas for industrial products in the world. They are protected by tariffs from external competition to exactly the same extent as other producers from the internal market. In return, the Turkish industrial producers have duty-free market access to the European Economic Area, an important element for both sides.

Fulfilling the requirements of the Customs union has been challenging – Turkey has introduced major reforms. But it has faced difficulties in fulfilling the requirements of it in particular when it tried to adopt and implement the EU's competition policy provisions on state aid and insuring adequate and effective protection of intellectual property rights. In those cases, the process for the requirements took a lot of time.

One lesson that one can derive from the Turkish experience is that trade liberalisation achieved through a preferential trade agreement successfully moved the economy from a government-controlled regime to a market-based one and another issue was related to the existence of political

¹⁸ *Ibidem*, 127.

will on the side of policy-makers to reform the economy. In Turkey there was political will to achieve the goal of EU economic integration on the path to becoming a full member of the European Union. As a result, adopted all of the preferential agreements the EU has concluded with third countries and it has also accepted the European Union's custom provisions, the harmonisation approach, the competition policy, the European intellectual property rights *acquis* and the European commercial policy regulations.

Although the administrative costs for the implementation of the requirements of the Customs Union have been quite substantial, it has incurred these costs with the hope of becoming a full member of the European Union. However, other countries may not have the prospect of the membership, but those countries may still be interested in integrating in order to achieve a relatively high, but sustainable economic growth measured by growth in real per capita income.¹⁹

The stages of negotiations

From the principles that govern the negotiations, it can be shown:

The negotiations are based on Turkey's own merits and the pace will depend on Turkey's progress for the requirements for membership. The presidency or the Commission has to keep the Council fully informed, so that the Council can keep the situation under regular review (the Union side can decide in due course whether the conditions for the conclusion of negotiations have been met; this will be done on the basis of a report from the Commission confirming the fulfilment by Turkey of the requirements).

As it was agreed at the European Council in December 2004, these negotiations are based on the article 49 of the Treaty on European Union and the shared objective of the negotiations is accession. These negotiations are an open-ended process, the outcome of which cannot be guaranteed beforehand and while having full regard to all Copenhagen criteria, including the absorption capacity of the Union, if the Turkish state is

¹⁹ Subidey Togan, *The EU – Turkey Customs union: a model for future euro-med integration*, Brussels: Medpro, 2012, 23-24.

not in a position for assuming in full all the obligations of membership it must be ensured Turkey is fully anchored in the European structures through the strongest possible bond.

The enlargement should strengthen the process of continuous creation and integration in which the Union and its member states are engaged, so that every effort should be made to protect the cohesion and effectiveness of the EU. According to the conclusions of the Copenhagen European Council from 1993, the Union's capacity to absorb Turkey, while maintaining the momentum of European integration is an important consideration in the general interest for both. The Commission shall monitor this capacity during the negotiations, with the whole range of issues set out in the paper from October 2004.

Negotiations are opened on the basis that Turkey sufficiently meets the political criteria created by the Copenhagen European Council in 1993, for the most part of the Treaty on European Union and proclaimed in the Charter of fundamental rights, so that the Union expects Turkey to sustain the process of reform and to work towards further improvement of the principles of liberty, democracy, the rule of law and respect for human rights and fundamental freedoms, also including relevant European case law and it should consolidate and broaden legislation and implementation measures specifically in relation to the zero tolerance policy in the fight against torture and ill-treatment and the implementation of provisions for freedom of expression, freedom of religion, women's rights, trade union rights and minority rights. The European Union and Turkey must continue their intensive political dialogue to ensure the irreversibility of progress in the areas.

In the case of a serious and persistent breach in the Turkish country of the principles of liberty, democracy, respect for human rights and fundamental freedoms and the rule of law on which the Europe is founded, the Commission will, on its own initiative or on the request of one third of the Member states, recommend the suspension of negotiations and propose the conditions for eventual resumption.

The advancement of the negotiations will be guided by the country's progress in preparing for accession.²⁰

The enlargement represents one of the most important policies of the EU, enabling it to cope better with global challenges and pursue its strategic interests; the Council of the European Union decides the opening of accession negotiation and verifies the most important policies for every acceding country.²¹

The enlargement belongs to the main "constitutional policies", according to Lowi. It affects the institutional structure of the EU and it could trigger modifications of the norms which apply the policy and the the policy-making process. Also, the enlargement has aspects of redistribution policy, especially in the field of it which benefit from more funds from the European budget.²²

The enlargement policy of the Union, being a structured policy, made possible close relations with the states that are not members, but enjoy the idea of joining in future.²³ With the diversified instruments (political, financial, technical) the enlargement policy made possible the transformation of the countries from the South-Eastern Europe with the union of Europe and the enlargement of the single market.

New members expands the single European market and increases the efficiency of the common policies.

As a rule, the enlargement policy consists of two sets of conditions. The first set includes general conditions that a state must fulfill in order to integrate. The second is the decisions that specify the concrete ways of joining. The modalities of accession are left to the accession negotiations.²⁴

²⁰ The European Commission, *Negotiating framework*, 2005, http://trade.ec.europa.eu/doclib/docs/2007/september/tradoc_135916.pdf, accessed on 28.05.2018.

²¹ Vasile Pușcaș, *EU accession negotiations*, Viena: Hulla & Co Human Dynamics KG, 2013, 32.

²² Helen Wallace, Mark A. Pollak, Alasdair R.Young, *Elaborarea politicilor în Uniunea Europeană*, Bucharest: Institutul European din România, 2011, 340.

²³ Comisia Europeană, *Procesul de extindere a Uniunii Europene*, 2011, http://ec.europa.eu/romania/news/articole_si_dialoguri/070411_extindere_ro.htm, accessed on 17.06.2018.

²⁴ Wallace, Pollak, Young, *op. cit.*, 339-341.

In 2018, for the first time together with the enlargement package, the Commission also published the annual assessments of the economic reform programmes for the Western Balkans and Turkey (the annual assessments of the programmes show the continued economic growth and efforts for strengthening the macroeconomic and fiscal stability in the light of current vulnerabilities. Sound policies have to be maintained and strengthened. The reforms speeded up to reduce the persisting macroeconomic risks and there are important sources for sustainable long-term growth and speed up convergence with the EU.²⁵

The divergent elements that hinder the negotiation process

The main opposition in the EU comes precisely from the great powers that do not want Turkey to be very influential as a result of potential integration, because with a large population, it should automatically be in the European Parliament governed by a number of direct politicians in proportion to the population, so, as a result, Turkey would surpass even Germany, from a numerical and a decisional point of view. The great powers would not accept that a country with a Muslim majority to be the main decision maker in the European Union.²⁶

A cause of delay in judicial progress may have its roots in the Armenian genocide: its damaging consequences were broader and more durable than expected for what was to be qualified as the first genocide of the 20th century. The mention of the genocide in connection with the events from 1915-1918 in the Ottoman Empire reveals primarily physical annihilation and the second aspect in those years was the denial of the genocide. As a result of the policy of destroying the Armenian population in Asia Minor, a new diaspora, composed of those who survived the massacres and deportations, emerged. If the armenocide did not completely

²⁵ The European Commission, *Enlargement package: Commission publishes reports on the Western Balkans partners and Turkey*, 2018, http://europa.eu/rapid/press-release_IP-18-3342_en.htm, accessed on 28.05.2018.

²⁶ Emilia Nicoleta Schiop, „Turcia între Uniunea Europeană și Uniunea Euroasiatică”, *Tabor*, no. 6, 2017, pp. 87.

exterminate an ethnic group, it was complemented by a white genocide by assimilating the Armenian diasporans into the foreign nations that host them and the genocide, as a whole, as ethnocide continued in the decades after consuming those events.²⁷

Erdogan supported the need to change the constitution of Turkey in 2017, an essential act, in order to turn the country into a real regional power and not only under its leadership. The challenges for Ankara are numerous, both externally and internally, in a context where the supporters of the president believe that by the changed constitution, the state will be more stable, but its challengers talk about building an authoritarian system and according to parliamentary debates, the move from a parliamentary political system to a presidential one gave full powers to the president elected by popular vote.

The president is able to hold up two mandates and to appoint directly not only his deputies, but also the members of the government, members whom he can dismiss at any time without the consent of the parliament. He has the right to be a political partisan, and to directly intervene in court by promulgating decrees.

The opinion of the Turks was requested in April 2017, when they were called to the polls. The difference between this referendum and others from other countries is the fact that Erdogan would not hold a referendum to lose, especially when the name is the synonym of power.

New Turkey is being built in a state of emergency, but its supporters thinks that this does not affect democratic values by offering the example of France, a state that, like Turkey, was in a alert to terrorist attacks, but will held presidential elections in April 2017 and the difference is that tens of thousands of people have not been arrested in France and censored to the mass media amid a state of emergency.²⁸

²⁷ Sergiu Selian, „Genocidul armean”, *Revista Siamanto*, nr. 1, 2013.

²⁸ Răzvan Munteanu, „ Noua Turcie: O construcție sub stare de urgență”, *Adevărul*, 2017, http://adevarul.ro/international/in-lume/turcia-grecianoii-tensiuni-marea-eggee-1_5897e3e35ab6550cb82ce1bb/index.html, accessed on 19.02.2018.

The perspectives and future challenges

It was supposed that Erdogan's support came from the United States, the Americans trying to reapply the Turks to maintain the regional status quo and to limit the Russian influence in Syria. It was difficult for the president Trump to resolve shortly the two major demands of Erdogan: the extradition of cleric Fetullah Gulen and the withdrawal of military support to Kurds in Syria. It could have put pressure on the Hizmet movement in the United States, but Gulen's extradition is not a political act, a court decision is needed and the process can even last longer than Trump's current mandate.

Instead, most likely the White house will close its eyes to future democratic skirmishes, consolidating in Turkey an authoritarian-competitive regime. It is paradoxical that a country that was regarded as a political model for the Middle East states to developing a political system like Syria. As a result of the political events in Ankara, there has been a greater rapprochement with Islam, losing the elements of secularization that have been sustained since the last century by Mustafa Kemal Atatürk.

Another problem is the endangering of relations between Turkey and Greece, which aggravates the problems within the state.

At the beginning of February 2017, they were on the brink of a naval confrontation around the Greek islands of Imia. It all happened after a rocket launcher and two other Turkish navy forces entered the Greek territorial waters, sailing around the small islands located five kilometres from Bodrum, Turkey. Soon, the Greek navy sent his forces to the east of the Aegean Sea, forcing the Turks to leave Greece after only seven minutes, followed by a tough dialogue between Athens and Ankara.

Erdogan, as a result of reproaches from the EU for failing to comply with principles has increasingly shown interest in joining other structures,

such as the Eurasian economic union. Russia has shown its approval for such a feasible move by the Turkish state.²⁹

Conclusions

Turkey has had a good start in the accession negotiations with the European Union. It begins to go a good way through a relative separation of a state religion by gradually bringing the *acquis communautaire* closer, by changing the mentality of the Turks in the sense of approaching Europe or by ever more interdependent trade between the Turks and the West. Unfortunately, crises put Turkey in a difficult situation and in recent years there has been a regression in terms of democracy in that state, increasingly feeling the influence of the Islamic religion in leadership.

Erdogan's reaction to the demands of the European Union has been farther away from Europe, manifesting his dissatisfaction by trying to approach similar structures, such as the Eurasian economic union. However, it is still not possible to specify exactly which route to choose Turkey...

It remains to follow international reactions that can influence the situation in one way or another.

Bibliography:

Anderson, Matthew. *L'Europe au XVIII^e siècle 1713-1783*, Paris, 1968.

Bideleux, Robert. *The Limits of Europe*, in *Eurolimes*, vol. I, 2006.

Brie, Mircea, Ioan Horga, *The European Union External Border. An Epistemological Approach*, *Revista Română de Geografie Politică*, 2009, 15-31.

Brie, Mircea. *Europe from Exclusive Borders to Inclusive Frontiers: Case Study Romanian - Ukrainian Frontier*, in Ioan Horga, Istvan Suli-Zakar (coord.), *Cross-Border Partnersip with Spacial Regard to the Hungarian-Romanian-Ukrainian Tripartite Border*, Oradea-Debrecen, 2010, 23-36.

²⁹ Idem, „Turcia și Grecia: Noi tensiuni în Marea Egee”, *Adevărul*, 2017, http://adevarul.ro/international/in-lume/turcia-grecianoi-tensiuni-marea-egee-1_5897e3e35ab6550cb82ce1bb/index.html, accessed on 19.02.2018.

Brie, Mircea. *European Culture between Diversity and Unity*, in *Analele Universității din Oradea, Seria Relații Internaționale și Studii Europene*, 2010, 79-92.

Brie, Mircea. *European enlargement and new frontiers Central and Eastern Europe*, in *Studia Universitatis Babeș-Bolyai, Series Europaea*, Cluj-Napoca, LIX, 1, 2014, 113-130.

Comisia Europeană. *Procesul de extindere a Uniunii Europene*, 2011. http://ec.europa.eu/romania/news/articole_si_dialoguri/070411_extindere_ro.htm, accessed on 17.06.2018.

Delanty, Gerard. *Border in Changing Europe: Dynamics of Openness and Closure*, in *Eurolimes*, vol. I, *Europe and Its Borders: Historical Perspective* (hereinafter *Eurolimes*, vol. 1), ed. Ioan Horga, Sorin Șipoș, Oradea, Institute for Euroregional Studies, 2006, 46.

European Commission. *Negotiating framework*, 2005. http://trade.ec.europa.eu/doclib/docs/2007/september/tradoc_135916.pdf, accessed on 28.05.2018.

European Commission. Turkey, 2016. https://ec.europa.eu/neighbourhood-enlargement/countries/detailed-country-information/turkey_en, accessed on 15.04.2018.

European Commission. *Enlargement package: Commission publishes reports on the Western Balkans partners and Turkey*, 2018. http://europa.eu/rapid/press-release_IP-18-3342_en.htm, accessed on 28.05.2018.

Horga, Ioan, Mircea Brie. *Europe between Exclusive Borders and Inclusive Frontiers*, in *Studia Universitatis Babeș-Bolyai, Series Europaea*, Cluj-Napoca, 2010, 63-86.

Hubeny-Berlsky, Annabelle. *Le financement d'ela PEV- la réponse proposée (1)*, in Laurent Beurdeley, Renaud de La Brosse, Fabienne Maron (coord.), *L'Union Européenne et ses espaces de proximité. Entre stratégie inclusive et partenariats removes: quell avenir pour le nouveau voisinage de l'Union?*, Bruxelles, Bruylant, 2007.

Matuszewicz, Régis. *Vers la fin de l'Élargissement?*, in Laurent Beurdeley, Renaud de La Brosse, Fabienne Maron (coord.), *L'Union Européenne et ses*

espaces de proximité. Entre stratégie inclusive et partenariats removes: quell avenir pour le nouveau voisinage de l'Union?, Bruxelles, Bruylant, 2007.

Munteanu, Răzvan. „Noua Turcie: O construcție sub stare de urgență”. *Adevărul*, 2017. http://adevarul.ro/international/in-lume/noua-turcie-constructie-starea-urgenta-1_588217815ab6550cb89ef4ea/index.html, accessed on 19.02.2018.

Munteanu, Răzvan, „Turcia și Grecia: Noi tensiuni în Marea Egee”. *Adevărul*, 2017. http://adevarul.ro/international/in-lume/turcia-grecianoi-tensiuni-marea-eggee-1_5897e3e35ab6550cb82ce1bb/index.html, accessed on 19.02.2018.

Pușcaș, Vasile. EU accession negotiations. Viena: Hulla & Co Human Dynamics, 2013.

Schiop, Emilia Nicoleta. „Turcia între Uniunea Europeană și Uniunea Euroasiatică”. *Tabor*, no 6, 2017, 84-89.

Selian, Sergiu. Genocidul armean” *Revista Siamanto*, nr. 1, 2013.

Taspinar, Omer. “The old Turks’ revolt: when radical secularism endangers democracy”. *Foreign Affairs*, no. 6, 2007, 114-130.

Togan, Subidey. *The EU – Turkey Customs union: a model for future euro-med integration*, Brussels: Medpro, 2012.

Wallace, Helen; Pollak, Mark A.; Young, Alasdair R. *Elaborarea politicilor în Uniunea Europeană*, Bucharest: Institutul European din România, 2011.

Copyright©Emilia Nicoleta SCHIOP

Copyright©Mircea BRIE

The Level of Competition in Public Procurement in the Republic of Moldova in the Light of International Commitments

Assoc. Prof. Dr. Dorina HARCENCO

dorinaharcenco@yahoo.com

Academy of Economic Studies of Moldova, Moldova

Abstract. Public procurement is an important sector of the economy that accounts a significant share of GDP both in developed and developing countries. The efficiency in PP by enforcing the main principles such as transparency, competition, non-discrimination, integrity, fairness, openness and accountability contributes to achievement of better value for money. In many developing countries the public procurement system requires substantive reform and is characterized by lack of efficiency. Republic of Moldova is currently in the process of reform of PP and in the article will be considered the evolution of the level of competition in PP in paper based and electronic procedures from the perspective of introduction of the eProcurement system and in the light of Moldova's international commitments: WTO GPA implementation and harmonization with EU Directives on PP from 2014.

Keywords: public procurement, competition, WTO, GPA, EU-RM Association Agreement, bid.

Public procurement plays a key role as a tool to promote good governance: procurement procedures can ensure the efficient management of public finances, guarantee enhanced transparency and promote fair competition among business entities.

Public and private entities often rely upon a competitive bidding process to achieve better value for money in their procurement activities. Low prices and/or better products are desirable because they result in resources either being saved or freed up for use on other purposes.

For many developing countries government procurement reform is a key issue, high on the good governance agenda. In addition, the recent revision of the WTO's Agreement on Government Procurement (GPA) that

came into force in 2014 has once again brought questions around transparency, discrimination, and the goals of procurement reform to the fore.

Public procurement generally accounts for a large share of public expenditure in a domestic economy. The European Union registered the average share of public procurement in the GDP of 16% in 2016 and 14% in 2017.¹ The Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (35 member countries) accounts on average 12% PP share in GDP in 2015. Low-income countries have the share of public procurement in GDP of around 14.5%, followed by upper-middle income countries, at 13.6%, high income with 12,6%.²

The public procurement market in Moldova, in 2012 represented 6,69% of Moldovan GDP (according to the public procurement agency statistics). In 2013 it represented 7,49%; in 2014 – 9,67%; and in 2015 it dropped to 5,68% due to economic recession, reflecting the negative shocks from external demand, remittances and financing. Nevertheless, PPA does not have competences in several categories of public procurement contracts like small value contracts and therefore, they are not fully quantified. In 2016 the total value of contracts in PP was 7.5 billion Lei, which constituted around 5.6% of GDP, thus the same share as in 2015.

The development of an efficient and trustful public procurement (PP) system represents one of the fundamental elements of the process of development of a state and this is an urgent need in case of Republic of Moldova. The intensification of the efforts of the elaboration of a harmonized legislation with the World Trade Organization Government Procurement Agreement and the public procurement policies of the European Union and the insurance of corresponding enforcement of the legal provisions in practice will contribute to the increase of efficiency of the PP system and will reduce the waist, fraud and corruption, thus contributing

¹ https://ec.europa.eu/growth/single-market/public-procurement_en

² <http://www.oecd.org/gov/public-procurement/>

to the consolidation of trust of citizens and business in the public procurement system.

Republic of Moldova has two major international commitments in the sphere of PP: World Trade Organization Government Procurement Agreement (WTO GPA), which entered into force for Moldova on 14 July 2016, and the European Union Association Agreement (AA) that provides a comprehensive roadmap to European integration for Moldova. The Association Agreement between the European Union and the European Atomic Energy Community and their Member States, on the one part, and the Republic of Moldova, on the other part was signed on June 27, 2014 in Brussels, Belgium. The Agreement was ratified by the Parliament of the Republic of Moldova on July 2nd, 2014 and by the European Parliament on November 13, 2014, and has been in full effect since July 2016, while the Agreement's provisional application has commenced in September 2014. Under 8th Chapter of Title V of the Association Agreement is foreseen the reform of PP and its harmonization with the EU legal acquis in this sphere, covering classic PP sector, utilities, concessions and review procedure together with capacity building at all levels inclusive for review body and ways of implementation the corresponding provisions. It envisages mutual access to public procurement markets on the basis of the principle of national treatment at national, regional and local level for public contracts and concessions in the public sector as well as in the utilities sector.

Due to the magnitude of the spending involved, PP can have a market impact beyond the mere quantities of goods and services purchased: through its procurement policies, the public sector can affect the structure of the market and the incentives of firms to compete more or less fiercely in the long run and thus bring efficiency into specific sectors of the economy and provide additional resources as a result of savings brought by increased competition and decrease of prices. Procurement policy therefore may be used as means to shape the longer term effects on competition in a particular industry or sector.

Competition between bidders provides the means for ensuring that public entities, and ultimately society as a whole, obtain the benefit of the best offers in terms of price, quality and innovation of the goods, services or works eventually purchased. Deficient competition means government institutions will have to spend more for the goods and services they buy and therefore increase the burden borne by the citizens. Promoting competition in PP is consistent with the principles that form the rules on public procurement, namely: free access to tenders, publicity and transparency of the procedures, equal non-discriminatory treatment of candidates both national and foreign, the quest for efficient use of public funds by requiring prior definition of the needs to be satisfied, safeguarding free competition and selection of the best economic offer.

Competition is a key factor in ensuring that governments, and the citizens, receive best value for money as a result of the procurement process. There are at least three channels through which competition can have desirable effects for procurement markets. First, with free entry and an absence of collusion, prices will be driven towards marginal costs. Second, suppliers will have an incentive to reduce their production and other costs over time. Third, competition serves as an important driver of innovation.

In small markets as is the case of the Republic of Moldova, competition in public procurement markets can be promoted by international liberalization. Participation in the WTO Agreement on Government Procurement (GPA), for example, promotes competition in at least four distinct ways. First, the GPA provides a vehicle for the progressive opening of the parties' markets to international competition. Second, the various provisions of the agreement relating to the provision of information provide a framework that is intended to ensure transparent and non-discriminatory conditions of competition between suppliers. Third, the agreement requires that all GPA parties put in place domestic review procedures through which suppliers can challenge questionable decisions by national procurement authorities. Fourth, the GPA provides recourse to the

WTO dispute settlement process in circumstances where parties believe that international competition has been suppressed.

However, merely opening bidding processes to foreign-based suppliers may not suffice to generate effective competition, if effective national competition laws and policies are not in place to deter collusion.

The PP reform should be approached in a wider manner. While working towards the full harmonization of the Moldovan legislation with the best international standards, the Government should undertake necessary actions to ensure that respective laws, regulations and rules are implemented and fulfilled in a corresponding manner, that a sound, effective and efficient PP system is developed and maintained in order to achieve value for money. In this regard, by the Government of Republic of Moldova has approved a National Strategy for the Development of PP System in 2016-2020 and an Action Plan for its implementation.

The legal framework of PP system in Moldova was relatively recently adjusted to EU 2004 Directives (mainly Directive 2004/18/CE of European Parliament and Counsel of 31 March 2004) by the approval of a new Public Procurement Law (PPL) (Law nr. 131 of 3 July 2015 in force since 1 May 2016). In general terms, the new PP law provides a satisfactory regulation framework and incorporates the fundamental principles of EU and WTO GPA as well as UNCITRAL Model Law on PP that regulate the public procurement procedures. Nevertheless, some of the provisions are not completely in line with EU requirements deriving from 2014 EU Directives and require further adjustments. The defense and utilities PP are still not regulated, and the legal framework covering concessions and public-private partnerships require revision and alignment to corresponding EU legislation.

The main goal in this regard is the creation of a functional, competitive, fair and transparent PP system that generates and ensures the trust of citizens of the country and international community in the procurement function of the state.

Hereinafter is presented the level of competition in the public procurement sector of Moldova in the period 2012-2016 in a comparative

view of the paper based procedures and ones conducted in the electronic system launched in 2012, although it was only partially used and had limited functionality. Currently in Moldova is implemented a new public procurement system based on a modern multi- platform architecture and on the golden triangle of collaboration between state, private sector and civil society. The new system is in the pilot phase now and an estimation of the increase of the competition level due to the implementation of the new electronic system will be possible after an extended period of use.

Analyzing the statistical data regarding the procurement of Moldova by the contracting authorities, in the period of 2012-2016, should be mentioned that PP procedures were carried out by two methods: a) Paper based procurement and b) by electronic means through the Automated Informational System Public Procurement State Registry (AIS PPSR).

In 2014, the largest volume of public procurement was recorded (more than 10 billion lei), which explains the large number of public procurement procedures undertaken. Subsequently, in the years 2015-2016 there was a decrease in the volume of public procurement, which was manifested by the decrease of the number of public procurement procedures carried out.

At the same time, there is a gradual increase in the number of public procurement procedures carried out through AIS PPSR.

It is worth mentioning that AIS PPSR was launched in 2012 on October 1, and was used by 34 contracting authorities to carry out procurement procedures. At the end of 2016, the number of contracting authorities using the system to carry out public procurement procedures reached 311, thus leading to the increase in the number of public procurement procedures conducted through SIA RSAP. The following types of public procurement procedures were used to carry out procurements through the system: Open tender; and request for price quotations (RfPQ) with publication of notice.

Figure nr. 1. Average number of bidders participating in public procurement procedures during 2012-2016

Source: Elaborated by the author based on data from www.etender.gov.md

Thus, it is noticed that the average number of bidders in the framework of the public procurement procedures carried out through AIS PPSR is gradually increasing, this being higher than in the framework of public procurement procedures in paper format. The use of electronic registry even with limited functionality leads to an increased level of transparency and thus has as an effect the increase of competition.

At the same time, competition was analyzed in the paper procurement procedures with and without the publication of notices in the Public Procurement Bulletin (PPB). The following level of competition was recorded in the public procurement procedures in the classic paper format:

Figure nr. 2. Average number of bidders in paper based procedures with and without publication of notices.

Source: Elaborated by the author based on data from www.etender.gov.md

It is noted that the level of competition in public procurement procedures with the publication of the notices in PPB is higher than in public procurement procedures without the publication of the notice (RfPQ without publication of the notice in PPB). At the same time, if we analyse the number of public procurement procedures and the average number of bidders, it is noted that in 2014, when the highest number of public procurement procedures was registered, the average number of bidders was the lowest, both for the public procurement procedures with the publication of the announcement of participation in PPB, and without its publication, and with the decrease in the number of public procurement

procedures carried out, it is registered an increase of the average number of submitted offers.

Below are presented the non-competitive procedures, correspondingly the evolution of public procurement procedures with 0-1 submitted offers in 2012 – 2016.

Figure nr. 3. Public procurement procedures with 0-1 submitted bids

Source: Elaborated by the author based on data from www.etender.gov.md

It can be noticed that, within the framework of the public procurement procedures carried out through AIS PPSR, a greater share of the procedures is registered with 0-1 submitted offers that is to some extent opposite to the normal expected effect, but this can be also explained by the parallel use of two systems as well as limited functionality of the AIS PPSR system.

Below will be analyzed the level of competition in selected sectors.

Figure nr. 4. Average number of submitted bids in procurement of food products

Source: Elaborated by the author based on data from www.etender.gov.md

In the procurement of food products, competition is higher than the average number of offers per procurement procedure for the period under review. It is noticed that the competition is even more significant in the procedures for the purchase of food products through AIS PPSR.

In procurement procedures of fuel and energy resources competition is about 2-3 bids, on average being slightly higher for the proceedings in paper format. Under the procedures for the procurement of petroleum products and energy resources through AIS PPSR, the number of offers is increasing with the increase in the number of conducted procedures. It should be noted that this sector is highly regulated one.

Figure nr. 5. Average number of submitted bids in procurement of automobiles and spare parts

Source: Elaborated by the author based on data from www.etender.gov.md

In the case of procurement of automobiles and spare parts, the competition tends to decrease, reaching the lowest values in 2016. At the same time, in the procurement procedures carried out through the AIS PPSR, the competition generally has a level slightly higher than in procedures conducted in paper format.

Figure nr. 6. Average number of submitted bids in procurement of construction materials

Source: Elaborated by the author based on data from www.etender.gov.md

In the case of procurement of construction materials, the competition generally has a fairly high level, registering higher values in the public procurement procedures carried out through AIS PPSR.

Figure nr. 7. Average number of submitted bids in procurement of computers, supplies and spare parts

Source: Elaborated by the author based on data from www.etender.gov.md

In public procurement of computers, supplies and spare parts there is a steady decline in the number of procedures performed. The level of competition, however, has a constant level, decreasing in the case of procedures in the paper format and increasing in the case of the procedures conducted through the AIS PPSR.

Procurement procedures for medicines and medical equipment are characterized by an increase in the number of procedures conducted through the AIS PPSR. This is due to the fact that starting with 2012 and until 2016 in the system were gradually introduced almost all contracting authorities purchasing medicines and medical equipment. Traditionally competition in these procurement procedures is high, with a trend of growth over the period under review in the AIS PPSR procedures reaching 5,75 bids per procedure in 2016.

In the procurement procedures for repair, construction and reconstruction works, traditionally there is satisfactory level of competition. There is an observed trend, competition is higher when the number of procurement procedures is lower, and vice versa, when the number of procedures for procurement of repair, construction and reconstruction works is increasing, the number of offers submitted is decreasing. The average number of submitted bids in 2016 reached 4,65 in electronic registry and 3,97 in paper based procedures.

In procurement procedures for repair of motor vehicles the number of procedures carried out tend to increase, while the level of competition tends to decrease. It was noticed that in the last three years competition is higher in the procurement procedures carried out through AIS PPSR.

In public procurement procedures for procurement of repair and maintenance of computers services competition has a constant level, being slightly higher for procurement procedures through the AIS PPSR. The number of procedures conducted for this type of procurements is generally small with a tendency to decrease per general and increase in case of public procurement procedures implemented through the AIS PPSR.

Conclusions and Recommendations

The legislative framework in general meets the minimum requirements in terms of promoting competition in public procurement, but the primary law has to be adjusted to the latest changes in international regulations on PP, mainly the implementation of 2014 EU Directives on

Public Procurement, with more emphasis on increasing the transparency level by implementation on the national level of full cycle electronic procurement.

Following the analysis of the structure of public procurement and average number of bids per sectors, can be concluded that the level of competition following the introduction of electronic notices have increased insignificantly with about 2% (the average number of bids is 4). The number of bids increases considerably (41%) if we compare the procedures conducted without publication of notices and with publication of notices. The level of uncompetitive bids is about 17% for procedures conducted in the current electronic system and about 10% for procedures conducted on paper. The sectors registering the highest average number of bids are: food products (average 7 bids per tender, the procedures conducted electronically register from 20% to 40% more bids per tender than those on paper); for construction materials also the average number of bids is about 4 and due to electronic means the number of bids has increased with about 30%). The same level of relative high level of competition is valid for medicines, for construction works, maintenance and repair services for ITC machines. In some sectors with high level of regulation, the average number of bids varies between 1,5 and 2,5, such as Internet services, fuels market, mobile communication services. At the same time, car repair services register a relatively low level of competition (varies between 2 and 3), while registering a positive trend of increase of number of bids following the introduction of electronic notices (between 15-40% in the past years).

Some recommendations:

- Enforcement of the legal provisions regarding the transparency, non-discrimination and competition in PP, especially by enlarging the access to a larger number of potential suppliers. This can be achieved by expanding the use of eProcurement on the national level, in line with 2014 Directives, by enabling the online submission of bids and online evaluation (as part of National Strategy).

- Implementation of WTO GPA provisions, as a GPA member by contributing to facilitating the access of foreign suppliers to Moldovan PP market.

- Building in the new eProcurement system that is currently under development an analytical tool that would contain red flags for automatic identifying procedures/behaviors that would potentially imply non-competitive actions/ measures etc. potential bid rigging and collusion.

- Increase the level of cooperation among institution in charge of PP regulation: PPA, MF, NCSA and CC.

- Capacity building and training of procurement officers concerning the risks related to non-competitive behavior and measures, ways to identify it.

- Finalizing the legislative reform, amending the primary law to bring it in line with current best international practice and adopt the secondary legislation that is currently missing for some procedures/methods of procurement.

- Increase the degree of transparency by making publicly available online as much information as possible regarding public procedures so that civil society will be able to actively monitor the public procurement sector.

- Centralization of procurement in certain spheres that would lead to increased competition due to more attractive potential contracts, and thus increased efficiency and value for public money.

- Ensuring that there will be one single point of access for all types of procedures and all information on public procurement.

Bibliography:

Government Procurement Agreement of World Trade Organization (2012 revised text).

Law on Public Procurement of Republic of Moldova, nr. 131 of 3 July 2015.

Competition and Procurement, OECD, 2011.

Republic of Moldova – European Union Association Agreement.

National Strategy for the Development of Public Procurement System of Moldova for 2016-2020, adopted on 14 December 2016.

https://ec.europa.eu/growth/single-market/public-procurement_en

<http://www.oecd.org/gov/public-procurement/>

www.etender.gov.md

www.statistica.md

Copyright©Dorina HARCENCO

The Rational Choice Theory as the Explanation of Coalition Formation in Germany 2017-2018

Ph.D. Student Viktoriia KHOMENKO

vikahomenko1996@ukr.net

Prof. Dr. Sci. Oleksandr DEMIANCHUK

demyanchuk@ukma.edu.ua

National University of Kyiv-Mohyla Academy, Ukraine

Abstract. The present article offers an explanation of the coalition negotiations and government formation in the German Federal Republic based on the rational choice theory and coalition formation theory. Despite numerous prognoses of the process failure and significant electoral defeat the Chancellor Angela Merkel has found the ways and arguments to convince political rivals on the Coalition Agreement. The success was immediately explained by some observers as the “conspiracy theory” practical realization. Nevertheless there is a deeper reasoning in the Merkel’s arguments first of all of the rational character. This article presents a description of the rationale from the Eastern Europe researchers’ point of view. The results of this study might be used as a methodological approach to complex political processes analysis.

Keywords: elections in Germany, coalition negotiations, Great Coalition, rational choice theory, coalition theory.

1. Problem statement

In the history of United Germany the formation of the government never lasted so long. It took almost 7 months to form a new government. Despite significant electoral defeats, German Chancellor Angela Merkel has managed to form a "Great Coalition" ("Große Koalition" in German) for the third time¹. The question remains whether the decision to form a "Great «Great Coalition»" was rationally and strategically correct?

¹ Foundation Democratic Initiatives. (2018). *Coalition in Germany: victories, losses, and results*. [online] Available at: <http://dif.org.ua/article/koalitsiada-v-nimechchini-peremogi-porazki-i-rezultati-bataliy> [Accessed 5 Jun. 2018].

Coalition talks in Germany have now become a very popular topic for research and analysis, and although the lack of full information about the decision-making process of the parties and their preferences in open access from the point of view of rational choice theory, coalition formation is covered in German media, publications, scientific articles, etc.

In this article, the formation of a coalition government is considered from the point of view of the rational choice theory. Assuming that the parties that formed the coalition used the rule of minimizing costs and maximizing benefits, it can be argued that an explanation of the coalition formation is possible in terms of this theory. The main actors who will be considered as rational members of the coalition formation are parties, whose efforts contribute to the formation of a coalition. First, a brief description of events describing the course of "coalitions" in Germany will be provided. The next part will give a brief description of the rational choice theory and the theory of coalitions, which closely linked to the latter. In the practical part, possible models of the process of making political decisions on the coalition formation will be considered, taking into account the interests of each party in terms of the rational choice theory and the theory of coalitions. The conclusions will suggest the predictions of further developments.

2. The course of events

On September 24, 2017, parliamentary elections were held in the Federal Republic of Germany. There were elected 598 members of the 19th Bundestag – the Federal Parliament of Germany. The Christian Democratic Union/Christian Social Union (CDU/CSU) and the Social Democratic Party of Germany (SPD) remained the two largest parties in the Bundestag, but both received far fewer votes than during the elections in 2013. The SPD has shown the worst result in its history and announced its withdrawal into

opposition². In addition, the Free Democratic Party (FDP) and Alternative for Germany (AfD) received enough votes to become participants in the Bundestag. These were the first federal elections in which the AfD received a sufficient number of votes to be represented in the Bundestag. Following the withdrawal of the SPD in the opposition, it was anticipated that a new coalition called "Jamaica"³ would be created (an idiomatic expression of the German political lexicon on the designation of the coalition of the three parties CDU / CSU, FDP and Alliance 90 / The Greens). The colors of the flag of Jamaica correspond to the party colors of the above-mentioned parties).

On the night of November 20, 2017, the FDP came out of negotiations on the creation of a new government coalition. In turn, the chairman of the FDP, Christian Lindner, said that "It is better not to govern than to govern badly"⁴. In a special congress of the SPD in January, 56 percent of delegates expressed support for the talks on a "Great Coalition", and a large number of the youth members wing of the party were strongly opposed⁵. On February 7, after lengthy negotiations, German conservatives headed by Merkel agreed with the leadership of the Social Democrats an agreement on the formation of a new government coalition. But the leaders of the SPD have put forward a condition: this agreement can be signed only if it is approved by ordinary party members – almost 460,000 party members. Voting by mail began on February 20 and lasted until March 4. During the March 4, 2018 mail voting, members of the Social Democratic Party spoke in favor of creating a "Great Coalition" with the Chancellor

² RBK Ukraine. (2017). *In the parliamentary elections in Germany, Merkel's conservative bloc won*. [online] Available at: <https://www.rbc.ua/ukr/news/parlamentskih-vyborah-germanii-oderzhal-pobedu-1506309039.html> [Accessed 5 Jun. 2018].

³ Monath H. *Jamaika-Koalition - Ein regionales Experiment* [online] Tagesspiegel. Available at: <https://www.tagesspiegel.de/politik/saarland-jamaika-koalition-ein-regionales-experiment/1614812.html>

⁴ Fried N. *FDP bricht Jamaika-Sondierungen ab* [online] Süddeutsche Zeitung. Available at: <http://www.sueddeutsche.de/politik/sondierung-fdp-bricht-jamaika-sondierungen-ab-1.3755800>

⁵ Glavcom.ua. (2018). *Social Democrats in Germany supported the creation of a coalition with Merkel*. [online] Available at: <https://glavcom.ua/world/observe/social-demokrati-nimechchini-pidtrimali-stvorenniya-koaliciji-z-merkel-478291.html> [Accessed 4 Jun. 2018].

Angela Merkel CDU / CSU⁶. "For" the creation of a "Great Coalition" voted 66.02 percent of party members, and "against" – 33.98 percent. This decision opened the way for the creation of a new government in the Federal Republic of Germany⁷.

3. Theoretical background

The classical economic theory of utilitarianism (Smith, Bentham)⁸ played a decisive role in establishing the methodology of the rational choice theory. This theory derives from the classical concept of "homo economicus," whose supporters argue that this concept is absolutely adequate for solving social problems. Becker⁹ believes that this approach reveals the essence of any human behavior¹⁰. According to the ideas of the Chicago school of economics, in politics, as well as in the economy, people operate in conditions of market competition, where each individual aspires to achieve its own goals¹¹.

In the rational choice theory one can distinguish the following basic "axioms":

- actors are trying to maximize their own benefits while minimizing costs;
- actors have conscious interests and specific goals that they try to achieve with the help of optimal means;

⁶ Glavcom.ua. (2018). *Social Democrats in Germany supported the creation of a coalition with Merkel*. [online] Available at: <https://glavcom.ua/world/observe/social-demokrati-nimechchini-pidtrimali-stvorenniya-koaliciji-z-merkel-478291.html> [Accessed 4 Jun. 2018].

⁷ Evropejska Pravda. (2018). *Merkel began new coalition talks*. [online] Available at: <https://www.eurointegration.com.ua/news/2018/01/7/7075762/> [Accessed 5 Jun. 2018].

⁸ Smith G., May D. 1980. *The Artificial Debate between Rationalist and Incrementalist Models of Decision Making*. — *Policy and Politics*, № 8.

⁹ Becker, G. (1976). *The Economic Approach to Human Behavior*. Chicago and London: The University of Chicago Press, 171.

¹⁰ Dekhtyarov, A. (2003). *Methodological foundations and conceptual models in the interpretation of political decisions (I)*. 167-169.

¹¹ Dekhtyarov, A. (2003). *Methodological foundations and conceptual models in the interpretation of political decisions (I)*. 167-169.

- actors have information about possible alternatives and their implementation;
- actors make choices between alternatives on the basis of stable preferences and rational rules.

When researching the formation of coalitions, the theory of coalitions¹² is often used. The theory of coalitions and the coalition of political forces is one of the most developed areas in political science, which is related to the theory of rational choice. To understand the process of a coalition government, it is not enough to confine itself to ideological and political frameworks. The rational interests of the parties must be also taken into account. According to Grofman, the behavior of parties can be estimated in three dimensions: office-, policy-, and vote-seeking¹³ dimensions.

Office-seeking parties aim to get seats in the government and create their own program in accordance with the programs of potential partners so that political senses do not become an obstacle in creating a coalition after the elections. At the same time, they are relatively flexible in the negotiations and are ready to give way to separate provisions for the entry into the government¹⁴. The main problem of this dimension is that it does not take into account the political component of the coalition, offers many options that cannot be realized in practice (for example, the union of the extreme left and right parties). In addition, this dimension cannot be explained by the emergence of minority coalitions.

Policy-seeking – parties are trying to get into the office, as this is the only opportunity for them to implement their policies, which are in their program. Accordingly, their negotiating position is more rigid, because work

¹² Oberreuter H. Stimmungsdemokratie. Zürich: 1987. 426-429.

¹³ Grofman B., Straffin P., Noviello N. The Sequential Dynamics of Cabinet Formation. Stochastic Error, and a Test of Competing Models // Schofield, N., Collective Decision-Making: Social Choice and Political Economy. Boston: Kluwer Academic Publishers, 1996. 281-293.

¹⁴ Klimovitsch, S. (2014). Coalition formation in Germany: process algorithm, prediction of consequences. *The Journal of the Perm State University*, 4(2014), 75.

in the government for them is not an end in itself, but only a way to implement their program provisions and fulfill the promises they gave their voters¹⁵.

Vote-seeking – the main task of the party is the maximization of votes in the next election. It is this fact that determines their behavior in the process of coalition negotiations, the willingness to join or not to join the coalition¹⁶.

A Model of coalition formation

In terms of the rational choice theory and coalition theory, one can construct a model that explains the prediction of coalitions. The starting point for using this model is the need for an absolute majority of votes in the parliament to form a coalition¹⁷. This model was developed by Klimovich, who used it to explain the formation of a coalition after the elections to the Bundestag in 2013. According to the model of Klimovitsch, there are 4 levels of coalition formation:

Level 1: The coalition must be minimal winning. At the same time, at this stage, those parties that are not in line with the winning principle that is, when it is impossible to form a government without an absolute majority, as well as minimal, allows them to include those parties that are necessary to ensure this absolute majority¹⁸.

Level 2: The coalition must be minimally linked to winning (*minimal connected winning*). At this level, from all variants of minimal winning, those

¹⁵ Klimovitsch, S. (2014). Coalition formation in Germany: process algorithm, prediction of consequences. *The Journal of the Perm State University*, 4(2014), 76.

¹⁶ Klimovitsch, S. (2014). Coalition formation in Germany: process algorithm, prediction of consequences. *The Journal of the Perm State University*, 4(2014), 76.

¹⁷ Klimovitsch, S. (2014). Coalition formation in Germany: process algorithm, prediction of consequences. *The Journal of the Perm State University*, 4(2014), 78.

¹⁸ Klimovich, S. (2014). Coalition formation in Germany: process algorithm, prediction of consequences. *The Journal of the Perm State University*, 4(2014), 76.

coalition that do not conform to the principle connected, are discarded, that is, they are not created on the principle of "left-right"¹⁹.

Level 3: The coalition is formed only by those parties that agree to join the coalition (that is, "not against"). At this stage, the parties that are not able to create a coalition and who denied entry into the coalition were withdrawn²⁰.

Level 4: The coalition is formed only by those parties that are mutually ready to enter the coalition. At this level, those parties that, 1) do not match the positive signals of the coalition, are shattered; 2) do not enter the opposite ideological blocks²¹. As a result, the most successful option for coalition remains.

4. Coalition formation 2017-2018

In 2017, the CDU / CSU again put forward a candidate from his party to the acting Chancellor of Germany – Angela Merkel. Martin Schulz represented the SPD. Less than a year ago, Martin Schulz, without exaggeration, triumphantly returned to German politics from the pan-European. He was almost unanimously elected chairman of the Social Democrats who were tired of the role of junior partner in the "Great coalition" and sought to take revenge at the parliamentary elections of 2017²². The real challenge for the party system of Germany was the rapidly growing popularity of the right-populist party Alternative for Germany (AfD).

¹⁹ Klimovitsch, S. (2014). Coalition formation in Germany: process algorithm, prediction of consequences. *The Journal of the Perm State University*, 4(2014), 70-87.

²⁰ Klimovitsch, S. (2014). Coalition formation in Germany: process algorithm, prediction of consequences. *The Journal of the Perm State University*, 4(2014), 70-87.

²¹ Klimovitsch, S. (2014). Coalition formation in Germany: process algorithm, prediction of consequences. *The Journal of the Perm State University*, 4(2014), 70-87.

²² Fond Democratic Initiatives. (2018). *Coalition in Germany: victories, losses, and results*. [online] Available at: <http://dif.org.ua/article/koalitsiada-v-nimechchini-peremogi-porazki-i-rezultati-bataliy> [Accessed 5 Jun. 2018].

Germany's election result, %

Source: <https://wahl.tagesschau.de/wahlen/2017-09-24-BT-DE/index-content.shtml>

The party bloc of the CDU / CSU won the election, gaining 33 percent of the vote. In comparison with the 2013 elections, the CDU lost 7.3 percent of votes, while the CSU dropped 1.2 percent. The SPD gained 20.5 percent of the vote. This is the worst result for the Social Democrats all the time after the Second World War. Compared with the 2013 elections, the Social Democrats worsened their results by 5.2 percent. The SPD intended to go into opposition. The right-wing AfD won 12.6 percent of the vote and got the third place in the elections. The FDP gained 10.7 percent of the vote and re-entered the Bundestag. The Left party gained 9.2 percent of the votes, Green – 8.9 percent²³. The turnout of voters was 76.2 percent. The distribution of seats between parties is presented below.

²³ Hrabka, A. (2017). *Germany has announced the preliminary results of the elections to the Bundestag*. [online] Deutsche Welle. Available at: <http://www.dw.com/uk/у-німеччині-оприлюднено-попередні-результати-виборів-до-бундестару/a-40666991> [Accessed 5 Jun. 2018].

Seat distribution in the German Bundestag post-election 2017

Source: <https://wahl.tagesschau.de/wahlen/2017-09-24-BT-DE/index-content.shtml>

According to the peculiarities of the German electoral system, 709 deputies may enter the new Bundestag. This is the largest number of deputies in the history of Germany. The Parliament of the previous convocation consisted of 630 deputies²⁴. Thus, the CDU / CSU alliance received 246 seats in the Bundestag of the new convocation, the SPD - 153 mandates, and AfD - 94. Free Democrats gained 80 seats in parliament, Alliance/The Green - 67, The Left - 69²⁵.

Let us consider the possible coalitions that could be created after the election.

²⁴ Hrabka, A. (2017). *Germany has announced the preliminary results of the elections to the Bundestag*. [online] Deutsche Welle. Available at: <http://www.dw.com/uk/у-німеччині-оприлюднено-попередні-результати-виборів-до-бундестару/a-40666991> [Accessed 5 Jun. 2018].

²⁵ Hrabka, A. (2017). *Germany has announced the preliminary results of the elections to the Bundestag*. [online] Deutsche Welle. Available at: <http://www.dw.com/uk/у-німеччині-оприлюднено-попередні-результати-виборів-до-бундестару/a-40666991> [Accessed 5 Jun. 2018].

Level 1: Of the 4 possible coalition options, only 3 would meet the “*minimum winning*” requirements: the CDU / CSU coalition, the Left and the Green, the Jamaica coalition or the "Great Coalition". Graphically, all possible coalitions are presented in the diagram:

Coalition generator 2017

Source: <http://www.spiegel.de/politik/deutschland/bundestagswahl-2017-alle-ergebnisse-im-ueberblick-a-1167247.html>

Level 2: Since the CDU / CSU, the Left and the Green parties are not on the right-left scale and have political contradictions, they also disappear at this stage. “*Minimal winning coalitions*” are "Jamaica" or "Great Coalition".

Level 3: The presence of negative coalitions signaled that, despite the openness of the representatives of the CDU / CSU to the cooperation

with the FDP, the latter decided to withdraw from the negotiations and thus excluded the possibility of a coalition with the CDU / CSU Union. There remains only one single option - "Great «Great Coalition»".

Level 4: Already at the stage of dropping out of coalition projects, it became clear that in addition to the option of the "Great Coalition", there would be no more options. Reflecting on whether the decision to create a "Great Coalition" was strategically correct, it should be noted that the decision was correct in general for Germany. The option of new elections was possible, and the SPD representatives, in their turn, could well benefit from re-election, but only if they did not change the transition to the opposition declared during the election campaign. Therefore, it can be argued that new elections would significantly degrade the reputation of the CDU / CSU and the SPD and strengthened the support of the right-populist party AfD²⁶.

The vote split delegates in late January almost equally to those who were openly opposed to a new coalition and those who were "for". The break in favor of the green light of a new alliance with the Christian Democrats in many respects occurred not even thanks to, but to the price, more precisely, the victim, the authority of Martin Schulz both in the party and in the political arena. That is, de facto Schultz really lost or lost as a politician not when his party suffered a crushing defeat in the elections, and when he began to stress that the "Great «Great Coalition»" suddenly became necessary and was the best of possible solutions²⁷. Martin Schulz wanted to compensate his authority for the post of German Foreign Minister, who is usually given to the "junior" coalition partner (in this case, the SPD because it has fewer votes). Therefore, the voluntary refusal of the

²⁶ Fond Democratic Initiatives. (2018). *Coalition in Germany: victories, losses, and results*. [online] Available at: <http://dif.org.ua/article/koalitsiada-v-nimechchini-peremogi-porazki-i-rezultati-bataliy> [Accessed 5 Jun. 2018].

²⁷ Hrabka, A. (2017). *Germany has announced the preliminary results of the elections to the Bundestag*. [online] Deutsche Welle. Available at: <http://www.dw.com/uk/у-німеччині-оприлюднено-попередні-результати-виборів-до-бундестару/a-40666991> [Accessed 5 Jun. 2018].

chairmanship of the party was forced, since it raised a wave of dissatisfaction with the policy of Schulz, and looked beneficial to the politician himself. However, Martin Schulz's proposed transition to the future government has come in opposition to the acting Foreign Minister Sigmar Gabriel. Thus, Martin Schultz himself became hostage to the situation he promoted and, due to the split within his own party of the SPD, on the principle of supporting the "Great «Great Coalition»", was forced to leave the office²⁸. It can be argued that this move was effective, since more than 66% of the SPD members voted in favor of the creation of a coalition with the CDU / CSU just after its abandonment.

For Angela Merkel, the "Great «Great Coalition»" looks like a logical step, but there were some contradictions within the bloc as well, due to the fact that most of the coalition agreement was in favor of the SPD.

There are notable changes in the new government: in particular, the head of the CSU Horst Seehofer heads the updated the Ministry of the Interior; Heiko Maas, the member of the SPD, the former Minister of Justice, became a Minister of Foreign Affairs, and the temporary acting head of the Social Democrats Olaf Scholz became a Minister of Finance. Particularly important for the SPD was the reduction of taxes and the abolition of the tax surcharge; citizens who receive the minimum wage should be exempted from paying taxes²⁹. In several steps, the so-called "surplus of solidarity" will be abolished in the tax on profits, which by 2021 will give German taxpayers savings of 10 billion euros. The healthcare sector has also become a stumbling block to the signing of a coalition agreement. SPD insisted on implementing Insurance (Bürgerversicherung), but the CDU / CSU rejected the proposal, as the introduction of equal pay for private insurance and

²⁸ Hrabaska, A. (2017). *Germany has announced the preliminary results of the elections to the Bundestag*. [online] Deutsche Welle. Available at: <http://www.dw.com/uk/у-німеччині-оприлюднено-попередні-результати-виборів-до-бундестару/a-40666991> [Accessed 5 Jun. 2018].

²⁹ Schuler K. *Keine Zeit für 177 Seiten? Worauf sich SPD und Union verständigt haben* [online] Zeit Online. Available at: <https://www.zeit.de/politik/deutschland/2018-02/grosse-koalition-koalitionsvertrag-union-spd>.

medical care services. Instead, a commission should be set up to create proposals for doctor payments³⁰. The SPD insisted on creating 8,000 jobs in older homes, raising wages for elderly people and people with disabilities; the average salary for patients' care should be 10.55 euro per hour. The CDU / CSU and SPD's aim to stabilize the ratio of pensions and average wages to 48% by 2025. Those who work will not have to deduct more than 20 percent of their income to the pension fund. Starting next year, the contributions of employees and their employers to the sickness cash desk will again be pared, which will slightly increase the financial burden on entrepreneurs³¹. The new government of Angela Merkel, at the request of the Social Democratic Party, has pledged, for example, to raise the monthly allowance for children at 25 euros per child, which is now 194 euros for the first two children, 200 euros – the third, and 225 euros for the fourth. Given the significant increase in rent in major German cities, the new government promises to help families build or buy their own home. In the first decade, they will be paid for such purposes 1,200 euros per year, if the total annual family income does not exceed 75,000 euros plus 15,000 euros for children³². Both parties have agreed in the field of migration policy and are aiming to prevent the influx of refugees by more than 180,000-220,000 people a year.

The situation shows that despite the formal victory of the CDU / CSU in an election, it might be the last cadence for Angela Merkel. There is no successor to her in the party today. And hence, the party's task for the next

³⁰ Schuler K. *Keine Zeit für 177 Seiten? Worauf sich SPD und Union verständigt haben* [online] Zeit Online. Available at: <https://www.zeit.de/politik/deutschland/2018-02/grosse-koalition-koalitionsvertrag-union-spd>

³¹ Jolkver, M. (2018). *Priorities of Merkel's Fourth Government*. [online] Deutsche Welle. Available at: <http://www.dw.com/uk/пріоритети-четвертого-уряду-ангели-меркель/a-42934451> [Accessed 8 Jun. 2018].

³² Jolkver, M. (2018). *Priorities of Merkel's Fourth Government*. [online] Deutsche Welle. Available at: <http://www.dw.com/uk/пріоритети-четвертого-уряду-ангели-меркель/a-42934451> [Accessed 8 Jun. 2018].

years will be not only the struggle for the return of the lost electorate but also the upbringing of a new party leader³³.

Conclusion

The article considered the formation of a coalition in Germany in 2017-2018 through the prism of the rational choice theory, namely through the theory of coalitions. The peculiarities of the theory of coalitions, namely, its four-stage coalition formation process, increase the explanatory force of the rational choice theory and allows it to be better used in explaining the formation of coalition governments. The main problem of the coalition theory is that it does not take into account the political component of the coalition, offers many options that cannot be realized in practice (for example, the union of the extreme left and right parties). In addition, this theory cannot explain the emergence of minority coalition or coalition surplus³⁴.

As a result of the study, it was found that besides the option of the "Great Coalition", there would be no more options. Reflecting on whether the decision to create a "Great Coalition" was strategically correct, it should be noted that the decision was correct in general. Nevertheless, the rational choice theory remains promising for use in political science and to explain the process of coalition formation.

So, the coalition agreement is an example of how the politicians can balance political forces to satisfy the needs of different electorates. The Social Democrats were able to defend their own interests in such socially important areas as: reviewing legislation in the area of pensions, migration policy, social policy, etc. In addition, portfolios of ministers of finance, labor, and social policy, and the post of Minister of Foreign Affairs were proposed

³³ Jolkver, M. (2018). *Priorities of Merkel's Fourth Government*. [online] Deutsche Welle. Available at: <http://www.dw.com/uk/пріоритети-четвертого-уряду-ангели-меркель/a-42934451> [Accessed 8 Jun. 2018].

³⁴ Fond Democratic Initiatives. (2018). *Coalition in Germany: victories, losses, and results*. [online] Available at: <http://dif.org.ua/article/koalitsiada-v-nimechchini-peremogi-porazki-i-rezultati-bataliy> [Accessed 5 Jun. 2018].

to the representatives of the SPD, which is uniquely important for the promotion of the SPD at the international level.

As for future prospects, the predictions are disappointing: leaders will either lose political ground under their feet (like Martin Schultz) or they will understand that the highest point of their political career has already passed and time is gradually being prepared to give way to new leaders from their camp (as Angela Merkel) . One can agree with the opinion of Maria Zolkina³⁵, the political analyst of the Ilk Kucheriv Democratic Initiatives Foundation, that "the parties themselves losing against the background of populism, suffering from the disappointment of voters who, from one, and from another camp," go "nowhere, but before radical "Alternatives to Germany". But with all this, German politics cannot be denied in a clear strategic sense, which the Social Democrats and the CDU / CSU are still practicing. Even if the German voter was tired of them."

Bibliography:

Becker, G. (1976). *The Economic Approach to Human Behavior*. Chicago and London: The University of Chicago Press, 171-195.

Budge I., Laver M. Office Seeking and Policy Pursuit in Coalition Theory // *Legislative Studies Quarterly*. 1986. № 11, 485-506.

Dekhtyarov, A. (2003). *Methodological foundations and conceptual models in the interpretation of political decisions (I)*, 159-170.

Evropejska Pravda. (2018). Merkel began new coalition talks. [online] Available at: <https://www.euointegration.com.ua/news/2018/01/7/7075762/>. [Accessed 5 Jun. 2018].

Fond Democratic Initiatives. (2018). *Coalition in Germany: victories, losses, and results*. [online] Available at: <http://dif.org.ua/article/koalitsiada-v-nimechchini-peremogi-porazki-i-rezultati-bataliy> [Accessed 5 Jun. 2018].

³⁵ Klimovitsch, S. (2014). Coalition formation in Germany: process algorithm, prediction of consequences. *The Journal of the Perm State University*, 4(2014), 74.

Fried N. *FDP bricht Jamaika-Sondierungen ab* [online] Süddeutsche Zeitung. Available at: <http://www.sueddeutsche.de/politik/sondierung-fdp-bricht-jamaika-sondierungen-ab-1.3755800>.

Glavcom.ua. (2018). *Social Democrats in Germany supported the creation of a coalition with Merkel*. [online] Available at: <https://glavcom.ua/world/observe/social-demokrati-nimechchini-pidtrimali-stvorenniya-koaliciji-z-merkel-478291.html>. [Accessed 4 Jun. 2018].

Grofman B., Straffin P., Noviello N. The Sequential Dynamics of Cabinet Formation. Stochastic Error, and a Test of Competing Models // Schofield, N., Collective Decision-Making: Social Choice and Political Economy. Boston: Kluwer Academic Publishers, 1996, 281-293.

Herbert A. Simon. Rationality as Process and as Product of Thought. Richard T. Ely Lecture // American Economic Review, May 1978, v.68, no.2, 1-16.

Hrabska, A. (2017). *Germany has announced the preliminary results of the elections to the Bundestag*. [online] Deutsche Welle. Available at: <http://www.dw.com/uk/у-німеччині-оприлюднено-попередні-результати-виборів-до-бундестагу/a-40666991> [Accessed 5 Jun. 2018].

Jolkver, M. (2018). *Priorities of Merkel's Fourth Government*. [online] Deutsche Welle. Available at: <http://www.dw.com/uk/пріоритети-четвертого-уряду-ангели-меркель/a-42934451>. [Accessed 8 Jun. 2018].

Klimovitsch, S. (2014). Coalition formation in Germany: process algorithm, prediction of consequences. *The Journal of the Perm State University*, 4(2014), 70-87.

Monath H. *Jamaika-Koalition – Ein regionales Experiment* [online] Tagesspiegel. Available at: <https://www.tagesspiegel.de/politik/saarland-jamaika-koalition-ein-regionales-experiment/1614812.html>.

Müller W. Koalitionstheorien // Helms, L., Jun, U., Politische Theorie und Vergleichende Regierungslehre. Frankfurt a.M./New York: Campus, 2004, 267-301. Riker W. H. *The Theory of Political Coalitions*. New Haven: Yale University Press, 1962.

Oberreuter H. *Stimmungsdemokratie*. Zürich: 1987, 426-429.

RBK Ukraine. (2017). *In the parliamentary elections in Germany, Merkel's conservative bloc won*. [online] Available at: <https://www.rbc.ua/ukr/news/parlamentskih-vyborah-germanii-oderzhal-pobedu-1506309039.html>. [Accessed 5 Jun. 2018].

Schuler K. *Keine Zeit für 177 Seiten? Worauf sich SPD und Union verständigt haben* [online] Zeit Online. Available at: <https://www.zeit.de/politik/deutschland/2018-02/grosse-koalition-koalitionsvertrag-union-spd>.

Simon H. 1947. *Administrative Behavior: A Study of Decision-Making Processes in Administrative Organizations*. N.Y.

Smith G., May D. 1980. *The Artificial Debate between Rationalist and Incrementalist Models of Decision Making*. – *Policy and Politics*, № 8.

Copyright©Viktoriiia KHOMENKO
Copyright©Oleksandr DEMIANCHUK

WHO'S WHO

Honorary Council

Co-Presidents:

Nico GROENENDIJK

Professor, Faculty of Behavioural, Management and Social Sciences, Twente University, Enschede, Netherlands

Co-Director, Centre for European Studies, Twente University, Enschede, Netherlands

Member, Assembly of European Regions, Strasbourg, France

President, Court of Auditors, Hengelo, Netherlands

President, ECSA Netherlands, Enschede, Netherlands

President, ECSA World, Damme, Belgium

Expert, Erasmus+, European Union

Jean Monnet Professor

Dusan SIDJANSKI

Professor Emeritus, Faculty of Economic and Social Sciences, European Institute, University of Geneva, Geneva, Switzerland

Board Member, Latsis Foundation, Geneva, Switzerland

Honorary President, European Centre for Culture, Geneva, Switzerland

Vice-Presidents:

Carlos Eduardo PACHECO AMARAL

Professor, Department of History, Philosophy and Social Sciences, University of the Azores, Ponta Delgada, Portugal

Coordinator, Research Unit Portugal and the Seas: Europeanism and the Transatlantic Relationship, Centre for Humanist Studies, University of the Azores, Ponta Delgada, Portugal

Jean Monnet Professor

Ioan HORGA

Professor, Department of International Relations and European Studies,
University of Oradea, Oradea, Romania

Dean, Faculty of History, International Relations, Political and
Communication Sciences, University of Oradea, Oradea, Romania

Expert, Romanian Agency for Quality Assurance in Higher Education,
Bucharest, Romania

President, Forum Oradea Foundation, Oradea, Romania

Director, Institute for Euroregional Studies, Oradea, Romania

Vice-President, ECSA Romania, Bucharest, Romania

Jean Monnet Professor

Helena TENDERA-WLASZCZUK

Professor, Cracow University of Economics, Cracow, Poland

Head, Department of European Economic Integration, Cracow University of
Economics, Cracow, Poland

Director, Jean Monnet Centre of Excellence, Cracow University of
Economics, Cracow, Poland

Expert, Erasmus+, European Union

Jean Monnet Professor

Members:

Francisco ALDECOA LUZARRAGA

Professor, Faculty of Political Science and Sociology, Complutense University
of Madrid, Madrid, Spain

Co-Director, Jean Monnet Centre for Excellence "Antonio Truyol",
Complutense University of Madrid, Madrid, Spain

Director, Tiempo de Paz, Madrid, Spain

Jean Monnet Professor

Alexandru ARSENI

Professor, Faculty of Law, State University of Moldova, Chisinau, Moldova
Lawyer, Chisinau Bar, Chisinau, Moldova

Elchin BABAYEV

Professor, Azerbaijan National Academy of Sciences, Baku, Azerbaijan
Executive Director, Science Development Foundation under the President of
the Republic of Azerbaijan, Baku, Azerbaijan

Enrique Lorenzo BANUS IRUSTA

Professor, School of Humanities, University of Piura, Piura, Peru
Dean, School of Humanities, University of Piura, Piura, Peru
Professor, University of Navarra, Pamplona, Spain
Jean Monnet Professor

Iordan Gheorghe BARBULESCU

Romanian Diplomat
Professor, National School of Political and Administrative Studies, Bucharest,
Romania
Dean, Department of International Relations and European Integration,
National School of Political and Administrative Studies, Bucharest, Romania
President, Senate of the National School of Political and Administrative
Studies, Bucharest, Romania
Expert, Romanian Agency for Quality Assurance in Higher Education,
Bucharest, Romania
President, ECSA Romania, Bucharest, Romania
Jean Monnet Professor

Leonce BEKEMANS

Professor, University of Padova, Padova, Italy
President, ECSA Belgium, Brussels, Belgium
Secretary-General, ECSA World, Damme, Belgium
Jean Monnet Professor

Christophe BERTOSSI

Professor, Paris Institute of Political Studies, Paris, France
Senior Researcher, French Institute of International Relations, Paris, France
Director, Centre for Migration and Citizenship, French Institute of International Relations, Paris, France
Expert, Erasmus+, European Union
Jean Monnet Professor

Mircea BRIE

Professor, Faculty of History, International Relations, Political and Communication Sciences, University of Oradea, Oradea, Romania
Editor-in-Chief, Annals of the University of Oradea, Series of International Relations and European Studies, Oradea, Romania
Jean Monnet Professor

Georges CONTOGEOGIS

Professor, Panteion University, Athens, Greece
Coordinator, Master Programme in European Studies, Panteion University, Athens, Greece
Scientific Director, National Centre for Scientific Research, Paris, France
Member, European Political Science Association, Wicklow, Ireland
Jean Monnet Professor

Larisa DERIGLAZOVA

Professor, Faculty of History, Tomsk State University, Tomsk, Russia
Director, Centre for European Studies, Tomsk State University, Tomsk,
Russia

Expert, Erasmus+, European Union

Jean Monnet Professor

Ioan DERSIDAN

Professor, Faculty of Letters, University of Oradea, Oradea, Romania
Council Member, Department of Romanian Language and Literature, Faculty
of Letters, University of Oradea, Oradea, Romania

Gaga GABRICHIDZE

Professor, School of Law, New Vision University, Tbilisi, Georgia
Dean, School of Law, New Vision University, Tbilisi, Georgia
Board Member, Association of European Studies for the Caucasus, Tbilisi,
Georgia

President, ECSA Georgia, Tbilisi, Georgia

Professor Jean Monnet

Ihar HANCHARONAK

Professor, Department of Doctoral Studies, Graduate School of the National
Academy of Sciences of Belarus, Minsk, Belarus

Rector, Graduate School of the National Academy of Sciences of Belarus,
Minsk, Belarus

Member, European Association for International Education, Amsterdam,
Netherlands

Wilfried HELLER

Professor Emeritus, Institute of Geography, University of Potsdam, Potsdam, Germany

Member, Research Centre for Germanic Connections with New Zealand and the Pacific, University of Auckland, Auckland, New Zealand

Asteris HULIARAS

Professor, Department of Political Science and International Relations, University of the Peloponnese, Corinth, Greece

Member, Hellenic Political Science Association, Athens, Greece

Jean Monnet Professor

Victor JUC

Professor, Institute for Legal and Political Research, Academy of Sciences of Moldova, Chisinau, Moldova

Deputy Director, Institute for Legal and Political Research, Academy of Sciences of Moldova, Chisinau, Moldova

Thomas KRUESSMANN

Professor, Faculty of Law, University of Graz, Graz, Austria

Director, Russian, East European and Eurasian Studies Centre, University of Graz, Graz, Austria

Chair, Supervisory Board of Higher School of Jurisprudence, Higher School of Economics, Moscow, Russia

President, Association of European Studies for the Caucasus, Tbilisi, Georgia

Jean Monnet Professor

Anatoliy KRUGLASHOV

Professor, Department of Political Science, “Juriy Fedkovych” Chernivtsi National University, Chernivtsi, Ukraine

Head, Department of Political Science, “Juriy Fedkovych” Chernivtsi National University, Chernivtsi, Ukraine

Director, Institute for European Integration and Regional Studies, “Juriy Fedkovych” Chernivtsi National University, Chernivtsi, Ukraine

Jean Monnet Professor

Ariane LANDUYT

Professor, Faculty of Political Science, University of Siena, Siena, Italy

Jean Monnet Professor

Ewa LATOSZEK

Professor, College of Economics and Social Sciences, Warsaw School of Economics, Warsaw, Poland

Expert, H2020, Bruxelles, Belgium

President, PECSA, Warsaw, Poland

Vice-President, ECSA World, Damme, Belgium

Jean Monnet Professor

Ani MATEI

Professor, Faculty of Public Administration, National School of Political and Administrative Studies, Bucharest, Romania

Secretary-General, National Commission of Romania for UNESCO, Bucharest, Romania

Jean Monnet Professor

Jose Maria MELLA MARQUEZ

Professor, Faculty of Economics and Business, Autonomous University of Madrid, Madrid, Spain

Jean Monnet Professor

Snezana PETROVA

Professor, Faculty of Philology “Blaze Koneski”, Ss. Cyril and Methodius University, Skopje, Macedonia

President, Association of French Language Teachers of Macedonia, Skopje, Macedonia

Oliver REISNER

Professor, Department for Central Asian Studies, Humboldt University, Berlin, Germany

Professor, School of Arts and Sciences, Ilia State University, Tbilisi, Georgia

Board Member, Association of European Studies for the Caucasus, Tbilisi, Georgia

Jean Monnet Professor

Maria Manuela TAVARES RIBEIRO

Professor, Faculty of Letters, University of Coimbra, Coimbra, Portugal

Director, PhD Programme in European Studies, University of Coimbra, Coimbra, Portugal

Corresponding Member, Academy of Sciences of Lisbon, Lisbon, Portugal

Member, ECSA Portugal, Lisbon, Portugal

Jean Monnet Professor

Grigore SILASI

Professor, Faculty of Economic Sciences, West University of Timisoara, Timisoara, Romania

Expert, Romanian Agency for Quality Assurance in Higher Education, Bucharest, Romania

Jean Monnet Professor

Mihai SLEAHTITCHI

Professor, Institute of Education, Chisinau, Moldova

Scientific Coordinator, Institute of Education, Chisinau, Moldova

Tudorel TOADER

Professor, Faculty of Law, “Alexandru Ioan Cuza” University of Iasi, Iasi, Romania

Minister of Justice, Bucharest, Romania

Honorary Member, Scientific Council of the Institute for Legal Research “Acad. Andrei Radulescu”, Romanian Academy, Bucharest, Romania

Member, Scientific Council of the National Institute of Magistracy, Bucharest, Romania

Member, Romanian Association for Constitutional Law, Iasi, Romania

Member, International Association of Criminal Law, Paris, France

Member, Commission of Venice, Venice, Italy

Grigore VASILESCU

Professor, Faculty of International Relations, Political and Administrative Sciences, State University of Moldova, Chisinau, Moldova

Director, Centre for European Studies, State University of Moldova, Chisinau, Moldova

Scientific Committee

Co-Presidents:

Marta PACHOCKA

Associate Professor, College of Economics and Social Sciences, Warsaw School of Economics, Warsaw, Poland

Member, Polish Economic Society, Warsaw, Poland

Member, University Association for Contemporary European Studies, Warsaw, Poland

Secretary-General, PECSA, Warsaw, Poland

Jean Monnet Professor

Victoria RODRIGUEZ PRIETO

Lecturer, Department of International Relations, Nebrija University, Madrid, Spain

Member, Spanish Association of Teachers in International Law and International Relations, Madrid, Spain

Member, Madrid Press Association, Madrid, Spain

Vice-Presidents:

Diana EERMA

Associate Professor, School of Economics and Business Administration, University of Tartu, Tartu, Estonia

Member, Estonian Economic Association, Tallinn, Estonia

Mihaela Narcisa NIEMCZIK-ARAMBASA

Researcher, Institute of Geography, University of Potsdam, Potsdam, Germany

Expert, Intercultural Counseling, Potsdam, Germany

Anna VISVIZI

Associate Professor, American College of Greece, Athens, Greece
Member, Academic Council, Institute of Diplomacy and Global Affairs,
American College of Greece, Athens, Greece
Director of Research, Institute for Central and Eastern Europe, Lublin,
Poland
Jean Monnet Professor

Members:

Paulo Emilio VAUTHIER BORGES DE MACEDO

Associate Professor, Faculty of Law, University of Rio de Janeiro, Rio de
Janeiro, Brazil
Vice-Coordinator, Master and Doctorate Programme in Law, Faculty of Law,
University of Rio de Janeiro, Rio de Janeiro, Brazil
Editor-in-Chief, Cosmopolitan Law Journal, Rio de Janeiro, Brazil
Legal Adviser, Brazilian Naval School, Rio de Janeiro, Brazil
President, Brazilian Section, Communio Journal, Washington, United States
of America

Paulo Jorge TAVARES CANELAS DE CASTRO

Associate Professor, Faculty of Law, University of Macau, SAR Macau, China
Coordinator, Master Programme in European Union Law, International
Law and Comparative Law, Faculty of Law, University of Macau, SAR Macau,
China
Judge, Red Cross International Humanitarian Law Moot Court, Hong Kong,
SAR Hong Kong, China
Member, Association of European Law and Economics, Coimbra, Portugal
Member, Association of Auditors on National Defence, Lisbon, Portugal
Member, Association of International Law, London, United Kingdom
President, ECSA Macau, SAR Macau, China
Jean Monnet Professor

Georgeta CISLARU

Associate Professor, French Language Centre, New Sorbonne University,
Paris, France

Member, Editorial Committee “Les Carnets du Cediscor”, SYLED-CEDISCOR,
New Sorbonne University, Paris, France

Simion COSTEA

Associate Professor, Department of History and International Relations,
“Petru Maior” University of Targu-Mures, Targu-Mures, Romania

Editor-in-Chief, L’Europe unie, Paris, France

Policy Officer, European Commission, Brussels, Belgium

Jean Monnet Professor

Klara CZIMRE

Associate Professor, Department of Social Geography and Regional
Development Planning, University of Debrecen, Debrecen, Hungary

Dorin DOLGHI

Lecturer, Department of International Relations and European Studies,
University of Oradea, Oradea, Romania

Editor-in-Chief, Romanian Journal of Security Studies, Oradea, Romania

Jean Monnet Professor

Sanna ELFVING

Senior Lecturer, School of Law, University of Bradford, Bradford, United
Kingdom

Programme Leader, LLM Programme, School of Law, University of Bradford,
Bradford, United Kingdom

Associate Fellow, Higher Education Academy, York, United Kingdom

Member, United Kingdom Environmental Law Association, Dorking, United
Kingdom

Member, Socio-Legal Studies Association, Birmingham, United Kingdom

Sedef EYLEMER

Associate Professor, Department of International Relations, Izmir Katip Celebi University, Izmir, Turkey

Jean Monnet Professor

Agnieszka KLOS

Associate Professor, College of Economics and Social Sciences, Warsaw School of Economics, Warsaw, Poland

Vice-President, PECSA, Warsaw, Poland

Jean Monnet Professor

Eva KOVAROVA

Associate Professor, Department of Public Economics, Technical University of Ostrava, Ostrava, Czechia

Aurelian LAVRIC

Associate Professor, “Alexandru cel Bun” Military Academy, Chisinau, Moldova

Senior Researcher, Centre for Defence and Security Strategic Studies, “Alexandru cel Bun” Military Academy, Chisinau, Moldova

Kerry LONGHURST

Associate Professor, European Research Institute, University of Birmingham, Birmingham, United Kingdom

Associate Professor, Department of International Relations and Sustainable Development, Collegium Civitas, Warsaw, Poland

Deputy Head, Department of International Relations and Sustainable Development, Collegium Civitas, Warsaw, Poland

Associate Professor, Department of European Interdisciplinary Studies, College of Europe, Warsaw, Poland

Jean Monnet Professor

Jose Luis DE SALES MARQUES

President, Institute of European Studies of Macau, SAR Macau, China
President, Council of Macanese Communities, SAR Macau, China
Vice-President, Maritime Silk Road Association, SAR Macau, China
Member, Board of the Portuguese School Foundation, SAR Macau, China
Member, Board of Trustees of the Cultural Industries Fund, SAR Macau, China

Marius MATICHESCU

Lecturer, Department of Sociology, West University of Timisoara, Timisoara, Romania
Jean Monnet Professor

Cristina-Maria MATIUTA

Associate Professor, Faculty of History, International Relations, Political and Communication Sciences, University of Oradea, Oradea, Romania
Member, Research Centre on Identity and Migration, University of Oradea, Oradea, Romania
Member, Romanian Society of Political Sciences, Bucharest, Romania
Editor-in-Chief, Journal of Identity and Migration Studies, Oradea, Romania
Jean Monnet Professor

Anne MCNAUGHTON

Senior Lecturer, College of Law, Australian National University, Canberra, Australia
Adjunct-Director, Centre for European Studies, Australian National University, Canberra, Australia
Fellow, European Law Institute, Vienna, Austria

Solomon MENABDISHVILI

Associate Professor, School of Law, Caucasus University, Tbilisi, Georgia

Associate Professor, School of Law, International Black Sea University, Tbilisi, Georgia

Visiting Scholar, School of Law, Durham University, United Kingdom

Director, Centre for Competition Law and Consumer Protection, Tbilisi, Georgia

Mihaela Daciana NATEA

Senior Lecturer, Department of History and Political Science, University of Medicine, Pharmacy, Sciences and Technology, Targu-Mures, Romania

Director, Department of History and Political Science, University of Medicine, Pharmacy, Sciences and Technology, Targu-Mures, Romania

Giancarlo NICOLI

Director, Italian Cultural Centre, Chisinau, Moldova

Editor-in-Chief, Il Ponte, Chisinau, Moldova

President, Moldova Film Commission, Chisinau, Moldova

Danielle OMER

Associate Professor, Faculty of Arts, Humanities and Social Sciences, University of Maine, Le Mans, France

Member, Centre for Research in Education, Nantes, France

Moses ONYANGO

Lecturer, School of Humanities and Social Sciences, United States International University – Africa, Nairobi, Kenya

Director, Institute for Public Policy and International Affairs, United States International University – Africa, Nairobi, Kenya

Lecturer, University of Johannesburg, Johannesburg, South Africa

Member, Higher Education Academy, York, United Kingdom

Marco OROFINO

Associate Professor, Department of International, Legal, Historical and Political Studies, University of Milan, Milan, Italy

Jean Monnet Professor

Saverina PASHO

Associate Professor, Faculty of Foreign Languages, University of Tirana, Tirana, Albania

Vice-President, French Alliance of Albania, Tirana, Albania

Valentin PETRUSENKO

Associate Professor, Faculty of Philosophy and History, Plovdiv University, Plovdiv, Bulgaria

Vice-Dean, Faculty of Philosophy and History, Plovdiv University, Plovdiv, Bulgaria

Member, Bulgarian American Studies Association, Sofia, Bulgaria

Jean Monnet Professor

Vadim PISTRINCIUC

Moldovan Legislator

Lecturer, Faculty of Sociology and Social Work, State University of Moldova, Chisinau, Moldova

Galina POGONET

Associate Professor, Faculty of Law, International Relations Institute of Moldova, Chisinau, Moldova

Lawyer, Chisinau Bar, Chisinau, Moldova

István József POLGÁR

Lecturer, Department of International Relations and European Studies, University of Oradea, Oradea, Romania

Jean Monnet Professor

Ada-Iuliana POPESCU

Lecturer, Faculty of Economics and Business Administration, “Alexandru Ioan Cuza” University of Iasi, Iasi, Romania

Lawyer, Iasi Bar, Iasi, Romania

Member, Romanian Union of Lawyers, Bucharest, Romania

Member, American Bar Association, Chicago, United States of America

Lehte ROOTS

Associate Professor, School of Law, Tallinn University of Technology, Tallinn, Estonia

Head, Department of Public Law, School of Law, Tallinn University of Technology, Tallinn, Estonia

Member, Estonian Bar Association, Tallinn, Estonia

Member, Estonian Refugee Council, Tallinn, Estonia

Vice-President, ECSA Estonia, Tallinn, Estonia

Jean Monnet Professor

Iryna SIKORSKA

Senior Researcher, Institute of Higher Education, National Academy of Educational Sciences, Kiev, Ukraine

Expert, National Team of Higher Education Reform, Kiev, Ukraine

President, Ukrainian Association of Professors and Researchers of European Integration, Kiev, Ukraine

Jean Monnet Professor

Zorina SISCAN

Associate Professor, Faculty of International Economic Relations, Academy of Economic Studies of Moldova, Chisinau, Moldova

Expert, EUBAM, Chisinau, Moldova

Member, Assorts Experts Team, Bruxelles, Belgium

Beatrice STEFANESCU

Lecturer, Faculty of Law, “Mihail Kogalniceanu” University, Iasi, Romania
Judge, Iasi Court, Iasi, Romania

Alina STOICA

Lecturer, Department of International Relations and European Studies,
University of Oradea, Oradea, Romania
Jean Monnet Professor

Aleksandra SZCZERBA-ZAWADA

Associate Professor, Faculty of Public Administration and National Security,
“Jacob of Paradyz” University of Applied Sciences, Gorzow Wielkopolski,
Poland

Head, Department of Public Administration, “Jacob of Paradyz” University of
Applied Sciences, Gorzow Wielkopolski, Poland

Member, PECSA, Warsaw, Poland

Jean Monnet Professor

Jean-Marc TROUILLE

Senior Lecturer, School of Management, University of Bradford, Bradford,
United Kingdom

Director, Master Programme in European and International Business
Management Deusto / Audencia / Bradford (EIBM), Bradford, United
Kingdom

Member, University Association for Contemporary European Studies,
London, United Kingdom

Jean Monnet Professor

Lika TSULADZE

Associate Professor, Faculty of Social and Political Sciences, “Ivane Javakhishvili” Tbilisi State University, Tbilisi, Georgia

Director, Centre for Social Sciences, Tbilisi, Georgia

Jean Monnet Professor

Penine UWIMBABAZI

Associate Professor, Department of Peace and Conflict Studies, Protestant Institute of Arts and Social Studies, Butare, Rwanda

Director, Directorate of Quality Assurance, Protestant Institute of Arts and Social Studies, Butare, Rwanda

Alexis VAHLAS

Associate Professor, Faculty of Law, Political Sciences and Management, University of Strasbourg, France

Director, Master Programme in EU Law, Institute for Political Studies, Strasbourg, France

Jean Monnet Professor

Diego VARELA PEDREIRA

Associate Professor, Faculty of Economics and Business, University of A Coruna, Spain

Executive Editor, European Journal of Government and Economics, A Coruna, Spain

Jean Monnet Professor

Tigran YEPREMYAN

Lecturer, Department of World History, Yerevan State University, Yerevan, Armenia

Coordinator, Expert Group on Politics at “Devout Generation” Foundation, Yerevan, Armenia

Researcher, Armenian Virtual College, Yerevan, Armenia

Adviser, National Assembly of Armenia, Yerevan, Armenia

President, ECSA Armenia, Yerevan, Armenia

Khaydarali YUNUSOV

Lecturer, Faculty of Law, University of World Economy and Diplomacy, Tashkent, Uzbekistan

Member, Uzbek Association of International Law, Tashkent, Uzbekistan

Member, American Society of International Law, Washington, United States of America

Jean Monnet Professor

Editorial Board

Editor-in-Chief:

Vasile CUCERESCU

President, ECSA Moldova, Chisinau, Moldova

Member, Association of European Studies for the Caucasus, Tbilisi, Georgia

Member, Eurolimes, Oradea, Romania

Jean Monnet Professor

First Deputy Editor-in-chief:

Ludmila ROSCA

Coordinator, EU Centre for Information and Communication, ECSA Moldova, Chisinau, Moldova

Professor, Department of International Relations and Political Science, International Relations Institute of Moldova, Chisinau, Moldova

Vice-Rector, International Relations Institute of Moldova, Chisinau, Moldova

Jean Monnet Professor

Deputy Editor-in-chief:

Mihai HACHI

Coordinator, EU Centre for Economic Studies, ECSA Moldova, Chisinau, Moldova

Associate Professor, Department of International Economic Relations, Academy of Economic Studies of Moldova, Chisinau, Moldova

Editors:

Ion BURUIANA

Coordinator, EU Centre for Human Rights, ECSA Moldova, Chisinau, Moldova

Associate Professor, Department of International Law, International Relations Institute of Moldova, Chisinau, Moldova

Lawyer, Chisinau Bar, Chisinau, Moldova

Jean Monnet Professor

Carolina DODU-SAVCA

Coordinator, EU Centre for Intercultural Dialogue, ECSA Moldova, Chisinau, Moldova

Associate Professor, Faculty of Letters and Journalism, Free International University of Moldova, Chisinau, Moldova

Member, French Alliance in Moldova, Chisinau, Moldova

Violeta MELNIC

Coordinator, EU Centre for Legal Studies, ECSA Moldova, Chisinau, Moldova

Associate Professor, Department of International Law, International Relations Institute of Moldova, Chisinau, Moldova

Member, Disciplinary Board of Judicial Executives, Chisinau, Moldova

Elena PRUS

Vice-President, ECSA Moldova, Chisinau, Moldova

Professor, Faculty of Letters and Journalism, Free International University of Moldova, Chisinau, Moldova

Vice-Rector, Free International University of Moldova, Chisinau, Moldova

Expert, Bureau for Central and Eastern Europe, Francophone University Agency, Bucharest, Romania

Expert, Horizon 2020, European Union

Alexandru ZNAGOVAN

Member, EU Centre for Information and Communication, ECSA Moldova, Chisinau, Moldova

Associate Professor, "Nicolae Testemitanu" State University of Medicine and Pharmacy, Chisinau, Moldova

9772345104101

ISSN 2345-1041

ISSN-L 2345-1041